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Simulation Games

Insights into International
Practice and Research

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Management
Simulation

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Simulation Games – Insights into International Practice and Research

ISAGA Conference 2025: Best of Two Worlds

The 56th ISAGA Conference 2025 took place from 15 to 18 July 2025 in Stuttgart at Baden-Württemberg Cooperative State University (DHBW Stuttgart) and its Centre for Management Simulation (ZMS), in cooperation with the International Simulation and Gaming Association (ISAGA) and the Swiss Austrian German Simulation and Gaming Association (SAGSAGA). The conference theme, “Shaping the Future through Simulation & Gaming”, invited an international and interdisciplinary community to explore how simulation games can help people understand complex systems, support learning, and facilitate dialogue about possible futures.

A distinctive feature of the 2025 ISAGA Conference was the deliberate integration of the European Simulation and Gaming Forum (EUPF) into the ISAGA Conference. Under the motto “Best of Two Worlds”, the event brought together ISAGA’s scholarly rigor and international research discourse with its focus on application and its community-of-practice orientation that characterize SAGSAGA and the EUPF. This combination was not merely programmatic; it was evident across the conference formats, fostering exchange between researchers, educators, designers, facilitators, and practitioners working in applied settings.

From Contribution to Publication

Out of 51 submissions, this volume in the ZMS publication series brings together 19 contributions presented at the ISAGA Conference 2025. In line with the conference’s “Best of Two Worlds” approach, most of the contributions in this volume deliberately foreground practice-oriented insights. They highlight application, implementation, facilitation, and transferable design knowledge, and share what can be learned from simulation and gaming in use: design decisions made under real-world constraints, facilitation strategies, implementation experiences, evaluation in applied settings, and reflections on how approaches can be adapted and transferred to other contexts.

All submissions to the conference underwent a double-blind peer-review process conducted by members of the Scientific Committee. Each manuscript was assigned to at least two reviewers, and cases requiring further clarification were discussed in a meta-review by the conference chairs. Following the conference, authors revised their papers based on additional editorial feedback, resulting in the final contributions published in this volume.

Structure of This Volume

To guide readers through the thematic breadth of applied work, the contributions are organized into five topical sections.

1. Sustainability

The first section demonstrates how simulation and gaming can support sustainable transitions and SDG-related learning and decision-making. Contributions range from a strategy-game approach to multi-stakeholder dialogue on low-carbon transition pathways to practical perspectives on educational games for sustainable development and awareness-creating games addressing issues such as waste management. Further contributions discuss how SDG-oriented games can move players from awareness to alignment and accountability, and how localized SDG simulation models can support transversal and cross-sector thinking in concrete regional contexts.

2. Education

The Education section centers on practical teaching and learning settings where games and simulations help to build future-relevant competencies. The topics in this section include simulated conflicts to prepare educators for teaching in crisis contexts, individualized immersive VR approaches in geography teaching, and reflective methods for tracking students' learning journeys during game development. Additional contributions discuss fostering digital literacies with elements of game-based learning and designing/assessing digital games for language-related perceptual skills.

3. Organizational systems & process management

This section highlights applied simulation and systems thinking in organizational contexts and management education. It includes work on using systems thinking and gamification to improve the acceptance of agile practices (such as Scrum) among decision-makers, a field report on implementing the ERPsim business simulation in higher education, and a systems-thinking-oriented simulation game based on the Impaction Method. Together, these contributions emphasize the organizational conditions under which simulation games create value – particularly when change, process management, and shared understanding are at stake.

4. Methods, tools & applied practices

The fourth section serves as an applied "toolbox" and highlights methods, tools, and applied practices. Contributions include an experiential learning simulation in the field of legal technology, a reflection on engaging conference participants through game formats that bridge plenary inputs and action, and a case-based analysis of how rules and facilitation interact in group formation and reconstruction. The section closes with a contribution on citizen science and simulation games for empowering urban transformation – illustrating how participatory approaches can connect local action, civic engagement, and game-based exploration.

5. Disaster management & urban security

The final section turns to the themes of risk, resilience, and urban security. One contribution transforms complex hydrological flood data into interactive visual narratives, highlighting how data storytelling can support engagement, understanding, and communication in flood contexts. Another contribution addresses urban security and resilience through an applied serious game perspective, focusing on design and facilitation choices that help participants collaborate on spatial or urban challenges.

Acknowledgments

A conference – and the publications that emerge from it – depend on collective effort. We thank all authors for sharing their work. We also extend our appreciation to everyone who contributed to the review, editorial, and organizational work around the 56th ISAGA Conference 2025, and to the broader conference community whose discussions and workshops brought the “Best of two worlds” to life during the event.

This volume serves not only as documentation of the 2025 ISAGA Conference, but also as a practical resource. It provides concrete inspiration and guidance for designing, facilitating, evaluating, and adapting simulation and gaming approaches in ways that help to address challenges in sustainability, resilience, education, and organizational development.

Stuttgart, April 2026

Friedrich Trautwein, Birgit Zürn, Gabriel Gaa,
Maren Schaal, Tobias Alf & Annemarie Zimmer

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Chapter Sustainability

Nicole Ponta, Céline Dillmann, Anne Dray, Julianna Nates, Annabelle Moreau Santos, Antoine Godin & Claude A. Garcia

PowerShift: Supporting Multi-Stakeholder Dialogue on the Low-Carbon Transition in Colombia Using a Strategy Game

Abstract

Colombia, an oil-producing country with a strong dependency on oil exports, faces the challenge of balancing economic stability with a political ambition to phase out fossil fuels and promote a just and sustainable energy transition. This paper presents PowerShift, a strategy game-based intervention implemented as a practical tool to support policy dialogues on Colombia's Climate Action Plan. PowerShift facilitated a multi-stakeholder dialogue across two series of workshops, engaging over 150 participants from ministries, financial and private sectors, and civil society to simulate the socio-economic and environmental dynamics of a low-carbon transition in a setting reflective of Colombian realities. Participants adopted roles as households, entrepreneurs, and government representatives, addressing critical scenarios such as oil reserve depletion, tax reforms, and climate El Niño events. While playing, they shaped and responded to challenges including monetary instability, deforestation, resource scarcity, and unrest caused by deteriorating social conditions monitored through an equivalent of the Human Development Index (HDI). This approach fostered insights into collaborative governance, strategic foresight, and inter-sectoral policy formulation, demonstrating the potential of strategy games to promote shared understanding, explore alternative policy pathways, and support policy outcomes that take full account of citizens and economic actors' agency. PowerShift offers a replicable model for any emerging economy reliant on fossil fuels to initiate policy dialogues on sustainable transition pathways, fostering the development of context-specific strategies and collective action towards a low-carbon future.

Keywords: Low-carbon transition, Colombia, Strategy game, Multi-stakeholder dialogue, Macroeconomic model, Natural resource extraction.

1 Introduction

Colombia faces significant challenges in transitioning to a low-carbon economy while maintaining economic growth and addressing social inequalities. The country's dependence on extractive industries such as fossil fuels and mining creates economic vulnerabilities and environmental pressures (Godin et al., 2023; Bernal-Ramírez et al., 2022). Achieving the ambitious targets of the Paris Agreement, including a 51% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by 2030, requires systemic changes that reconcile diverse stakeholder interests and mitigate socio-economic disruptions (Daumas, 2023). In this context, participatory approaches and serious games emerge as powerful tools for policymaking (Garcia, 2022). They enable stakeholders from various sectors to collaboratively explore complex dynamics, test strategies, and understand the trade-

offs inherent in decision-making processes. PowerShift was designed to address these challenges by simulating Colombia’s macroeconomic system and fostering dialogue among key actors, including government officials, private-sector representatives, and civil society. The game’s objectives are to enhance systems thinking, support multi-stakeholder dialogue, and foster strategic thinking on sustainable pathways for Colombia’s energy transition. The project “Supporting multi-stakeholder dialogue on national determined contribution (NDC) trajectories in Colombia using strategic games” is a partnership between the French Development Agency (AFD), LEAF Inspiring Change, Bern University of Applied Sciences (BFH), ETH Zürich, and the University of Lausanne (Unil). It builds on a long-term collaboration between AFD, the National Planning Department, the Colombian Ministry of Finance, and the National University of Colombia that led to the development of the GEMMES macroeconomic model to assess Colombia’s economic opportunities and vulnerabilities in the global energy transition (Godin et al., 2024). This paper presents the co-creation of PowerShift, a strategy game that aims to (1) strengthen understanding of the macroeconomic aspects of the energy transition in Colombia, (2) identify stakeholders’ mental models concerning the energy transition and global low-carbon shift, and (3) reinforce high-level inter-ministerial dialogue.

2 Methodology

The consortium headed a participatory process to develop a strategy game simulating Colombia’s macroeconomic challenges in transitioning to a low-carbon economy. Crafted through collaboration, the game was born from a participatory and iterative process following a three-phase journey, as described in Figure 1. Throughout the whole process, a monitoring and evaluation process was implemented with ex-ante and ex-post questionnaires and interviews at given stages.

Figure 1. The Three-Phase Process From Co-Conceptualization of the Model to Game Implementation and Dissemination to Support Political Dialogue Towards Transition.

2.1 Phase 1: Modeling and validation

Between February and March 2024, a series of six online brainstorming sessions were facilitated by LEAF to develop the game’s conceptual foundation. In total, 13 participants from two Colombian ministries (Finance and Public Credit, Mining, and Energy), a government agency (National Planning Department), and the AFD attended one or several of the sessions. The first

session introduced participants to an existing serious game to illustrate the potential of a final product. In the following five sessions we applied the ARDI methodology to explore key elements of Colombia’s low-carbon transition and collaboratively built a preliminary conceptual model connecting actors, resources, and processes involved in reducing fossil fuel use over the next 20 years. More specifically, this methodology helped to systematically analyze the system by identifying

- (1) the boundaries of the system (scope and limits),
- (2) the main actors (relevant stakeholders, power dynamics, and exposure to the issues),
- (3) the main resources (physical and financial components),
- (4) the main dynamics (processes and temporal aspects associated with the energy transition), and
- (5) the main interactions (links between actors and resources).

Through this process, the participants increased awareness of strategy games as decision-support tools, defined and clarified expectations for the research project, generated knowledge on Colombia’s low-carbon economic transition, fostered trust between Colombian stakeholders and LEAF/AFD teams, and co-created a shared representation of Colombia’s transition pathway. Once the participatory sessions were concluded, the preliminary model was refined through literature review and expert interviews. The finalized model representing the financial and real economy flows of the country was presented and validated with Colombian partners through a final participatory session.

2.2 Phase 2: Scenario exploration and dialogue facilitation

Building on the conceptual model, PowerShift was designed as a strategy game to simulate the social, environmental, and economic challenges of transitioning from an extractive to a sustainable economy.

Figure 2. Number of Participants and Distribution of Roles per Type of Organization for the Nine Game Sessions Organized in Bogotá Between June and September 2024.

The internal crash tests and refinements took place between May and June 2024 with AFD representatives, Colombian government officials, and energy transition experts. Nine game sessions were then organized between June and September 2024 in Bogotá, involving a total of 158 participants from 57 organizations, including ministries, governmental agencies, financial institutions, the private sector, and civil society (Figure 2).

Among the participants, 77 were women; the sessions thus had a balanced gender ratio of approximately 48%. The session analysis presented below focuses specifically on the workshops conducted in Colombia. A subsequent session was held in Switzerland in October 2024 with a primarily academic audience, not as part of the testing phase but rather as an opportunity to present and promote the finalized tool.

2.3 Phase 3: Restitutions

Phase 3 began in July and October 2024 with the production of communication materials immediately following the game sessions and will continue through a series of webinars, podcast, and additional publications between March and June 2025. After each mission, LEAF produced a flyer summarizing the key findings of the game sessions and debriefings. In addition, two videos were produced, one describing the game and its implementation, and another featuring testimonials from participants recorded after a game session. In March 2025, two webinars were organized: One in Spanish for Colombian participants and another in English for the funding agency and partner, AFD. Meanwhile, other communication materials – including press articles, and a scientific publication – are in progress. Additionally, further game sessions in Paris. Two sessions were organized in May 2025, each in a different setting. The first took place during the AFD Group's Innovation Spring Week, where 16 AFD staff members participated in an internal experimentation session. The objective was to test the use of serious games as facilitation tools within the organization. The session allowed staff from different departments to engage collectively with transition-related dilemmas and to reflect on how such formats could support internal learning and dialogue across teams working on climate and development issues.

A second session was organized at the Académie du Climat in Paris, bringing together around 25 participants, including journalists, researchers, public officials, consultants and activists. The diversity of the group led to particularly lively exchanges during the role-playing exercise. As reported in a press article covering the event, participants debated issues such as the political justification of continued oil extraction, the management of social protests blocking infrastructures, and the tensions between environmental objectives and fiscal dependence on hydrocarbons.

3 Powershift

3.1 Game structure

This section briefly presents the main components, storyline, and dynamics of PowerShift. The game challenges players to transition the fictional country of Columbia from an extractive economy to a low-carbon future while maintaining economic stability and ensuring the well-being of its citizens. Players assume one of three roles: households, entrepreneurs, or government.

Households must meet their needs for a sufficient diet, health, fuel, and electricity by securing employment with private and public companies or relying on the informal sector and/or converting land into a profitable business asset.

Industries manage companies by securing inputs (including labor) and selling products domestically or internationally. They can expand or invest in different sectors. PetrolEco, the state-controlled oil company, holds a key role.

The government manages a budget to support ministries and promote the transition. Dependent on revenues from extractive industries, it must meet Paris Agreement targets while balancing household needs and economic stability.

PowerShift requires several facilitators to operate smoothly (Figure 3):

- A game master to guide players through the process and lead debriefing;
- Two facilitators to manage the international market, banking system, and statistics office while collecting data and supporting players.

Figure 3. Overview of a Game Session and Distributions of Players: Households (Left), Industries (Center), and the Government (Right). The Game Master and Facilitators Move Around the Room and Follow Players' Actions.

All transactions use the in-game currency, Corona (₴), and gameplay is driven by tokens representing key resources:

Energy and minerals:

1. Petroleum is a finite resource central to the economy. Managed by *PetrolEco*, it is extracted from proven reserves and can be stored or exported. Accessing untapped reserves requires government approval for new drilling.
2. Minerals, such as coal, support industries and government functions. Minerals can be stored between rounds.

3. Electricity powers all sectors. Initially sourced from hydroelectric and thermoelectric plants, availability can be increased through investment in other energy sources. It cannot be stored but can be exported.

Agricultural goods:

1. Plantain is the staple food. It can be bought, imported, or earned in the informal economy. Production is affected by water shortages, while agroforestry enhances resilience. It cannot be stored but can be traded internationally at a fixed price.
2. Meat is a higher-cost alternative, available from livestock farms, imports, or the informal economy. Its availability is affected by droughts and cannot be stored.
3. Coffee is a luxury export with no domestic demand. Agroforestry improves resilience but does not affect prices. Coffee can be stored.

Other goods:

- Machinery supports industries and government functions, and it is crucial for innovation and establishing new businesses. Demand often exceeds supply, requiring costly imports. Machinery can be stored.
- Consumer goods are imported items that support ministries' functions and improve citizens' quality of life and access to jobs. Domestic production is desirable but costly. Consumer goods can be stored.
- Health is essential to ensure the population's well-being. Health services are provided by public hospitals or the informal economy. Private hospital investments can increase health care access. Health cannot be stored.

3.2 Game phases and indicators

Each round simulates economic activity: Households seek employment in private or public companies, while industries and government pay salaries. If jobs or wages are insufficient, households turn to the informal economy. Those with more resources have priority access to formal jobs and can seek work abroad – provided they have fuel to travel. Players trade goods domestically and internationally to allow companies to operate and meet household needs. Some goods are scarce, and once depleted, prices rise. Domestic prices are negotiable, while international prices are fixed and depend on the exchange rate. Public and private companies that have acquired all necessary inputs, including labor, proceed with production, which varies based on input levels and the current scenario. The game begins with a strong reliance on fossil fuels, posing a challenge for the government's commitment to the Paris Agreement. While the extractive industry generates substantial revenue through royalties and dividends, the environmental impact of fossil fuel consumption both locally and globally calls for a transition to sustainable energy sources. Land use change adds complexity – converting forest or savanna generates profit but also increases emissions. Agroforestry offers a more sustainable alternative but requires more labor. To boost and diversify the economy, players can expand existing sectors or establish new industries, including production facilities for consumer goods. A critical opportunity is creating a Research Center, which serves as an innovation hub that generates

knowledge and unlocks access to renewable energy projects such as solar and wind farms and biogas facilities. The game also allows players to explore alternative sustainability strategies beyond those outlined here. A just transition is achieved when emission reductions do not come at the cost of social and economic stability. If households lose access to jobs or energy, the transition is considered unjust.

The game tracks indicators across the three pillars of sustainable development:

- Economic: Exchange rate and gross domestic product (GDP). The exchange rate is linked to the country's trade balance, while GDP is based on household spending, company operations, government expenses, and investments.
- Social: Human Development Index (HDI). HDI reflects health, education, and living standards, and it is determined by citizen consumption and government investments in education and labor.
- Environmental: Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. GHG emissions result from petroleum and mineral consumption and land use changes. The game tracks both domestic emissions – categorized by consumer sectors – and emissions generated abroad from exported fossil fuels.¹

These indicators help players assess the economic, social, and environmental impact of their decisions, allowing them to refine their strategies for the next round, balancing short-term gains with long-term sustainability goals.

4 Results of the Game Sessions

A total of nine game sessions were conducted: three in June 2024, following a series of preliminary crash test sessions, and six in September 2024. The June sessions were still exploratory in nature, serving to gather additional player feedback and refine some of the game mechanisms. As such, they were not fully consistent in terms of game rules, scenarios, or data collection methods. By contrast, the six sessions held in September 2024 followed finalized game mechanics, standardized scenarios, and consistent data collection protocols. The break between the third (June) and fourth (September) sessions provided a crucial period for analyzing feedback and implementing final adjustments to the game. Below, we present the results of the six game sessions held in September 2024 in Bogotá. Although each had its own mix of participants, the six game sessions revealed recurring dynamics that influenced Columbia's GDP, the Human Development Index of its citizens, the exchange rate between coronas and dollars, and the level of domestic and exported emissions.

¹ The concept of exported emissions is usually not used to address the leakages of CO₂ emissions through trade. Traditional carbon accounting distinguishes between production footprint (i.e. the emissions generated in the geographical space) and consumption footprint (i.e. the emissions generated to produce all the goods and services consumed in the geographical space, that is including imported goods and services). In this paper, the notion of exported emissions represents the emissions generated abroad via the combustion of petroleum extracted domestically. Typically, these are not assigned to national footprints (neither production nor consumption) but they are useful in the context of the game to highlight the broader impacts of depending on fossil fuel exports.

4.1 Key emerging dynamics

A consistent theme was the fragile balance between public revenues and the government’s ability to run the country efficiently while advancing a low-carbon transition. Government interventions – such as tax and royalties increase, wage hikes, and export restrictions – often led to unintended consequences, reducing production, further straining public finances, and causing sectoral disruptions. GDP fluctuated accordingly, growing when investments and trade from specific sectors expanded but contracting when key industries, particularly PetrolEco, faced crises or restrictions. HDI followed a similar pattern, often declining due to reduced citizen consumption, job market instability, and disruptions in public services such as healthcare and education. A key reason behind the instability was the lack of a proper initial diagnosis of the country’s situation. This reflects a real-world situation: The government inherited pre-existing conditions from the preceding administration, had limited time to act, and needed to secure resources for its own operations while ensuring availability for citizens and industries. Figure 4 illustrates the results of these efforts by showing the variation between Round 2 and Round 1 (R2 – R1) for GDP and HDI in each session. In half of the sessions, both indicators increased, while in the other half, HDI, or both HDI and GDP, declined. The most extreme case was Session 6, where an oil crisis led to a dramatic drop in exports and domestic oil scarcity, resulting in declines in both indicators. Session 3 is a clear example of rushed government policies: The wage increase, intended to improve living conditions, put pressure on public finances, ultimately defunding the hospital system and triggering a healthcare crisis, which caused the HDI to drop. At the same time, GDP increased due to the establishment of a thermoelectric plant, which was built in response to a catastrophic drought. A similar tax and wage reform in Session 2 led to different short-term outcomes: While some companies shut down due to reduced profitability, others diversified and new businesses emerged, triggering improvements in both GDP and HDI. However, the long-term sustainability of these gains remained uncertain, as the full economic impact of these shifts would have materialized in the following round.

Figure 4. Change in GDP and HDI Between the Second and First Rounds (R2 – R1) Across All Sessions. The Dashed Lines Divide the Figure Into Four Quadrants, Representing Different Outcome Scenarios: GDP Growth With HDI Decline (Blue Quadrant), Simultaneous GDP and HDI Increases (Green Quadrant), HDI Growth With GDP Decline (Yellow Quadrant), and a Decline in Both Indicators (Red Quadrant).

Energy availability – both in terms of raw materials and electricity – was another recurring challenge, affecting both emissions and economic activity. Five out of six sessions saw blackouts and/or fuel shortages that limited production and household well-being. While domestic emissions often declined due to economic slowdowns and ministries that were not operational, this did not indicate innovation or true environmental progress. In fact, in some cases, while domestic emissions dropped, exported emissions increased sharply, highlighting how companies prioritized international markets over domestic needs (Figure 5). This pattern, in the absence of technological advancements, points to an unjust transition where ministries, industries, and especially households suffered from fuel shortages. Only in Session 6 did all emissions, except those related to land use change, decrease from Round 1 to Round 2. However, this was not due to innovation but rather to an oil crisis and PetrolEco’s decision to accumulate production instead of selling. Overall, corporate emissions remained stable across sessions, indicating limited innovation in the domestic production system.

Figure 5. Variations in Domestic Emissions (Produced by Households, Industries, and Government Consumption, as Well as Those Caused by the Loss of Forests and Plains) and Exported Emissions per Round for Each Session.

Except for Session 1, the exchange rate remained volatile, with a general tendency to decrease from Round 1 to Round 2. In most of the sessions, exports – mainly driven by petroleum, coffee, minerals and, sometimes, energy – exceeded imports, leading to an appreciation of the corona. However, as previously explained, these currency fluctuations were not incorporated into the gameplay. Again, Session 6 was an outlier due to the decision to halt oil exports, which drastically altered trade dynamics and exchange rate movements.

4.2 Debriefings and insights for the climate action plan

At the end of each session, facilitators asked participants two questions: What surprised them most about the game, and what key insights from the game should be integrated into Colom-

bia's Climate Action Plan. Their responses highlighted several recurring themes. Participants across multiple game sessions expressed surprise at how closely PowerShift mirrored real-world transition challenges. The profit maximization mindset dominated business decisions, with industries often prioritizing capital growth over social considerations, while governments struggled to address overwhelming demands with insufficient resources. The most striking aspect was the persistent lack of cross-sector collaboration and leadership, as players pursued siloed interests despite recognizing the need for coordination. The reactive approach to innovation was revealing, as it emerged only after environmental taxes increased or crises demanded it. Energy sector dynamics surprised many participants: Despite climate concerns, petroleum demand remained stable, with availability, not climate impact, driving decisions. Political instability and power imbalances further complicated planning, with the private sector often dictating partnership terms. The game highlighted how immediate survival-focused needs consistently trumped long-term planning, even when participants recognized the value of ecotourism and other sustainable initiatives. Perhaps the most instructive insight was seeing how inadequate indicators, planning gaps, and communication barriers undermined progress, reinforcing that successful transitions require not just technical solutions but robust dialogue mechanisms, adaptive leadership, and shared knowledge development across all sectors. These revelations directly informed participants' recommendations for Colombia's Climate Action Plan, emphasizing seven critical dimensions for effective implementation:

- **Coordination:** Strengthen proactive, efficient, and timely communication between government, industries, and citizens to ensure aligned decision-making and policy implementation.
- **Diagnosis:** Conduct thorough assessments to identify the needs, strengths, and challenges of different stakeholders, ensuring that policies are data-driven and context-specific.
- **Indicators:** Develop comprehensive indicators that accurately capture social, economic, and environmental realities, allowing for informed decision-making and progress tracking.
- **Anticipation:** Establish clear short-, medium-, and long-term objectives, using scenario planning to navigate uncertainties and proactively address risks.
- **Adaptation and resilience:** Promote flexible and forward-thinking approaches that integrate preventive and cross-sectoral strategies to enhance national resilience.
- **Commitment and will:** Foster a culture of cooperation by focusing on shared goals and the common good, avoiding polarization that may hinder effective policy implementation.
- **Leadership:** Cultivate inclusive, participatory leadership that builds trust, encourages innovation, and drives strategic, long-term action for sustainable development.

While these insights may not be entirely new, experiencing them firsthand through PowerShift reinforced their significance, transforming abstract concepts into tangible challenges and actionable strategies. This experiential process aligns with established theories on simulation-based and experiential learning (Crookall, 2011; Duke, 1974; Kolb, 1984). The power of immersive engagement lies in the game's ability to bridge cognition, emotions, and actions. The game sessions served as more than just illustrative exercises. As expressed in the M&E surveys, they offered a safe place for participants to reflect on their own biases, system-level blind spots, and coordination gaps. These observations and ex-post feedback from participants reinforce

the role of serious games in promoting strategic thinking, adaptive and cooperative capacities and anticipatory governance.

Despite the game allowing policy exploration, the recommendations produced were not sufficiently specific to inform or guide current public policies. A more targeted focus – such as testing a concrete policy already implemented or under consideration in the country – might have helped generate more actionable outcomes.

4.3 Insights from the Monitoring and Evaluation process

The M&E framework provided valuable insights into participant experiences and project outcomes. The use of pre- and post-session questionnaires and interviews allowed for an in-depth analysis of changes in knowledge, perspectives, networking, and engagement levels. The M&E process was structured around a mixed-methods approach combining ex-ante questionnaires immediately before gameplay (86 respondents), an ex-post Google Form questionnaire sent one week after the sessions (20 respondents), and an in-depth post-session interview (21 respondents) three months after the session. Drawing on Sen's capability framework (Sen, 1985), the analysis tracked changes in participants' knowledge ("I have learned something"), interlinking ("I have met new people"), strategic analysis ("I have expended my vision of possible pathways/trajectories"), strategic engagement ("I have a clearer idea on how to plan the transition") and implementation strategy ("I have taken concrete actions"). While this approach does not claim to be exhaustive in its ability to fully measure impact, this mixed-methods approach enhanced the depth of the findings, offering a more holistic understanding of the project's effectiveness. Participants in the ex-post interview expressed a 95% degree of satisfaction with the game experience. We advocate that this very high positive feedback is linked to the unconventional, immersive, and interactive nature of the strategy game experience. It provides a safe and participatory space that enables collective thinking on the complexities of the low-carbon transition by simultaneously engaging both intellectual and emotional reasoning, two key factors in experiential learning (Kolb, 1984; Wenzler & Chartier, 1999). The PowerShift game effectively broadened participants' understanding of the low-carbon transition, with 66% of participants in ex-post interviews reporting significant knowledge gains. The game facilitated critical thinking and perspective shifts, enabling participants to navigate the complexities of decision-making under uncertainty. Players gained insights into a wide range of transition challenges, such as economic dependencies, political obstacles, and institutional coordination issues. Many reported increased empathy towards other stakeholders, particularly in understanding the economic and social implications of energy policies. Serious games have proven useful in enhancing emotional engagement and changes of perspectives, fostering deeper understanding of diverse viewpoints (Flood et al., 2018; den Haan & van der Voort, 2018). By stepping into each others' shoes, participants were able to grasp the constraints, motivations, and trade-offs faced by different sectors, leading to more nuanced dialogues. Participants also reported improvements in negotiation, communication, and dialogue skills. These results confirm prior research that highlights the role of strategy games in developing empathy, trust, and collaboration (Mayer, 2009; Reckien & Eisenack, 2013). Additionally, 81% of participants in ex-post interviews reported to consider a broader range of pathways, indicating that the game expanded their strategic thinking. The interactive nature of playing allows participants to explore a set of policy options and trade-offs related to the low-carbon transition and experience firsthand their im-

plications on the system and other stakeholders. While expanding mental models of participants, the game also enables them to refine their strategic projection on how to tackle the transition. The game had a more moderate impact on concrete policy engagement and collaboration. While 43% of participants reported taking some form of strategic action after playing, 57% saw limited direct implementation impact. This suggests that while the game was successful in fostering dialogue, sustained engagement beyond a single session may be required to translate insights into policy and institutional changes. 29% of participants felt that PowerShift significantly facilitated the creation of new relations, and another 14% reported a moderate increase. The results suggest that while immediate networking and concrete actions were somehow limited, the game influenced how participants would communicate and frame energy transition issues going forward. The relative weakness of these dimensions compared to knowledge acquisition and strategic thinking suggests that more interactive sessions with targeted working groups are needed to translate insights into concrete actions. A well-structured, multiple-day workshop would help to ensure that the valuable strategic thinking that emerged during the sessions can be effectively converted into tangible initiatives and policy implementations.

5 Powershift: Implementation Successes, Challenges, and Next Steps

Overall, PowerShift proved to be a successful tool for engaging a diverse range of stakeholders from the public and private sectors as well as civil society, simulating key challenges faced by Colombian stakeholders in the low-carbon transition, and supporting dialogue around the low-carbon transition and providing a safe environment to experiment with policies and explore their systemic implications. However, key interconnected challenges remain.

5.1 Time management

Each game session took approximately half a day. Within this limited time frame, participants were introduced to the game, played two rounds, and engaged in a generally short debriefing. The first round primarily served as a learning phase during which players familiarized themselves with the tool, their role, and the other players. In the second round, players started to experience the consequences of their decisions or the impacts of scenarios that were imposed by the game master. These challenges sparked meaningful discussions and initial attempts at strategizing. However, the time available was insufficient for players to fully respond to crises, develop policies, foster innovation, and test sustainable long-term strategies. To effectively explore and refine solutions to complex challenges, game sessions would need to be significantly extended – ideally spanning multiple days. PowerShift offered a springboard to explore how experiential learning can be translated into real-world policy behavior. This aligns with the work of Kriz et al. (2024) on simulation transfer, which explores the conditions under which knowledge and collaborative strategies developed during play-offs can translate into institutional practices. PowerShift began to articulate clearer strategic visions, as reported in the M&E analysis. However, the persistence of such outcomes required specific support structures with long-term follow-up engagements and alignment with policy cycles, which can be complicated, as in the case of Columbia, in the context of political shifts leading to rapid turnover among ministry staff.

5.2 Realism vs. complexity

Realism is a crucial attribute for any model aimed at supporting decision-making. The crash test sessions demonstrated that participants perceived PowerShift and the emerging dynamics as both realistic and relevant to the context of Colombia. However, when dealing with complex systems, there is a tendency to incorporate all possible variables to ensure that every influencing factor is considered. This approach, however, risks making the game overly complex, to the point where the critical interconnections between causes and effects – central to the game’s purpose – become obscured and difficult to extract.

This tension between realism and complexity has been well-documented in simulation and gaming literature. Klabbers (2009) emphasizes that effective simulation design requires balancing fidelity to real-world systems with usability and learning objectives. As he argues, “increasing complexity does not necessarily lead to enhanced learning or decision quality” (p. 186). Similarly, Duke and Geurts (2004) suggest that game designers must make deliberate choices about which elements of reality to include and which to abstract, focusing on the “transferable essence” of the problem rather than perfect replication.

Therefore, striking a balance between realism and complexity is essential. As long as the game enables participants to navigate diverse values, fragmented perceptions, and sometimes conflicting stakeholder agendas, it remains sufficiently realistic to serve its purpose effectively. This balance also guided design choices throughout the game development phases. For example, extreme exchange rate fluctuations were deliberately excluded to prevent excessive complexity. Similarly, other suggestions raised by participants – such as adding more ministries or representing biodiversity in greater detail – were not implemented, as they risked overcomplicating the game without significantly enhancing its core objectives. This approach aligns with Meadows’ (2008) observation that the most effective models capture essential system behaviors while remaining comprehensible to users.

5.3 Engaging the high-level players

For a game session to be successful, it is essential that the right players are at the table at the right time. In this project, the ideal participants are high-level decision-makers who can shape Colombia’s climate and economic policies and have a shared question to address. However, engaging such players – especially for extended game sessions – is notoriously difficult.

A key advantage of this project was AFD’s role as a convener – not only due to its reputation but also because of its ongoing collaboration with key Colombian partners through the GEMMES project. This established relationship provided valuable access to stakeholders and created important opportunities for engagement. Despite these advantages, securing the participation of deputy ministers and parliamentarians remained a challenge, underscoring the inherent difficulty of bringing high-level decision-makers to the table. Several factors likely contributed to this challenge:

- Perceived unseriousness of the tool: Decision-makers may view simulation games as lacking the rigor or credibility required for high-stakes policy discussions.
- Time constraints: High-level officials have demanding schedules, making it difficult to allocate time for non-traditional policy engagement methods.

- Political sensitivities: Certain players may hesitate to participate in a setting where their decisions and interactions are observed, interpreted, or potentially scrutinized, especially when stakeholders from different sectors are present.
- Competing priorities: With numerous urgent policy matters on their agenda, participating in a game-based exercise may not be seen as an immediate priority.
- Need for task-oriented objectives: While each session incorporated the recurring goal of reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and certain groups (such as NGOs) had specific objectives (e.g. identifying civil society's role in the energy transition), participants might have benefited from more structured and task-oriented goals to increase engagement and motivation.

Addressing these challenges requires strategically framing the game's relevance and ensuring it is introduced in the right spaces at the right time.

5.4 Applications and future steps

The most desirable application would be the use of PowerShift as a tool to support real-world decision-making processes. For this to happen, it is essential to identify a dedicated working group with a shared agenda – one that is willing to engage with the tool over multiple days to overcome bottlenecks, explore and test policy options, and refine strategies. This iterative approach would enable stakeholders to assess the consequences of their decisions, adapt their strategies in response to emerging insights, and build consensus around viable policy solutions. Crucially, it would allow participants to move beyond the crisis experienced by players in Round 2, fostering a more structured and solution-oriented decision-making process.

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Disclosure of Interests

The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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Ulrich Holzbaaur & Ingeborg Patsch

Educational Games for Sustainable Development

Abstract

Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) aims to provide the competences required to act towards sustainable development. This not only entails understanding the complex systems that determine the future in an interaction of dynamic, stochastic, and chaotic processes of nature, culture, and multiple decision makers. It also aims to give the target group the competence and motivation to decide and to act in favor of a sustainable future. Many of these aspects call for implementation via games. Games can be used as an experience-based method in formal education and in extracurricular learning.

There are various games that teach facts and understanding and/or boost planning and management competences relevant for sustainable development. Other games address conflicts or target motivation, attitudes, or emotional intelligence. These games can be embedded in an ESD scenario, some of them have a sustainability connotation.

Building on the principles of ESD, we look at the main contents and competencies that should be incorporated in ESD games. For the main areas, we give examples of educational games and game concepts that can be used for ESD. We reflect on our own research and development and on practical experience in education and training in various countries.

Keywords: Sustainable development, Educational games, Agenda 2030

Introduction

In a changing world, there are several megatrends influencing education. We will focus on sustainable development as one vision of a valuable future and on games as an innovative method of teaching.

We see sustainability as an overarching goal which is based on the fulfillment of human needs, the conservation of natural and cultural resources, and the improvement of society. It includes education and entrepreneurial thinking as a means to promote welfare. The 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development came into effect in 2016 (United Nations, 2015). They address issues including poverty and hunger, employment and work, innovation and infrastructure, justice and equality, and education. Entrepreneurship and employability are core elements to achieving the socio-economic goals.

Education is not only a goal but also an important tool to foster sustainability. The challenge is to find adequate methods to support these goals. We will show how educational games can contribute to achieving the SDGs and sustainable development in general.

Education for Sustainable Development

UNESCO defines Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) as follows: “ESD empowers learners to take informed decisions and responsible actions for environmental integrity, economic viability and a just society, for present and future generations, while respecting cultural diversity. It is about lifelong learning and is an integral part of quality education” (UNESCO, 2018).

Shaping competences

The term “Gestaltungskompetenz” (shaping competence) has been coined by de Haan and Harenberg (1999) to describe the relevant competences in ESD. In brief, shaping competences are the competences needed to shape a sustainable future. Throughout the years, there have been a lot of definitions and lists of competences. Most of the authors list between eight and twelve elements of shaping competences.

In a previous work we condensed these into five core areas which also relate to models and modeling (remarks in brackets) (Holzbaur, 2013):

1. Ethics: Competency to deal with own and other people’s and groups’ values (models),
2. Knowledge: Competency to acquire and integrate new knowledge and models,
3. Planning: Competency to plan (create a model of the future),
4. Action: Competency to implement plans and to participate in decision-making processes,
5. Reflection: Competency to analyze and reflect processes (model-based).

Inner development goals: From insight to action

An important part of learning that has been gaining more and more attention over the last years is the notion that in order to achieve a transformation to sustainable institutions we require a shift in worldviews. “The need to shift mind-sets is the biggest block to successful transformations,” reads the summary of a McKinsey article. Simulations provide a safe learning space in which participants can explore the interrelationship between their assumptions, habits, attitudes, and hence their actions and resulting impacts in an external scenario. In this context, ESD is coupled with techniques for developing inner skills such as self-reflection, systemic thinking, or emotional intelligence (Ankrah et al., 2023).

Our basic model for ESD

This model for sustainable action and ESD (Holzbaur, 2020) shows the main aspects of (E)SD from insight to action and also the relation between facts (science) and normative aspects (ethics, politics).

Table 1. Facts and values in (E)SD.

Level	Facts, Scientific aspects	Values, Normative aspects	Consequences
Analytical	Facts and knowledge, Learning, Modeling	Ethics, Empathy evaluation	Decision
Synthetic	Planning, forecasting, management	Norms, Values of others	Planning Action
Personal	Self-motivation, Motivation, Leadership, Teamwork	Match with own values	Individual action, Resilience

In the following, we will show how and where games can contribute to each aspect.

Sustainable Development and the SDGs

The so-called Brundtland definition published by the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED) is the most popular definition of sustainable development: “Sustainable development is development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (WCED, 1987).

The Agenda 2030 describes the SDGs. We summarize them in brief:

- Fighting poverty: SDG 1 was also central to the Millennium Goals. Everyone should have the resources to meet their own needs. This also implies SDG 2 and needs an intact economic and social system, hence calling for SDG 8, i.e. decent work, fair payment, and qualitative growth (Welfare 5.0).
- Climate action and biodiversity: At present, SDGs 13 (climate change), 14, and 16 (biodiversity) present the most urgent challenges for humanity. They are interrelated with many SDGs. These goals are endangered by unlimited quantitative growth coupled with increasing resource consumption.
- Education and justice: The most important foundations for reaching a path to sustainability are education (SDG 4) and justice (SDG 16), in particular strong institutions for enforcing the rules which mankind (UN) and nations have given themselves to achieve a sustainable future.
- Decent work and the understanding of economic growth: The prerequisite for fighting poverty and hunger and providing the necessary resources for meeting the needs of humanity and for achieving the SDGs is the value created by humans or machine labor. In the short term, employability gives the individual direct access to the world of work and to welfare. In the long term, we must understand and manage the processes governing the creation of goods and services, wealth and welfare, profit and prosperity via SDG 4 and SDG 8.
- Short-term measures for meeting the physical needs of people relate to SDGs 2, 3, 6, and 7, while SDGs 4, 5, and 16 relate to the mental needs that are relevant for humanity.

Achieving the SDGs is not just about setting targets but understanding their complex interconnections. As highlighted by the Stockholm Resilience Center (Randers, et al., 2018) in their report *A Smarter Scenario*, the simultaneous fulfillment of all SDGs is impossible, as they influ-

ence and sometimes counteract each other. Sustainability efforts must therefore adopt a systemic approach, recognizing the trade-offs and synergies between different goals. A narrow focus on achieving a single SDG at a local level can have unintended global consequences, potentially undermining progress in other areas (Downing, et al., 2021). The System Change Game encourages this perspective by simulating how financial and governance systems interact, emphasizing that economic, social, and environmental goals must be addressed holistically rather than in isolation. Educational games are a great way to explore and learn about complexity.

Educational games and ESD

Gaming is a well-known training method that has its roots in chess. There is a set of notions for these games referring to their historical background (war games), their decision orientation (planning games), or their use in management education (management games). Other names come from their implementation as computer games (serious games) or computer models (simulation games). We use the term educational games to indicate a focus on the pedagogic use of these games. Educational games are simulation games which involve situation analysis and decisions in one or several roles and which are aimed at education and training. From the SDG and ESD focus of the game, a number of names have evolved, including sustainability games, entrepreneurial games, climate games, eco games.

Educational games form an experience-oriented approach to ESD. Simulations are a tool for creating insight into future developments. Games play a central role in ESD, as they can be used for a variety of content and competences due to their flexibility. A simulation game is a simulated exercise in which participants gain experience in planning and decision-making through their active involvement. It allows participants to recreate complex scenarios and try out different courses of action in order to develop a better understanding of the dynamics and impact of their decisions.

Games and ESD

Games can contribute to various components of ESD:

- Competences: Social competence, problem-solving competence, design competence: analytical and synthetic
- Knowledge and understanding: Knowledge and facts/contexts, ESD-relevant knowledge and contexts
- Personality and ethical aspects: Personal competence/self-reflection, action competence, empathy

Table 2. How games support the phases of ESD.

Level	Facts, Scientific aspects	Values, Normative aspects	Consequences
Analytical	Fact-learning Simulations show consequences of the current state and decisions and potential future development path	Role-based games can develop empathy and the sense for conflicts and cooperative work	In any educational game, decisions have to be made.
Synthetic	Project management, Future scenarios create awareness for the impact of decisions and planning skills		Any game is an example of individual decision-making and group-based reactions
Personal	Self-motivation, Motivation, Leadership, Teamwork	Games allow reflection of personal values	

Educational games for socio-economic development

Socio-economic development for all countries and a globally responsible use of natural resources are the two pillars of sustainable development. To achieve socio-economic development and to create jobs and wealth, entrepreneurial thinking is required, and for this, fundamental training for future entrepreneurs is necessary. This training should also address sustainability issues such as the protection of nature, the preservation of resources and cultures, justice and human rights, welfare, and global citizenship. Sustainable development means responsibility in business and new opportunities for enterprises.

Educational games can be used to teach the competences needed by entrepreneurs in various formats:

- Formal education (university, school, vocational education),
- Informal education for entrepreneurs and start-ups,
- Lifelong learning and training within and outside the enterprise,
- Evaluation of business plans with focus on plausibility, feasibility, risk, and strategy,
- Casual learning where learners do not intend to learn but use the game for fun and learn within a situation of informal learning.

Educational games can be helpful and efficient to support employability, entrepreneurship, and ESD. In order to match the specific educational goal and training situation, games can be developed from scratch or adapted. To ensure training success, educational games need adequate preparation and adaptation. The game must be embedded in a training framework and accompanied by adequate briefing and debriefing. Moreover, training the trainers is essential for the success of educational games.

Educational games and the SDGs

Education is addressed in SDG 4, especially in SDG 4.4, where the focus is on education for employment, while ESD is addressed in SDG 4.7.

Education will also contribute to innovation (SDG 9) and a stable economic system (SDG 8) and via that to reducing inequalities (SDG 10) and fighting poverty (SDG 1) and hunger (SDG 2).

Moreover, education is crucial for achieving SDG 3 (health) and SDG 12 (responsible consumption and production), supporting responsibility vis-à-vis natural and cultural resources (SDGs 6, 7, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, and 16) and fighting corruption, which is part of SDG 16 (Peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development) and an important prerequisite for achieving sustainability and human rights.

Individual development and its relation to ESD

Many games focus on the development of individual competencies. These competences are not only needed to act towards a sustainable future but also to make sure that the acting individual maintains mental stability, self-reflection, and a coherent value system.

Examples

In the following chapter, we describe and reflect on various games. They represent a multiplicity of games and game types and their contribution to ESD, each focusing on different aspects of ESD as introduced above. We focus on physical (haptic) games, but the content can also be implemented as a computer-based (serious) game.

Role-based game Albuchmühle

Sustainability is not only a matter of knowledge but of implementation. To bridge the gap between knowing and doing, people need to negotiate and plan. Albuchmühle is a role-based game for sustainable development and has a successor for sustainable event management and entrepreneurship, Albuchscheuer. Both rely on the interaction of and tension between the role players who manage a mill and the local newspaper reporters who are going to write about the mill and its development.

The roles include the owner of the mill and his children, who are going to inherit the mill but have different ideas in mind for its future. An important aspect is the significance that sustainability has for the various players:

For Max Müller, owner of the mill, sustainability above all means the preservation of healthy soil and intact agriculture and forestry. He finds the term itself superfluous, as for him the preservation of all things created and care for future generations are self-evident.

Stefan Müller is the son of Max. For Stefan, sustainability includes not only aspects of ecology but also of social justice. That is why he wants to establish the Albuchmühle as a high-quality brand whose values resonate with the wider population and that strengthens agriculture as a regional economic factor. He would like to generate more of the energy for the mill from the stream that runs through the mill grounds.

Isolde Müller is the daughter of Max. For Isolde, sustainability means a long-term economic return for the Albuchmühle and a contribution to the value chain. She would therefore like to cooperate more with farmers and bakers under the Enjoy Albuch brand in order to create a uniform brand.

For Margret Market, marketing manager, sustainability is primarily about inspiring customers and consumers to protect the environmental and preserve nature. Her aim is to position the Albuchmühle as a high-quality brand in the long term. For her, the core of sustainability is a reliable regional supply of healthy agricultural products.

Erwin Lean is the CFO of the mill. For him, sustainability primarily means securing the mill's yield in the long term. The financial success allows the Albuchmühle to support voluntary work and social NPOs.

The editor-in-chief of the A-Stadt News, Ulrich Bernd, has a strong interest in the role of modern media in a modern democracy. Sustainable development can only succeed if the transparency of companies and government lead to forward-looking decisions and corruption is prevented through openness.

Susi Schreiber is a reporter with the A-Stadt News for three years and has made a name for herself primarily through her critical reporting. She is in favor of obliging companies to take action in the main areas of climate adaptation, biodiversity, anti-corruption, and consumer education that moves beyond greenwashing.

Ben Bauer is a volunteer at the A-Stadt News. He focuses on sustainable development. During the presentation of Stefan's plans to generate power at the Albuchmühle, his party vehemently campaigned in favor of a fish ladder.

Albuchmühle shows the various aspects and challenges of implementing sustainable behavior. It has been used in various training situations with students and in professional workshops. The advantage of role-based games is that they foster ongoing interaction and reflection among participants.

VALYU game set

ESD also needs to address entrepreneurial thinking and various normative aspects. The educational game set VALYU consists of six haptic games which address dedicated aspects of entrepreneurship and sustainability in each game level. The levels and their relation to the subjects of economics education are compiled in Table 3 (Bühr & Rey, 2011; Holzbaur et al., 2013b & 2016):

Table 3. Levels, values, and components in the VALYU game.

Level	Value aspect	Contents
6	Adding value to society	Business canvas as a tool to develop and analyze entrepreneurial business models Role-based games on entrepreneurial attitudes and competences
5	Entrepreneurial values & ethical values	Fishpond on the tragedy of the commons and multi-stakeholder aspects of sustainability Ecological puzzle – an artist approach to sustainability Role-based game on sustainable management
4	Valuing people and culture	Management – Lego Tower game on project management and competition Leonardo Bridge – teamwork and cooperation; definition of interfaces
3	Creating value for the market	Marketing – various markets and pricing concepts Trade and speculation – pricing and contracts with stochastic supply and demand
2	Adding monetary value	Bookkeeping and accounting board game; balances, fixed costs, investment, depreciation Elementary processes to foster entrepreneurial approaches
1	The concept of value creation	Economy for dummies – a haptic board-based game introducing basic economic principles

VALYU teaches economic skills and sustainability attitudes while also addressing normative and behavioral aspects of entrepreneurship and employability. It has been successfully deployed in various settings in Germany and South Africa (Conradie et al. 2020).

Cause canvas: A game-based approach to sustainable business models

The Cause Canvas, developed by one of the authors of this paper in Nepal, is an interactive method that supports participants in designing social and sustainable business models through a structured gamification approach. It combines strategic decision-making, scenario-based exploration with collaborative problem-solving, making business development engaging and experiential.

Participants navigate a set of guided questions, selecting from six thematic matrixes that align with different stakeholders of an organization, such as creating ethical products, integrating disadvantaged groups, supporting fair supply chains, or promoting community-based resource sharing. Teams refine and present their models, adapting strategies through iteration and feedback, simulating real-world entrepreneurial challenges. Cause Canvas helps organizations facing a particular challenge to identify crucial points for intervention.

First tested in a sustainable entrepreneurship workshop, the method engaged nearly 40 participants, including students, entrepreneurs, and sustainability advocates. The hands-on structure encouraged participants to think systemically, integrate sustainability into business planning, and develop actionable strategies. A follow-up session linked the game to real-world social entrepreneurship in Nepal, reinforcing alternative economic approaches and their practical application.

Aligned with ESD, the Cause Canvas fosters systems thinking, entrepreneurial action, and experiential learning. By immersing participants in the complexities of sustainable business, it builds key competencies for transformative innovation and social impact.

Fish and the tragedy of the commons

The free use of public goods (resources, media) is one of the core problems in sustainable development. The tragedy of the unmanaged commons is a model for these problems and provides any entry point to understanding the principles of sustainability. The fish game goes back to ideas of Dennis Meadows, and it shows how individual decisions regarding the use of common goods (resources, media) can lead to the deterioration or destruction of the system, as there are no jointly developed and agreed rules governing individual exploitation. It is a haptic game that involves discussions within and among the groups. It should be accompanied by an introduction to sustainability in general and to the tragedy of the unmanaged commons or similar game-theoretical constructs. This means that a comprehensive briefing of the trainers is necessary.

Fish game description

5 fishing boats are fishing in an area (pond/ocean). At the start of the game there are 50 fish, which is the maximum number. After each year of fishing (= one game round), the remaining population doubles (up to the maximum number of 50 fish). Usually, the number of fish in the pond is unknown to the players.

There are many modifications, for example:

The fish are represented by coins of different value. One coin corresponds to one fish. The sales value corresponds to the cent value of the coin. Players must pay their fixed and variable costs every round. The aim is to create a thriving long-term business.

The fish game has been used in many versions around the world, as the moderator usually leaves open to interpretation what thriving means, or players to opt to maximize the number of fish. Usually, after a few rounds the pond is empty, and the outcome can be reflected and/or the game can be played again for a second chance.

The participants learn that it is not the aim to be “the best” by ruining the world and exposing everyone to a situation that is worse than one’s own, but to create maximum welfare.

The game is described vaguely with regard to communication and agreements. You have the freedom to allow or disallow agreements. Players usually do so by setting up rules on who is allowed to extract how many fish each round. In advanced groups, the challenge can be increased by increasing the fixed costs for the players so that sustainable interaction is only possible if one player forgoes their possibility of covering fixed and variable costs.

The game highlights the impact of egoistic individuals that exploit a common good and the central role of managing commons through collaboration and the setting of rules. It can be used as a simple introduction (awareness, self-reflection) to rather complicated settings involving mathematical game theory and aspects of interaction, contracts, and corruption.

SDG game and Possible World game

To achieve sustainable behavior and decisions, it is important to make players aware of the potential that a shift in perspective or goal of a system plays in achieving sustainability. ESD needs to show learners that their actions are relevant. The Possible World simulation, inspired by the SDGs, was initially developed as a card game (SDG Game) and is now available as an online simulation too. Players engage by using resources such as time and money to implement projects or interact with one another. Each project they undertake affects both the player’s individual status and the simulated world around them.

A key feature of the game is the world condition meter, which provides real-time feedback on the three pillars of sustainability: economy, environment, and society. Players can monitor these indicators throughout the game, as every project implemented directly impacts one or more of these pillars. Additionally, several project cards include requirements for minimum levels in one of the pillars, prompting players to consider the broader impacts of their actions.

In addition to markers for time and money, the game introduces markers for three intangible concepts that represent progress toward achieving one’s personal or social “calling”. These concepts include:

- A sense of accomplishment for contributing to social goals, such as eradicating poverty,
- Progress in restoring environmental health, and
- Contributions to social justice.

When a player completes a project that aligns with these intangible goals, they earn corresponding markers: blue (social targets), green (environmental health), or yellow (social justice).

At the start of the game, players randomly select a goal card. Each goal card outlines a numeric target for resources (time, money, or markers) and includes a shared qualitative objective: “To live in a balanced and thriving world.”

The game encourages collaboration and creativity, as all interactions are permitted as long as they are mutually agreed upon by the participants. To incorporate reflection and encourage mindset shifts, the simulation is typically played in two rounds.

After the first round, players reflect on their experiences through journaling and group sharing. The focus of the reflection depends on the players' consciousness regarding sustainability issues. In some cases, insights center on the realization that better communication and a mutually agreed upon target lead to greater success. In other instances, players realize that they have neglected certain aspects of the game – such as a specific sustainability pillar – and discuss how this affected their outcomes. These reflections allow players to refine their strategies and perspectives before re-entering the game for a second round.

The simulation is designed to help players develop a deeper understanding of sustainability and systems thinking. One of its key learning goals is to create what is known as a Kizuki effect – a moment of realization where players gain new insights into how their own perspective influences their actions and, in turn, the impact they make on the world. By fostering this awareness, the game encourages participants to reflect on their decision-making processes and consider the broader consequences of their choices. By engaging with sustainability concepts, practicing collaboration, and exploring the interplay between individual actions and collective outcomes, the game offers a powerful tool for inner reflection, mindset shifts, and learning.

The game usually raises a number of recurring topics. Deep and ongoing communication and defining a target serving the common good are key to achieving sustainable results. Often the players with economic goals (to earn money, understand economic principles) start working on their own, while those pursuing yellow (social justice) or green principles (environmental health) are soon running out of resources to achieve their respective goal.

The game can be influenced a lot by the moderator, for instance if during the introduction less emphasis is given to the individual goals and more to the common goal of achieving high scores in the world condition meter.

A similar game, *Eco²* (Holzbaur 1993, 2001), was also based on a simulation in which the players have different roles and aims and their decisions mutually influencing factors such as socio-economic and ecological development, individual wealth, and wellbeing. It was implemented as a board-based and as a computer-based game.

Simulations of possible world developments mirror to players the effects of their decisions and the conflicts when making decisions in different roles.

System Change game: Exploring alternative economic systems for sustainability

As part of ESD, games also allow testing alternative models and increasing economic literacy and entrepreneurial competences. Developed by Teresa Karayel, the System Change Game is an educational board game that explores the differences between the conventional Euro-based financial system and an alternative model, often the Gradido system. Through experiential learning, participants gain insights into wealth distribution, interest rates, and systemic transformation, thus deepening their understanding of economic stability and social equity.

Designed for 4–9 participants, the game begins by simulating the Euro-based system, where prices incorporate taxes and interest payments. Players take on roles such as shop owners, a bank, a state representative, and a rentier, managing finances, paying debts, and discussing fairness and sustainability. After several rounds, they reflect on their experiences and vote on whether to transition to an alternative system. If they opt for Gradido, new rules apply:

- A universal basic income in Gradidos is introduced, subject to demurrage.
- Transactions occur in both currencies, with 10 percent of Euros converted to Gradidos each round.
- Taxes are replaced by automatic contributions to social and environmental budgets.
- Players collaboratively develop community projects, deciding how to allocate Gradidos and whether to co-finance initiatives.

By immersing participants in a real-time monetary transition, the game encourages critical reflection on financial systems and their constraints. It aligns with ESD by fostering economic literacy, social responsibility, and participatory decision-making. Through active engagement, players experiment with sustainable financial alternatives, enhancing awareness of economic justice and systemic transformation and experience.

Being immersed in a particular system can make us blind towards the effects and impacts this system has on our actions, decisions, and (sustainability) dynamics in that system. The game experience makes visible the otherwise unrecognized aspects of our financial system and highlights its non-sustainable aspects. Only after having been exposed to a fictional alternative model are players able to see the current system and start a constructive conversation on how to shape it differently.

If longer or repeating sessions are played, the group will gradually realize that giving away money as a (interest-free) loan is actually a way to save for the future, as money kept will decrease. On some occasions, the conversation and reflection delves deeper into the participatory aspect of the game in terms of joint budgeting and implementation of public action towards social and the environmental wellbeing.

Lego Tower

To take action to promote sustainability means to start a project – e.g. a campaign, a venture, an enterprise – and to cooperate with partners and coordinate the work. Hence, project planning is a prerequisite for achieving results. Lego Tower (Bethman et al., 2005) was developed to give the learners a feeling and understanding for the magic triangle (or triad) of project management:

- The project result, which is the most important aspect and the reason for starting a project. Representation in the game: Height and stability of the tower.
- The resources which are needed and must be provided to enable project success. Representation in the game: Labor (time for planning and building), bricks.

- The time and milestones which are the most visible aspect of the project. Representation in the game: Planning time, proposed construction time, construction time achieved by the team.

By planning a tower made of Lego bricks, learners face the challenge of balancing the triad consisting of result (height, stability), resources (bricks, labor), and time (for planning and for construction). Each factor has an impact on the value for the customer and on the price the customer is willing to pay. Lego Tower provides the learner with soft skills and project competence.

Lego Tower has been successfully used at schools and universities and in project management training. It also helps to tie project management training to discussions on the importance of aims and resources in projects and in sustainability.

PPM/ESPRESSO

The best simulation is reality. To achieve and experience impact, you must act in the real world. In previous work, we have analyzed the idea of using prepared projects (PPM) for education and for achieving real-world results (Holzbaur et al., 2013a, 2017). PPM creates a setting for projects which uses core ideas of educational games: Preparation, control, interaction, and feedback (Holzbaur et al., 2013b). Via well-prepared projects, learners will be able to handle challenging tasks. The ESPRESSO (Experience Science and Practical Relevance and learn Sustainably via Sustainability Projects) method provides a good chance of success to learners, a controlled environment for educators, and a positive impact for society. PPM/ESPRESSO can be seen as transferring the game concept to real-world projects or as an education game that takes place in the real world and has the power to change this world. Projects play an important role in education and are used all over the world.

Summary

Entrepreneurial education and ESD share core issues such as the know – can – do triad and the basic importance of models. Both entrepreneurship and sustainable development can be taught using educational games. We have seen that the entrepreneurial game set VALYU with its six levels and the associated games and training units integrates entrepreneurial education, ESD, and mathematical competences.

We have also shown how education can promote the fulfillment of the SDGs of the 2030 Agenda and sustainable development in general.

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Wasteria: A Gaming Simulation Approach to Raise Awareness of Waste Management

Abstract

Waste management in Indonesia remains a critical challenge. With more daily waste generated than current landfill capacity, many people arguably dispose of waste improperly. Although rapid urbanization and population growth each play their role in environmental degradation, public health risks, and social inequality, Indonesia's leading causes of waste management issues include low awareness regarding waste separation by type, recycling, and reuse, further perpetuating improper waste disposal practices. Despite these challenges, creating an awareness movement for impacted communities can be a starting point to untangle the complexity. In response, *Wasteria*, a game designed for educational and social impact, aims to foster eco-friendly waste management habits among individuals. This article explains the development of the *Wasteria* board game. The game fills the gap concerning the causes and effects of serious issues while providing education in a fun way. *Wasteria* aspires to contribute significantly to Indonesia's sustainable waste management movement and beyond.

Keywords: Waste management, Awareness, Gaming simulation, Development planning, Planning information system.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

Over 175,000 tons of waste are generated daily in Indonesia, a large portion of which ends up in landfills without proper treatment (Andriani & Atmadja, 2019). This situation is exacerbated by rapid urban growth and rising populations. Landfills are facing overcapacity, while land has become a scarce commodity. Cities, especially those with high populations but no advanced waste management infrastructures, face high volumes of waste, compromising environmental quality and public health issues. In addition, the informal urbanisms typical to Global South countries also influence the waste management system in Indonesia, as many informal methods such as scavenging have become prevalent but often remain unrecognized and unregulated, creating further challenges for effective waste management (Harfadli et al., 2025; Putri et al., 2018). Many individuals and households remain unaware of the importance of separating, recycling, and reusing waste, perpetuating a culture of improper disposal, although the situation is improving in several areas (Kurniawan et al., 2023). Among the root causes of these issues are limited access to waste management infrastructure, insufficient community awareness, and a lack of sustainable policies at the local level (Damanhuri et al., 2009).

As Universitas Gadjah Mada, where Wasteria was developed, is located in the heart of Yogyakarta Metropolitan Area (*Kartamantul*), the game is also motivated by the closing of Piyungan landfill site that serves Yogyakarta Municipality, Sleman Regency, and Bantul Regency. Similar closures have affected other metropolitan areas on Java Island, such as the Jakarta and Bandung Metropolitan Areas, suggesting the complexity of the problems. This situation might have to do with the limited resources in these areas, such as land availability, institutional arrangements, and funding (Damanhuri et al., 2009; Sasaki et al., 2014). These problems also relate to scale, as urban areas typically face a scarcity of suitable land. By contrast, the surrounding rural areas have vacant land but might not want to have landfill sites, reflecting a not-in-my-backyard (NIMBY) attitude (Permana et al., 2023). While this situation invites the government on a higher scale, i.e., the provincial government, to manage these issues, many efforts on a smaller scale have been made. However, it still takes time for the desired outcomes to manifest.

1.2 Purposes

This article aims to explain the development of Wasteria as a board game to raise awareness regarding solid waste management in Indonesia. This game tries to raise awareness regarding the stagnant phase of current waste management in many Indonesian metropolitan areas. The main goal is to create a movement encouraging individuals to change their habitual waste management actions through roleplaying (see Pojani & Rocco, 2023). This paper and the game aim to push those changes towards greener and eco-friendly waste management using the context of Indonesia. The game was initially submitted as the final assignment for TKP213B42 *Simulasi Permainan untuk Perencanaan* [Gaming Simulation for Planning], an elective course in the Bachelor of Urban and Regional Planning (BURP) Program at the Department of Architecture and Planning, Universitas Gadjah Mada, in 2024. The course's learning outcomes include that the students should be able to (1) identify the concepts and techniques in gaming simulation, (2) implement the development planning issues, problems, and potentials in a gaming simulation, and (3) formulate ideas to be implemented into a well-designed and functional gaming simulation.

For the final project of the course, the students were asked to create a simulation game based on any issues related to regional and urban planning. Each group was required to present their game and develop a mock-up, along with comprehensive game instructions and a report detailing the design process. The evaluation criteria included the game's context, system analysis, construction process, and design and visualization. In this process, three main steps in designing and applying a game are used: Designing the game based on a real-life problem, playing the game, and conducting a debriefing session where players discuss their experiences and relate them to real-world contexts (Peter et al., 1998). This approach enables players to generate new knowledge through experiential learning.

Later on, the course convenors chose two of the best works in the course to join the ISAGA Simulation and Gaming Competition (ISGC) 2024. Wasteria was one of the nominees and received an ISAGA Student Award for Gaming Special Work.

Figure 1. The Typical Condition of Landfill Areas in Indonesia.

Source: <https://waste4change.com/blog/kondisi-tpa-penuh-indonesia/>

2 Game Overview

This section provides a comprehensive game overview, including its name, target audience, core objectives, and key design elements.

2.1 Game's name and purpose

Officially titled "Wasteria: Turn Trash into Gold", Wasteria is a simple game focused on encouraging the development of well-organized waste management in everyday life by raising awareness and providing education. It is based on the assumption that the environmental problems caused by untreated waste can be decreased and that recurring problems would not further increase human health risks.

2.2 Game's intention and details

In line with the game's target, Wasteria is a simulation intended to educate people. Though games have always been known primarily for their enjoyment, Wasteria was developed with players' enjoyment in mind while providing an educational message. Wasteria was mainly a board game inspired by the well-known game Monopoly™. Modifications of the said game were reflected by creating unique paths that resemble road networks in real life. We also use cards

as one of the tools in the game, since players need a designated direction (left or right) to move along pathways. We also designed cards for the points system (waste management infrastructures) and for “game changers”, various situations that represented events that can happen in the real world at different stages of the waste management process.

Wasteria can be played by a maximum of four people. The board game consists of one board, one set of action cards, and one set of infrastructure cards.

Figure 2. Wasteria Board.

Source: Authors, 2024

Wasteria’s board is designed like tree branches, with loops at the edges to maintain continuity in the game flow. There are 193 squares, with a few containing different types of waste for players to collect. The banana icon represents organic waste, the green-colored trash bag icon represents inorganic waste, and the purple potion icon represents toxic and hazardous waste. There are also orange-colored trash bag icons representing action cards, which players must draw if they land on these squares. To decide which direction players should go, this game provides direction cards to be drawn during the game.

During the game, players set out to solve challenges that closely resemble real-life waste management problems. We challenge players to plan policies by prioritizing which waste management infrastructure to buy and build first. This inspired us to apply certain conditions to the game so it would urge players to visualize how complex waste management is.

Figure 3. Wasteria Action Cards.

Source: Authors, 2024

Infrastructure is the key to excellent waste management. As it is the “tool” to process waste, we must bring it into the game. We make it to the finish line of the game. There are different infrastructure cards awarded with different points. Infrastructure with more points is considered more crucial in real life. However, it would be different in other countries since the game uses Indonesia as its case.

The game is played by taking turns rolling the dice and passing through the spaces on the board. Some squares are littered with waste, which can be collected if the player stops on such a square. Collected waste can be exchanged for coins at the end of each turn. Then, coins can be

exchanged for pawns with various multiplying point effects or waste infrastructure cards, which can deliver the winning points if collected as required.

Figure 4. Wasteria Waste Infrastructure Cards.

Source: Authors, 2024

3 Development Process

The development process will be explained by elaborating the steps of the game's development, its educational and social impact, and its challenges and limitations.

3.1 Development steps

In developing Wasteria, the initial team consisted of the BURP Program students who participated in the TKP213B42 *Simulasi Permainan untuk Perencanaan* [Gaming Simulation for Planning] course, convened by three lecturers from the department. After course evaluation, two lecturers joined the team members to participate at ISGC 2024 and have remained in the team since.

Wasteria was developed based on the structured process of designing a simulation game by Peter and Westelaken (2014). The board game development process (see Figure 5) began with a brainstorming session to explore recurring issues faced in Indonesia, such as waste management and public transportation. Through discussion, we decided to focus on waste management

as the theme of our game, acknowledging its importance and potential for raising environmental awareness.

Figure 5. Wasteria Development Timeline.

Source: Authors, 2024

We researched Indonesia’s waste management system through online articles to deepen our understanding of the real-world situation. Using the 5W1H Framework, we mapped the real-life condition and translated it into the elements of our game.

Table 1. 5W1H Framework.

Meta	Question	Game
The phenomenon of high waste volume in several cities in Indonesia	What	Collecting scattered waste on the game board
Government, citizens	Who	Players
Indonesia	Where	Simulated place
20 years	When	30 rounds
Maintaining a clean environment and improving public health quality	Why	Earning points to achieve the waste infrastructure goals
Waste management policies and programs	How	Collecting waste by playing the game using dice and cards

The gameplay focuses on collecting three types of waste commonly found in Indonesia: organic, inorganic, and toxic hazardous waste. In the game, these wastes can be traded for coins. The concept of waste banks in Indonesia strongly influences this mechanism. Additionally, we adopted the existing waste infrastructure commonly used in Indonesia as the key element of this game. This infrastructure includes waste banks, temporary disposal sites (*Tempat Pembuangan Sementara* or TPS), integrated waste management facilities (*Tempat Pembuangan Sampah Terpadu* or TPS-T), and final disposal sites (*Tempat Pembuangan Akhir* or TPA). Each type of infrastructure has points set based on the sustainability of its waste management process.

To summarise the game design, we composed a matrix including various components such as scenarios, unexpected events, roles, and rules.

Table 2. Game Matrix.

	Players	Facilitator
Scenario	Players roll the dice according to the rules, collect waste to trade for coins, and purchase infrastructure to earn points and win	The facilitator observes the game and ensures the rules are followed until the game ends
Events	Each turn, players can draw action cards that affect themselves or other players	
Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Waste collector – Waste infrastructure developer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Card shuffler – Convert waste into coins
Rules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Players draw a direction card and roll the dice – If players land on a square with waste, they collect the waste – If players land on a square with an action card icon, they must draw an action card – Players trade their waste for coins after the turn ends – Players must follow the instructions on the action card drawn in the previous turn – Players can build waste infrastructure with the money they earn and gain points to win 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Facilitators shuffle the direction and action cards for players to draw – Facilitators pay out coins to players at the end of each turn

Our game's debriefing phase differs depending on the number of players. The facilitator is optional. However, this role is substantial in gameplay with more players. Several tests were run during the development phase by organizing our peers into different groups, each with various players. We noticed that groups with more players struggled to play without a facilitator, where pawn placement and coin exchange were the main issues. As a result, the game stayed below the authors' expectations. We also noticed that the players seemed unenthusiastic at the end of the game. Building on this outcome, we decided to establish a facilitator as one of the default roles in the game to ensure smooth gameplay and an effective debriefing.

Furthermore, several revisions were needed to improve the game. Since the game was initially intended as an assignment, much feedback came from the class. We received the first feedback in a session where our game was presented to our peers and lecturers. The feedback primarily emphasized how we could make the game comprehensible, which became crucial because a well-defined gameplay would make the game enjoyable. However, we were unable to meet that specific requirement at the time. We added a simple guidebook, the game matrix's detailed version, to address the feedback. The players were able to understand each step to play the game by having a guidebook. Additional feedback was obtained from the same class at a later phase, namely the moment when we finally submitted the game to be graded by our lecturers.

The feedback was shared when we were preparing for ISGC 2024. Although there was not much to be revised in the game, we needed to ensure the players could comprehend the rules.

Aside from class feedback, we also received constructive input from the ISGC 2024 reviewers. This feedback highlighted the players' diverse conditions, limiting some from fully experiencing the game. Furthermore, these differences were associated with the players' age and education level, which affected their ability to understand the gameplay – although no quantitative evaluation has been performed to confirm this issue, which later became one of our challenges in improving the game. This feedback has had significant impact on the game's development process up to this day, particularly on the idea of developing another version of Wasteria aimed at a specific target.

3.2 Possible outcomes

Multiplayer games usually have a winner to make the game more competitive and fun. Winning requires the player to meet certain criteria. In Wasteria, the winner must gather the most points by collecting waste infrastructure cards, meaning the players must collect more waste. Initially, 50 points were needed when Wasteria was first created. While modifying the game for ISGC 2024, we adapted the rules so that the player who has collected the most points after 30 rounds wins the game. TPS-T has the most points (7 points). Then, the other infrastructure points are 5 points for TPA, 3 points for TPS, and 1 point for *Bank Sampah*. If it is a draw, the winner is decided based on the importance of the infrastructure they own. So, if two or more players have the same points, the player who owns the TPS-T card will win. If none of the players has the card, ownership of the TPA, TPS, and *Bank Sampah* cards (in this hierarchy) determines the winner.

The winner aside, some players inevitably lose. In Wasteria, we call them runner-ups, since no player is worse at the game than the other. The game is about the players' strategy to build up excellent waste management. This makes it clear that there would be different feelings or reactions from the players after finishing the game. Based on the initial Wasteria gameplay experience, when we played the games ourselves and asked our peers to play, we noticed that winners seemed to understand the strategy of the waste management mechanism. They set priorities in choosing the infrastructure and pawns to collect the points efficiently. At the same time, the runner-ups seemed to grasp the strategy after finishing the game. All the players understood that efficiency in waste management came from supporting waste transport services and processing infrastructures. This was the case at ISGC 2024, when the reviewers seemed to understand the priority of the game items. It led to an understanding of the best way to process waste, especially in the context of Indonesia.

3.3 Educational and social impacts

Indeed, the target and intention of Wasteria is to have an educational and social impact. This game aims to educate players on waste management and how some waste is still valuable and not total garbage. In this way, it raises public awareness that waste problems can persist if no substantial action is taken. For reference, many countries have already regulated proper waste management and are incentivizing recycling habits by paying for collected plastic waste, for example, or even by exchanging waste for energy (Gregson, 2023, Chapter 6; Memon, 2023;

Oliveira & Rosa, 2003; Ragan et al. 2018). Furthermore, organic waste that has already gone bad can be further utilized, for instance as biopore and food supply for maggots (Odjo et al., 2019). Even though biopore practice is commonly known, it is still widely unknown among the public in Indonesia, while maggot cultivation businesses have recently been trending to answer many households' waste management struggles and encourage the green waste management movement. Such innovations have become a potential direction in which Wasteria can be developed.

Wasteria's target and intention also relate to the Indonesian academic community's local responsibility. This responsibility – *Tri Dharma Perguruan Tinggi* [Three Pillars of Higher Education] – is stated in Law 20/2003 on the National Education System. *Tri Dharma Perguruan Tinggi* should be implemented in a well-balanced way, ensuring high-quality education (*pendidikan*), socially beneficial research (*penelitian*), and meaningful community engagement (*pengabdian masyarakat*) that creates a positive impact on Indonesian society (Rosser, 2022). The idealistic targets of Tri Dharma are embedded in the developing process of Wasteria, as this game primarily seeks to deliver multiple advantages for the different communities. Apart from the university students and academic institutions for which this game was initially intended, the advantages can be rescaled by educating the broader Indonesian public on waste management through the university's community engagement efforts (*pengabdian masyarakat*). This chain of application can also evaluate and improve the game by testing its usability and the briefing and debriefing stages. Therefore, the community will have a broader impact, especially in creating a better environment.

3.4 Challenges and limitations

While developing Wasteria, our primary focus was on simplifying the game's thematic content in only six months (see Figure 5 for the timeline of the Wasteria development process). However, following its presentation at ISGC 2024, we recognized that the game did not engage all the target demographics as initially anticipated. The game's inherent complexity may confuse players of specific age groups. For example, given that the game centers on waste infrastructure, children may not fully comprehend the underlying mechanisms of waste management. Moreover, numerous adults, irrespective of their Indonesian nationality, may also lack the capacity to understand the complete waste disposal process from inception to conclusion. Consequently, Wasteria does not directly enhance public awareness of the solid waste issues in Indonesia. Instead, the game appears to be more accessible to individuals already familiar with the waste management system, which is characterized by several local yet technical terminologies, such as temporary disposal sites (TPS), integrated waste management facilities (TPS-T), and final disposal sites (TPA). This observation further underscores the importance of incorporating comprehensive briefing and debriefing phases within the gaming simulation.

4 Conclusion and Future Prospects

This article set out to explain the development of the Wasteria: Turn Trash into Gold board game, which addresses Indonesian solid waste management. It is based on everyday Indonesian solid waste management practices, which are translated into game components and rules. Development mainly underwent two stages initially, as this game was created as the final assign-

ment for an elective course in the BURP Program, Department of Architecture and Planning, Universitas Gadjah Mada, before it competed for – and won – the ISAGA Simulation and Gaming Competition 2024. Despite the accolades, the game still needs further tweaking and refining, as the game expects players to already have a basic understanding of solid waste management in Indonesian municipalities.

Nevertheless, in a broader narrative, the development of *Wasteria: Turn Trash into Gold* highlights several research strands worth pursuing further. The first is that a gaming simulation can be a pedagogical tool in explaining current issues in regional and urban planning (Meier & Duke, 1966; Wärneryd, 1975; Bereitschaft, 2023), which focuses on the design thinking approach. Not only does the game reflect the extensive understanding of second-year BURP students regarding solid waste management gained during the short game development phase, it also reflects its potential dissemination through multi-level government institutions (see Anindito et al., 2022 for the hierarchical government in Indonesia), waste management practitioners and academics, and non-governmental organizations. These stakeholders play pivotal roles in waste management systems, and we anticipate that their engagement with the game will foster greater commitment to the maintenance and improvement of existing waste management practices (Mayer, 2009). As this game also uses a roleplaying strategy, we envision these groups utilizing the game as a tool to promote awareness among the public, particularly by integrating it into educational curricula as an early intervention strategy in addressing emerging waste problems (see Pojani & Rocco, 2023). This dissemination can hopefully help bridge the gap between the two dominant perspectives in regional and urban planning nowadays, which are the technical-rational and the communicative rational perspectives (Raghothama & Meijer, 2015). The debriefing phase of this game can raise important questions and discussions regarding its simulation of real-world problems, particularly by assessing its complexity for further development (Istrate & Hamel, 2023; Mayer et al., 2004; Poplin, 2012). This design thinking approach, which requires iterative participation from game players, is also important in game development. Hence, the game can be improved, particularly in terms of why the game was built in the first place.

While the first research strand underscores the importance of design thinking in solving regional and urban planning problems through gaming simulation, the second strand focuses on representing the Global South context within gaming simulations for development planning. These nations often grapple with substantial challenges caused by inadequate waste management infrastructure (Davidson, 2024). Such challenges arise from a constellation of factors, including economic constraints, climatic conditions, and educational deficiencies. In this context, *Wasteria* holds promise as a potential educational tool that addresses these systemic issues. The primary objective is not to mandate the ubiquitous adoption of the game but to inspire innovative solutions and proactive engagement from countries facing similar waste-related difficulties (Istrate & Hamel, 2023), thus contributing to a broader dialogue about sustainable waste management practices.

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Disclosure of Interests

This study has no potential conflict of interest.

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Pieter van der Hijden

Gaming/Simulation and Sustainable Development Goals: From Awareness via Alignment to Accountability and Impact-by-Design

Abstract

In 2015, all 193 UN member states adopted Resolution 70/1, titled “Transforming our world; the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development”, briefly summarized as the 17 Sustainable Development Goals and the 169 subgoals. The implementation of this program is in the hands of national governments, but the program is so ambitious that the commitment of all social actors is indispensable.

Over the years, governments, companies, academia, non-governmental organizations, and citizens involvement in the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) has evolved. Various sources distinguish four different development stages:

1. Awareness: Bluff your way in SDGs.
2. Alignment: Align with the SDGs.
3. Action: Brace yourself for an SDG tender.
4. Accountability: Commit yourself to SDG impact-by-design.

At each stage, organizations can benefit from a different type of games. Each stage therefore offers the gaming/simulation community different opportunities.

The presentation is based on the author’s experiences as coordinator of the Global Working Group Fablabs & SDGs during the past eight years. Fablabs are open workplaces for digital manufacturing; they are located in 143 countries worldwide; 2,627 fablabs were officially registered as of 31 March 2026.

Keywords: SDGs, Impact-by-design, Accountability, Fablabs, Gaming/Simulation, Sustainability, Climate change, Urban planning, Public participation, Society in transition, Dealing with crisis, Disaster management.

1 Introduction

The global program for the UN Sustainable Development Goals (see text box) runs from 2016 to 2030 (United Nations, 2015). Implementation is in the hands of individual governments, but public resources are completely insufficient. For this reason alone, a contribution is expected from every organization: local governments, companies, civil society organizations, academia, and individuals. This also applies to gaming/simulation professionals and, for example, to fablabs (open workshops for digital manufacturing) (Gershenfeld et al., 2017), the author’s field of work.

Figure 1. Official Flag of the UN Sustainable Development Goals.

In the early years of the SDG program, organizations everywhere were mainly active in the area of awareness-raising. They made an effort on a voluntary basis or through funding to convey the SDG message. However, very little was done “on the ground”. Information material was available in many languages. For example, the flag with the pictograms of the 17 goals is well-known. However, the underlying 169 targets that indicate much more concretely what the 17 goals are intended to achieve were hardly discussed.

Over the years, you see that organizations that have embraced the SDG message sooner or later take follow-up steps. Today, you can even speak of different maturity levels or stages that organizations as well as individuals can go through in their involvement with the SDGs. Of course, they determine themselves whether they take such steps and at what pace they do so.

Figure 2. Inclusive Business Maturity Levels.

(Source: Deloitte/UNDP)

Consulting firm Deloitte, together with the UNDP, tackled the central theme of the SDGs, “Leave No One Behind” (Deloitte/UNDP, 2016). They formulated six maturity levels for “inclusive busi-

nesses". By this they meant commercially viable activities in which the people at the base of the socio-economic pyramid (BoP) were involved, as a supplier, as an employee, and/or as a customer. The maturity levels according to Deloitte and UNDP are: The Bystander, the Accidental Tourist, the Responsible Citizen, the Explorer, the Builder, and finally the Champion.

These maturity levels focus on "inclusive businesses". When it comes to a more generic implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals, you see maturity levels such as Awareness, Alignment, Action, and Accountability (for impact). We will elaborate on these four more generic levels here and discuss what that means for gaming/simulation. We will give examples of games, preferably frame games where the structure is fixed but the content is variable/interchangeable. We will also introduce game components, parts of games that can be used as building blocks in multiple games. Thinking in and working with game components and frame games can significantly boost the efficiency of game development, keeping it affordable and accessible for an ever-increasing range of applications.

2 Maturity Levels

The image below (Figure 3) shows four generic SDG maturity levels. It shows the complete SDG flag with 17 goals under "Awareness", the focus of an organization on a limited number of goals under "Alignment", concrete activities towards one of the goals under "Action", and one specific "target" to which an organization commits under "Accountability".

Figure 3. Four generic SDG maturity levels.

We use this AAAA classification to indicate and describe what gaming/simulation (in a broad sense) can mean for the UN Sustainable Development Goals: Games can help organizations to reach the next maturity level (rite of passage). Conversely, the SDG maturity levels offer specific opportunities to gaming/simulation professionals.

The following section will discuss the four maturity levels in detail.

2.1 Awareness: Bluff your way in SDGs

We focus on organizations and/or individuals who know virtually nothing about the SDGs and we want to ensure that they can at least have a say in the matter. Although there already exists a vast number of games and other media aimed at raising awareness of the 17 SDGs, we missed directing our attention to the 169 subgoals or targets. Figure 4 shows the 17 goals (each with

its colored pictogram) and the corresponding targets for each goal (an average of 10 per goal). The figure as such is impossible to decipher, but it illustrates that you miss a lot of detail if you limit yourself to looking at the goals only and giving them your own interpretation.

Figure 4. The 17 Goals with the 169 Targets.

This was our reason to develop our own gaming activities to promote SDG awareness. We also wanted to offer our activity in multiple languages and prevent activities from resulting in a huge amount of paperwork. So we developed the game components SDG Crash Course and SDG Explorer; as accidental ‘by-catch’ this process produced two further game components, the SDG Translator and the SDG Gallery:

- The SDG Crash Course can be used as a prelude within other games;
- The SDG Explorer (Tool, 2018) is an online tool for browsing SDG goals and targets; this tool is used within different games to quickly analyze the SDG texts and avoid extensive paperwork; the tool is available in different languages.
- The SDG Translator (Tool, 2019) takes an SDG target number as input and produces the corresponding content in different languages.
- The “SDG Gallery” contains the SDG flags and icons in different languages (United Nations, 2016).

We will discuss the first two in more detail below.

The SDG Crash Course (Duration: 5 min.)

We developed a five-minute SDG Crash Course that we can use as a prelude within other games, but also in completely different contexts or even as a stand-alone game. The activity is long enough to teach participants who do not know anything about the topic aside from some key concepts, and short enough not to bore participants who are already knowledgeable. In essence, it is a short presentation, optionally followed by a short online test.

Figure 5. The SDG Crash Course.

These are the key concepts we want to convey:

1. The SDGs were not conceived top-down but are the result of a global bottom-up process that culminated in the UN resolution "Transforming our world: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development".
2. This resolution focuses on 17 Goals that are divided into 169 targets. To monitor progress, a set of 242+ indicators has been developed. Publications often only touch the 17 goals. We emphasize the 169 targets because they are much more concrete and informative.
3. All 193 member states of the United Nations have agreed on the SDGs.
4. The individual governments are responsible for implementing the goals.

5. The required budget is estimated at several trillion USD per year; the Multilateral Development Banks only have a budget of a few billion USD per year (factor 1,000!).
6. The bottom line of the whole program is: Leave No One Behind!

The SDG Explorer

We developed the SDG Explorer (Tool, 2018), an online tool for searching for SDG goals and targets. This tool is used within different games to quickly analyze the SDG texts and avoid extensive paperwork. The tool is available in different languages.

Figure 6 shows the online tool when it is launched: Only the 17 goals are visible. Each goal can be opened separately to inspect the corresponding targets. Zooming in and out to view everything properly is no problem. The tool allows you to search the full text so that you can browse through all goals and targets containing the search term or fragment, e.g. "kind" or "techn".

The SDG Explorer is currently available in Brazilian Portuguese, Dutch, English, French, Indonesian, and Spanish. It is also used in language education.

Figure 6. SDG Explorer With All 17 Goals Collapsed; Right: Zoom Function; Bottom Left: Menu with Search Function.

Gaming/Simulation

There are still countless organizations worldwide that have little knowledge of the SDGs. For gaming/simulation professionals, there are still extensive opportunities. It requires little prior knowledge to develop applications for the maturity level "Awareness". Keep in mind that the supply of games is quite high and competition from other providers is also high.

Table 1. Gaming/Simulation for Awareness.

Properties	Awareness
Size of target group	Very large
Type of games	Quick to learn, quick to play; playing time 1 hour max.
Existing supply	Very large
Required SDG expertise of gaming/simulation professionals	Alignment

2.2 Alignment: Align with the SDGs

We focus on organizations (you could also think of individuals!) that are aware of the SDGs and want to take the next step: to align their organization with the SDGs.

We let an organization focus on a selection of up to four SDGs. We do this for two reasons:

- The number of 17 SDGs is too large to be effectively manageable; a selection of four goals is more manageable.
- The selection itself forces you to think about your priorities.

We developed:

- A game: The SDG Alignment Game. This results in an SDG profile, a possible policy change, and a reflection on your place within your own network (Van der Hijden et al., 2018).
- A game component: An online overview of all Fablab SDG profiles, updated monthly and supplemented over the years with relevant country information (WG Fablabs & SDGs, 2018–2026).

Figure 7. An SDG Alignment Game Session (Before the SDG Explorer Existed; Participants “Drowned” in Paper).

The SDG Alignment Game

We developed the SDG Alignment Game (Van der Hijden et al., 2018), a game/workshop format that aligns your organization with the SDGs. The result is an SDG profile, a possible policy shift, and a reflection on your place within a relevant network.

Figure 8. Collage of the SDG Goals, A Completed Alignment Game Planning Board, and A Partial Overview of Fablab SDG Profiles.

This game is intended for the staff members of an organization. Together they go through the following steps:

1. The participants decide together which four SDGs they find most suitable for their organization. They determine what they mean by "suitable". We want them to take the next step towards SDG involvement; we do not want to be normative in this. They place the SDG cards of their selection in the first column of a planning board.
2. The participants formulate together why they chose the four SDGs and write down their reasons in the second column of the planning board.

3. To get a better picture of the four selected SDGs, participants also look at the corresponding targets. They then discuss how their organization could align its current activities with the SDGs. They document this in the third column of the planning board.
4. Finally, the participants investigate which networks their organization belongs to. For example, fablabs belong to national and regional organizations of fablabs, but also to the global fablab network. The participants answer the following question about such a network: Suppose that SDG profiles are also used within your network, what would your organization want to offer to that network? And what would you like to ask that network to offer to you? They write down their conclusions in the fourth column of the planning board.

After completion, it is up to the organization itself to further implement these intentions. In the case of the fablabs, the Working Group Fablabs & SDGs supports them by collecting all SDG profiles and visualizing them in a global overview (see the Overview of SDG Profiles game component).

Fablabs are autonomous organizations. They can also choose their own path in determining an SDG profile. This will then still be processed via the Working Group.

Figure 9. Info Card Germany with Part of the Fablab SDG Profiles.

The Overview of SDG Profiles

We developed the Overview of SDG Profiles game component (WG Fablabs & SDGs, 2018–2026). Initially this is intended for fablabs and their SDG profiles, but all components are open source and relatively easy to apply to other organizations with SDG profiles and their networks.

Within the fablab network the working method is as follows:

1. Fablabs submit their SDG profile online; if they want to update it later, they can upload a new version.
2. The WG Fablabs & SDGs carries out a light test and adds it to a public repository.
3. The WG generates a new and up-to-date overview every month and puts it online.

This game component started as an overview of Fablab SDG profiles only, but over time this overview has been enriched with all kinds of other information, especially at country level, such as:

- the frequency with which the individual SDGs appear in the profiles,
- area and population size of the countries and, derived from this, the “fablab density” per country,
- a hyperlink to a possible UNDP Accelerator Lab in that country (Portal: UNDP Accelerator Labs), and
- a hyperlink to the very comprehensive online interactive country dashboard of the Sustainable Development Solutions Network (Sachs et al., 2024).

Gaming/Simulation

There are also alternative games for SDG Alignment and conversely, ours could also be used in a different context (see the following paragraph on spin-offs). The Overview of SDG Profiles game component is custom-made but open source and therefore adaptable.

Table 2. Gaming/Simulation for Alignment.

Properties	Alignment
Size of target group	Big
Type of games	Compact, highly structured, concrete results, and follow-up possibilities; playing time 4 hours max.
Existing supply	Small
Required SDG expertise of Gaming/Simulation professionals	Action

Spin-off

- The SDG Alignment Game followed by the visualization can be used in many situations. For example by students individually, as a class, as a school.

- The Overview of SDG Profiles game component is useful in situations where one wants to provide participants with extensive information about one or more countries.
- The Overview of SDG Profiles game component can also be used as a starting point for data-enriched storytelling.

2.3 Action: Brace Yourself for an SDG Tender

We focus on organizations that want to go beyond adjusting their existing policy and/or placing their SDG profile on their website. These are organizations that want to take action. They are no longer waiting for donations or subsidies but want to make a productive contribution in the right direction themselves, for example by registering for tenders.

Our advice: Prepare for SDG tenders, have your paperwork in place, and professionalize your staff.

Figure 10. Overview of Actions Such as the Fablab Network Initiated.

Organizations that want to make a productive contribution to the SDGs, apart from providing donations and subsidies, show diverse behaviors. We see that they sometimes organize regionally (Asia), sometimes sectorally (healthcare), sometimes along humanitarian values (disaster response).

Our sincere advice is: Prepare for SDG tenders, have your paperwork in place, and professionalize your staff.

On closer inspection we identified the following learning needs, i.e. gaming opportunities:

1. Prepare for SDG tenders: We developed materials to explain the tender procedure of Multi-lateral Development Banks and a game to arrive at an expression of interest.
2. Have your paperwork in place: A tender often works with short deadlines in which you have to deliver something. You have to be prepared for that. We thought of an approach such as the SDG profile: A game/workshop to produce content such as a company profile and a harvesting process to be able to share that content with each other.

3. Professionalize your staff: This topic is very broad. It is about project-based work, the route from prototype to product, business-like organization, organizational health, and safety.

We gauged interest in the topics 1. Prepare for SDG tenders, 2. Have your paperwork in place, and 3. Professionalize your staff. The results were disappointing. The organizations involved have not made that much progress yet and the topics seemed too boring and bureaucratic. The third topic is quite broad, not specific to the SDGs, and there is already a large supply of training courses in this area.

Gaming/Simulation

Our ideas for support through gaming/simulation on the way to and during the Action stage did not seem to catch on very well. That is why we chose a different approach:

- The UNDP has set up Accelerator Labs in more than 100 countries (Portal: UNDP Accelerator Labs). Each lab practices three areas of expertise:
 - a. Exploring the environment: Understanding what is going on in society, what is needed, and where opportunities lie,
 - b. Developing solutions: Program of requirements, prototypes, production,
 - c. Implementing solutions: Involving the various stakeholders, agreements in principle, organizational development, procedures, and training for this.
- The expertise of the organizations we work with, i.e. fablabs, is mainly in developing solutions. We could extend that expertise to exploring the environment and implementation. Systems thinking, system dynamics, and gaming/simulation could be methods and techniques that transcend the expertise.
- First steps in this direction are:
 - “The Quest for the Data Workbench”: A workshop where participants gain experience with data analysis and the tools that come in handy (Repository: Workshop Data Workbench),
 - A pilot workshop full of gaming elements for local administrators leading to SDG-related project proposals, and
 - A frame game to develop an (SDG) implementation plan.

Table 3. Gaming/Simulation for Action.

Properties	Action
Size of target group	Medium
Type of games	Varied mix of training games; playing time 8 hours max.
Existing supply	Big but fuzzy
Required SDG expertise of gaming/simulation professionals	Accountability

2.4 Accountability: Commit yourself to SDG impact-by-design

We focus on organizations that want more than a contribution in the right direction, organizations that want to take responsibility for the actual implementation of one of the SDG targets, for example in the context of their own city. This may well be broader than what the organization normally does. They will therefore have to broaden their activities or enter into a joint venture with other organizations.

The SDG Impact Game

Organizations that want to take responsibility for the actual implementation of one of the SDG targets, e.g. in the context of their own city, face a special challenge. To help with this, we have developed the SDG Impact Game (Repository: SDG Impact Game).

Suppose your organization is quite familiar with developing and delivering technical training. You are convinced that this contributes to SDG target 4.4. But can you demonstrate this (Rogers, 2014)?

Figure 11. Accountability for Impact (Collage).

We propose not to see impact as something you work towards, but as something your design process starts with – impact by design. If you reason back from SDG 4.4 within the context of a city, for example, you will undoubtedly come back to training courses, but

- the specifications for these trainings are much more closely aligned with the impact to be achieved, and
- the activities required will be more comprehensive than simply providing training.

An organization may need to diversify to accommodate all of this; this may be a reason to enter into a joint venture with other organizations. And there is another factor: The implementation of the SDGs involves much larger sums than public funds can release. It is therefore desirable for organizations to be able to develop commercially viable activities that achieve the desired impact without placing too heavy a burden on public funds.

For this challenge we have developed a game: The SDG Impact Game. The participants play in groups, first taking on the role of a think tank at a ministry, then the role of a director of an SDG Investment Fund, and finally the role of an organization such as a fablab that wants to guarantee a certain impact. It is clear that such a game must be tailor-made, adapted for example to the country where the game is played. Therefore, the game is a frame game that we can load with specific content for a certain country. As content we use the country profiles from the annual Sustainable Development Report (Sachs et al., 2024) and statistics from the fablab network (WG Fablabs & SDGs, 2018–2026).

Gaming/Simulation

The SDG Impact Game is the first game we developed for this maturity level. It is clear that more can follow.

Table 4. Gaming/Simulation for Accountability.

Properties	Accountability
Size of target group	Small
Type of games	Tailor-made course with lots of interaction and consultation; playing time 16 hours max.
Existing supply	Small and custom-made
Required SDG expertise of gaming/simulation professionals	Accountability

3 Bottom Line

The table below shows the differences between gaming/simulation as customers move through the different maturity levels. Here we summarize the opportunities we see for gaming/simulation, the suggestion that we have to keep gaming affordable, and the challenges for gaming/simulation professionals.

Table 5. Gaming/Simulation for SDGs.

Properties	Awareness	Alignment	Action	Accountability
Size of target group	Very large	Big	Medium	Small
Type of games	Quick to learn, quick to play; playing time 1 hour max.	Compact, highly structured, concrete results, and follow-up possibilities; playing time 4 hours max.	Varied mix of training games; playing time 8 hours max.	Tailor-made course with lots of interaction and consultation; playing time 16 hours max.
Existing supply	Very large	Small	Big but fuzzy	Small and custom-made
Required SDG expertise of gaming/simulation professionals	Alignment	Action	Accountability	Accountability

Opportunities

Organizations go through different maturity levels when developing their SDG engagement. Each maturity level can benefit from its own type of gaming/simulation (see table above). Therefore, each maturity level offers its own opportunities for the gaming/simulation industry.

Efficiency

Custom game development is expensive. Budgets are limited. To keep customization affordable, the efficiency of game development must be improved. Therefore, we recommend the use of frame games, the application of reusable modules or game components, and even extending the latter to continuous gaming paths (chain games):

1. Frame games: Aim for frame games where only the content is specific but the game structure (frame) is generic.
2. Game components: Work with game components that you can reuse in multiple games.
3. Chain games: Create a gaming path of multiple consecutive games where the output of one game is the input for the next.

Expertise

For the individual gaming/simulation professional this means everything:

- Determine your own maturity level and offer interventions to organizations up to that level.
- Keep evolving and make sure that in a year you are one level further than you are now.

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Implementation of and Learning from Transversal Thinking in the Hybrid Localized SDG Simulation Model SustainDarmstadt2035

Abstract

The localized SDG simulation model SustainDarmstadt2035 is a digital simulation model that integrates and implements event formats that are designed to contribute to a transformative sustainability framework. We consider these formats to be a new best practice because they combine analog conversational and digital methods to enable participants to cope with the complexity of dynamic interactions and interrelations between the diverse target dimensions of the SDGs on the municipal level of Darmstadt (Germany) by training them to prepare, discuss, and take decisions in simulated situations of multi-actor governance. As part of DELTA (Darmstadt Energy Lab for Technologies in Application), a real-world energy transition laboratory on the municipal level of the Wissenschaftsstadt Darmstadt (City of Science Darmstadt), SustainDarmstadt2035 and its derivative formats are experimentally developed and implemented, integrating the methodology presented in this contribution. Finally, we propose to employ this and develop similar approaches to specifically enable current and future decision-makers to identify and (re)design overlooked (mis)alignments and interactions of current and future developments while co-creating new transversal bodies of knowledge and rationales on an eye-to-eye level with involved actors in the urban sphere.

Keywords: Sustainable urban development, Transversal city, Complexity management, Transdisciplinarity, Roleplay, Simulation, Decision-making and negotiation.

1 Purpose and Design Principles of SustainDarmstadt2035

1.1 Identification of key requirements

The localized SDG simulation model SustainDarmstadt2035 is a digital simulation model that integrates and implements event formats designed to contribute to a transformative sustainability framework by facilitating and demanding more complex, coherent, locally contextualizing, and therefore more transversal decision-making processes. For that purpose, it combines analog conversational and digital on-screen methods to allow participants to improve strategies for coping with the complexity of dynamic interactions and interrelations between the various goals and respective target dimensions of the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) originating in the localized perspective of Darmstadt. From the player's perspective, participants embark on a journey to jointly prepare, discuss, and take decisions in multi-actor governance settings in which virtual and real processes are constantly being integrated into a hybrid structure: Knowledge regarding the circumstances of sustainable development across all spatial scales from local to global is presented in a virtualized form that is geared to trigger among

participants the realization, discussion, understanding, and design of locally entangled elements, processes, and hence unfolding complexities.

In the context of education for sustainable development (ESD) methodologies, but also urban development processes in general, there already exist SDG-related simulations, games, and other teaching and learning formats. To our knowledge, these employ the SDG framework mostly as a tabulating system in order to help participants recognize the multitude of simultaneous goals when steering action towards sustainable development and, at least in the context of German higher education, hardly aim for a high level of ambition that would, for instance, constructively address areas of conflict in sustainable development (Müller-Christ et. al, 2017).

Drawing on our own experience, if new formats and their underlying methodologies are to be designed primarily for highly educated participants such as current and future decision-makers, they should not only aim (1) to meet this aforementioned high level of ambition, but additionally (2) provide and generate detailed inter- and transdisciplinary insights on how closely, multi-referentially, intricately, and dynamically intertwined the SDGs and their corresponding measures are, which also depends on which measures exactly are taken in which constellations and under which circumstances, including spatiality. And (3) they should, again based on our own experiences and presumptions, evoke substantial content-related involvement of participants. To this end, they must offer facilities for cognitive engagement, i.e. “the active participation in the construction of knowledge” (Gatti et al., 2019, p. 668) that is geared to transgress the realm of virtual simulation by integrating cross-references to ongoing real-world-processes on different spatial levels ranging from the neighborhood to the city, the region, the nation state, the EU, and finally the world as a planetary system (for the role of transgressive practices and processes for sustainable development in the creation of knowledge, see West, 2023; 2019; 2014a; 2014b; and West et al., 2023).

We assume that the provision for the three aspects mentioned above can be methodologically integrated in decision-making discourses as well as in educational curricula by grounding their elements, references, and discussions in local contexts, taking into account their specific strategies, processes, scopes, goals, actors/stakeholders, problems, and problem solution resources. Following this principle, the localized level SDG simulation model SustainDarmstadt2035 outlined below becomes a valuable tool to leverage underestimated potentials: to elicit, reflect on, and alter mental models, which are a “relatively enduring and accessible, but limited, internal conceptual representation of an external system whose structure maintains the perceived structure of that system” (Doyle and Ford, 1998, p. 17). Following this theoretical approach, mental models emerge from individual lived-in realities, are applied context-related, and can be altered through self-critical reflection that considers contradictory observations. We therefore argue that for a variety of contexts such as political-administrative decision-making at the municipal level or the professional and academic education of decision-makers, SustainDarmstadt2035 might be an educational tool that taps into ignored potentials to bring about highly ambitious transformative ESD while providing a methodological foundation to perform comparative and explorative research on its effects on urban-level transformative action towards sustainable development.

1.2 SustainDarmstadt2035 aims to be a discourse enhancement tool, not a probabilistic or accurate prediction tool

When society is seen as a planetary system, the discursively mediated dynamics or disrupted processes of human actors evaluating and dealing with the impacts of taken or not taken measures are inherently volatile, or at least not reliably predictable with regard to when they will trigger other processes and actions, and how these in turn will influence its poly-contextual, multiply overlapping subsystems as well as the earth system altogether. This notion calls for the integration of Luhmann's system theory approach (cf. Luhmann, 1984) in combination with the concept of transversal orientation (cf. West, 2021; 2019) and a hitherto underrepresented analytic understanding of spatial relations and of the interplay of heterogeneous spatial conceptualizations, while consistently returning to the municipal level as a fixed spatial scale (cf. Elverfeldt, 2014; Giddens, 1997). To allow for this emerging complexity to partially appear within SustainDarmstadt2035 and thereby enable transformative reasoning as well as scientific testing of the implemented methods, it is a constant key requirement and challenge of SustainDarmstadt2035 to create and maintain openness towards incorporating the greatest possible variety of aspects or thought experiments instead of containing inevitable uncertainties outside of technological advances, ecological impact, or economic rationalities.

1.3 A hybrid structure to trigger transversal sustainable urban-level development

The design and hybrid structure of SustainDarmstadt2035 builds on the assumption that its potential can only be leveraged by integrating real-world aspects that deliberately trigger interexchange between parts of the virtual simulation and issues, processes, spaces, and actors in the "real" world. This starts by communicating the framing context of the format, which is the Darmstadt Energy Lab for Technologies in Application – DELTA. It is a real-world laboratory for the energy transition that is publicly funded by the former Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action (BMWK), now the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (BMWE), to implement and roll out primarily technical-technological solutions in and for Darmstadt, combined with an experimental approach to find and develop new ways to bring about the energy transition altogether and to form new alliances to take practical steps towards sustainable development for Darmstadt and the world (cf. Kohne et al., 2023; West, 2023). The tool and event format SustainDarmstadt2035 plays a crucial role within the DELTA Energy Academy to foster experimentation and critical exploratory communication within the DELTA consortium as well as between DELTA and the rest of the city/society (cf. Figure 2 below; West, 2023). Previously and continuously elaborated, created, and integrated issues, processes, results, as well as alliances, cooperations, and networks that have been formed over the course of the project (cf. West, 2023, p. 268) are invited to contribute to the ongoing development and adaptation of the SustainDarmstadt2035 format. This method helps the simulation processes to open up "windows of opportunity" that are being used to approach, understand, and shape the sustainable development at the urban level in a transversal way, thus "transgressing established or dominant categories of distinction and differentiation" (West, 2023, p. 254; West, 2021; West et al., 2023) by experimenting and establishing new modes of thinking and acting, new forms of co-creation, urban governance, and rationales of action (cf. West, 2023; West, 2019).

While an array of aspects of SustainDarmstadt2035 is tailored to fit the municipal level of Darmstadt, including some of its idiosyncrasies, the simulation is designed to be applicable in other German cities as well. This is because its core element is neither preciseness nor accuracy of forecast, but qualitative discursive enhancement based on possible but inherently volatile development paths. To the contrary, there are many similarities and cross-references that trigger insights, recognitions, questions, and critical reflections that are relevant to most German cities and beyond, even if some of them might need to be translated to a different spatial setting or can be identified as being less or not relevant at all. In the context of sustainable urban development, relying on interdependency and a common orientation of cities, especially the latter realization even can trigger highly relevant knowledge building for decision-making.

1.4 Complementary framework for “Scenario Simulation Mode” and “Exploration Mode”

SustainDarmstadt2035 is designed to be a complementary framework for integrating different modes of knowledge generation: It can be used in an “exploration mode” as well as in a “scenario simulation mode” which can also be seen as a simulation game. Their separate or mixed implementation depends on participants’ knowledge and the goals of the event format in which the game is played. While the first focuses on specific measures and their outcomes, scrutinizing them in more depth and breadth by testing them under specifically designed varying assumptions, strategies, and conditionalities, the latter focuses more broadly on the systemic interdependencies of sustainable development and is designed to trigger critical discussion on and reflection of certain topics by deploying scripted events and influences – potentially triggering changes of mental models of sustainable development. Even though the exploration mode is designed to support the functionality of the scenario simulation mode and vice versa, this article focuses on the latter due to the fact that its main features align with established modes of teaching, including in the field of public and private management.

The scenario simulation mode of SustainDarmstadt2035 operates with game-like elements and state-of-the-art knowledge to stimulate discussion on and cognitive engagement with a potentially overwhelmingly complex system of multi-referential, poly-contextual, dynamically interactive processes, elements, and interrelations that play a role in achieving or failing to achieve sustainable development goals (cf. West, 2014, p. 118), which is operationalized by computing and depicting percentage changes in the achievement of each single SDG as well as the average achievement level of all SDGs as main performance indicators. The event format can and should be seen as a hybrid of virtual and real rationales, because on one hand it reduces the world to a more or less manageable set of values and rules to simulate and play with, while on the other hand it is imbued with discursive ties to the ‘real world’ with its ambiguities, enormous complexity, ties to locally embedded processes, and unforeseeable external and internal events. In SustainDarmstadt2035, this hybridity serves to remind participants – as in serious gaming approaches – that they are not merely playing a game, in the sense that rather than considering it as not real, they are taking existentially relevant glimpses at and uncovering linkages to possible futures in the real world and possible ways to actually influence ongoing and future processes. This hybrid characteristic of shaping virtual, real, and virtually real futures is amplified by the circumstance that SustainDarmstadt2035 can also be used in an exploration mode, a more extensive, feature-rich analytical tool that supports various decision-affiliated stakehold-

ers such as the climate action advisory board for Wissenschaftsstadt Darmstadt [City of Science Darmstadt], the currently emerging energy advisory board, as well as civil society initiatives developing and carrying out measures within the discursive field of sustainable urban development in and for Darmstadt. In both modes, the applied methodology is primarily designed to encourage participants to identify positive and negative synergy effects as possible outcomes of measures that have not yet been thought of or brought together in specific ways outside of the game to identify, create, compensate for, or avoid certain positive or negative synergies. To reinforce this process, participants are told that without identifying these synergies, as in the real world, it will not be possible to achieve considerable progress on any individual, let alone the full set of SDGs.

2 What's in It? Setup and Contents

2.1 Playing SustainDarmstadt2035: Topology of the scenario simulation mode setup

To provide insight into SustainDarmstadt2035 as a simulation game, the topology of the scenario simulation mode setup is illustrated in Figure 1. The topology consists of spheres and their interactions through digital, analog, and discursive elements, including communicational key parameters required to bring the simulation model into operation as part of an event format. It deploys team play, role play, and scenario-like narratives to invite participants to critically test, reflect, and creatively design assumed understandings of current and future relations and processes of sustainable development at the urban level of Darmstadt and beyond.

In the scenario, the participants form the Climate Action Advisory Board for the City of Science Darmstadt, with each person additionally taking on a different role with different proposed core themes and pre-existing personal and professional experiences. The participants are asked to have open rounds of discussions and mutual counseling to make and improve decisions regarding the measures to be implemented next in order to gradually achieve the 17 equally important SDGs by 2035. The simulation progresses in rounds, with each round representing 1 year and comprising four operational steps embedded in group conversation (see also Figure 1): (1) Pre-viewing, discussing, and selecting measures; (2) activating measures through the facilitator; (3) computing triggered effects; and (4) monitoring triggered effects. The facilitator assists by operating the digital sphere, asking for and activating measures, providing technical and procedural support, and asking for reasoning and critical reflection, especially if these would be neglected. This would particularly be the case if participants focus too much on gaming rationales, such as purely mathematic or formulaic reasoning, bypassing context and qualitative aspects.

When a selected measure is played out (Phase 2 in Figure 1), it has a direct impact on the achievement levels of those SDGs that are most strongly influenced by that measure (Phase 3 in Figure 1). Which and how many measures can be played is limited by two types of budgets (see dashed box between Phase 2 and 3 in Figure 1) from which the corresponding amount is deducted when a measure is played. The available budgets can be increased or decreased in different ways (triggered in Phase 4). Since each measure has manifold other potential direct and indirect effects, these are generalized and additionally included in the form of so-called "interactions" at the target level: A predefined part of the change in achievement level of the

respective SDGs is passed on to influence other SDG achievement levels. This impulse triggers an independent cascade of effects that is continuously played out in subsequent rounds, with the original impulse gradually fading. In addition, there is a predefined external degradation effect that reduces the achievement level of several SDGs each round. This is why new impulses and strategies to leverage synergies are needed to achieve higher SDG achievement levels, and participants are informed about this logic to stimulate their search for synergetic interdependencies.

Figure 1. Communicative Topology and Technical Setup Topology of the Scenario Simulation Mode in SustainDarmstadt2035.

The scenario simulation mode encourages and gives participants opportunity to discuss future effects and scenarios beyond the digital and technical setup of SustainDarmstadt2035. These explorations can take on the character of thought experiments (West, 2021; West et al., 2023)

when these thought experiments produce unexpected outcomes because they allow participants to critically reflect their own assumptions about interdependencies, aspects, and elements of the real world beyond the scenario simulation.

Further, the scenario simulation is designed to foster transversal thinking (cf. West, 2023; 2019; 2014a; 2014b, and West et al., 2023), i.e. the ability to re-focus on real-world processes and multiple perspectives, regardless of dominant categories of difference or distinction, and regardless of established ways of preparing solutions for sustainable development and action. To give a simple example how this can be methodologically implemented: A participating student preparing for a senior civil service career informs the other participants about a local civil society renewable energy initiative and its methods and goals. The knowledge that local civil society initiatives can be a central actor to carry out specifically relevant measures in the scenario simulation is new to the other participants or players and can trigger further processes of reflection and exploration. Thus, self-owned knowledge from the real world is brought into the system and can be woven into discussions and tentatively developed strategies. In a situation like this, transversal thinking can be applied by imagining potential in-game scenarios emerging from the idea to support the initiative: How and with whom could they form an alliance in a next step? What would follow-up measures look like, and what circumstances do they need to contribute to sustainable development? Which phenomena or developments could be triggered in different parts of society? The fact that the pertaining civil society initiative continuously contributes to the pool of ideas and development of SustainDarmstadt2035 increases the chances of identifying and transversally elaborating previously invisible synergies and missing links that can lead to substantially more sustainable developments.

To foster the intended functionality of the tool, it is crucial that it is introduced, moderated, and supervised by specifically skilled facilitators (Figure 1) who are trained and have the background to handle the high complexity, poly-contextuality, and transversality of this hybrid real-world simulation model.

Also, they need to be able to assist or advise playing participants to resume discussions and reflect on them afterwards in the same way that they critically approach real-world interrelations while encouraging them to engage with real-world topics and actors in an open-minded, co-creative, constructive, curious, and transversal way.

2.2 Incorporating local stakeholder knowledge during the initial construction cycle of the local-level SDG simulation model SustainDarmstadt2035

While building the knowledge base to apply the methodology outlined above, it is necessary to readapt the UN SDGs in a process-oriented transversal way which also localizes the globally defined SDG goals and targets. To show how this was initially done considering the different respective spatial and institutional levels, Figure 2 gives an exemplary overview of the respective process for SDG 7, “Affordable and clean energy”.

Figure 2. Exemplary Process-Oriented Transversal Localizing Readaptation of SDG Goals and Targets as Key Governance Parameters in SustainDarmstadt2035.

Phase 1 of the first complete construction cycle of the local-level SDG simulation model SustainDarmstadt2035 is shown in Figure 2 and consists of three methodological steps. The iterative process starts with incorporating local stakeholder knowledge into a process of localized readaptation of the SDG goals and targets (Figure 2, Step 1). For that reason, we carried out workshops with local actors from civil society, such as a local renewable energy production initiative, Fridays for Future, and the Local Agenda 2030, from the city administration, the magistrate, municipal and local councils, the Climate Action Advisory Board, the local energy provider, and from different fields of expertise on the energy transition who are members of the DELTA consortium. They were instructed to define, complete, and readapt the SDGs as well as to reflect upon their current achievement level from the local point of view, setting Darmstadt as the main frame of action. To increase compatibility with supralocal levels, the outcomes were completed and integrated by way of the following procedure, which is also shown in Figure 2 (Figure 2, Step 2): Taking a worldwide scope, outcomes are first compared with UN-level SDGs and targets to detect which locally generated goals are fully covered and what aspects are missing, misleading, contradictory, or wrong as a result of the altered spatial and discursive context. Moving down the different spatial levels of institutional authority, multiple definitions,

translations, and derivations of the SDGs are identified, compared, readapted, and incorporated. This phase of iteration continued until all present elements and encountered aspects were considered and/or integrated. The obtained set of localized SDG goals and targets were then processed (Figure 2, Step 3) to form the foundation for subsequent phases. In Phase 2, previous and new participants were asked to discuss, assess, and quantify within this fixed set of goals and targets how improving the achievement level of one specific SDG – bearing in mind its targets – directly impacts the achievement levels of the other SDGs, identifying the 2–5 most influenced ones.

The initial construction cycle of SustainDarmstadt2035 is completed by Phase 3: It is informed by workshops in which participants formulate, collect, revise, and critically discuss measures, including those guiding political-administrative policies or concepts and activities of local initiatives, in light of their potential to invoke real-world progress towards achieving the respective SDGs in alignment with the localized set of SDG targets. The generated, revised, and readapted measures are then translated and incorporated into SustainDarmstadt2035 to be analyzed in the exploration mode and to be deployed in the scenario simulation mode.

3 Need for Formats and Methodologies of Transversal Knowledge Building for Sustainable Development in and Through Decision Makers

In this contribution, we outlined the theoretical and operational concept of a new best practice format in the field of simulation and gaming that aims to contribute to a transformative sustainability framework. To conclude, we call on actors from the field of simulation, gaming, sustainable urban development and planning to experiment with, develop, and implement new complementary or compatible concepts, formats, elements, and processes that integrate aspects, parameters and methods presented in this contribution. The aim is not to reduce but to increase the complexity of the matters discussed, while integrating knowledge that transcends the boundaries of disciplines, rationales, fields of action and spatial scales. In line with the goal of contributing to a transformative sustainability framework, we emphasize that in order to ensure the functioning and impact of ESD, it is crucial that formats such as SustainDarmstadt2035 must be specifically designed to reach current and future decision-makers, in addition to enabling and empowering everyone to act sustainably. The goal is that participants are empowered to identify and (re)design previously invisible (mis)alignments and interactions between current and future developments while co-creating new transversal bodies of knowledge and rationales on an equal footing with involved actors in the urban sphere.

Disclosure of Interests

The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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Chapter Education

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Beyond the Textbook: Using Simulated Conflicts to Prepare Educators for Teaching in Times of Crisis

Abstract

This article examines the implementation of clinical simulations in an online format as a means of practicing soft skills during wartime or times of crisis. With the shift to remote learning and training necessitated by crisis conditions, online simulations have proven to be an effective alternative to traditional face-to-face methods. Designed to address complex interpersonal challenges, these simulations provide a safe, controlled environment for both trainees and participants to practice communication, conflict resolution, and decision-making skills in scenarios mirroring real-life challenges.

The article details the methodology of adapting clinical simulations to the online medium, including designing branching roadmaps for dynamic scenarios, training actors for virtual settings, and developing techniques to create a realistic, immersive experience through Zoom.

The article highlights the benefits of simulation-based learning (SBL) by fostering experiential and reflective learning, even in remote environments. Participants reported the ability to apply the skills acquired during SBL to real-life challenges encountered in their professional roles.

This article underscores the potential of online clinical simulations to serve as a powerful training tool for developing soft skills under exceptional circumstances, ensuring accessibility and relevance even during crises.

Keywords: Online clinical simulations, Simulation-based learning (SBL), Communication skills, Online instructor training, soft skills training.

1 Introduction

On 7 October 2023, Hamas carried out an attack on Israeli communities located near the border with the Gaza Strip. During the assault, 1,167 individuals (INSS, 2026) were killed and 251 were abducted to Gaza. These events were widely perceived as traumatic by most Israeli citizens, leading to a profoundly diminished sense of personal security. The incident was extensively covered by the media and widely discussed on social networks, exerting a significant impact across various spheres of life, including the Israeli academic sector.

These events and the subsequent outbreak of war created an unprecedented reality for all Israeli society, Jews and Arabs alike. After the initial shock, it became evident that maintaining normalcy across various frameworks was imperative. At the Jerusalem Multidisciplinary College (JMC), as in other academic institutions nationwide, the need to establish a new routine alongside the ongoing conflict became apparent to ensure that all students, Jews and Arabs, would feel safe back on campus. This initiative aimed to support those remaining on the home front.

Located in central Jerusalem, JMC is home to a diverse student body of Jewish and Arab students, including Palestinian students from East Jerusalem. The events of 7 October generated a climate of mistrust among students, who began scrutinizing each other's social media expressions to gauge their peers' affiliations, positions, and identities. Concurrently, faculty members grappled with profound concerns: How could they continue teaching in an environment so deeply unsettled? Recognizing the profound impact of these extreme events, which had destabilized the delicate social fabric enabling coexistence on campus, the college leadership acknowledged that conventional methods of addressing these challenges were inadequate and that a different approach was necessary.

The Center for the Development of Quality Instruction collaborated with the Campus Diversity and Inclusion Officer to design a workshop that would equip faculty with the tools needed to teach in a multicultural classroom during wartime. This workshop featured both theoretical and practical components. The theoretical segment outlined guidelines for classroom management during volatile periods, while the practical segment employed clinical simulations involving professional actors. These simulations depicted conflict scenarios arising between Jewish and Arab students during class. Participants were challenged to address realistic, extreme situations inspired by past incidents within the college. Professional actors portrayed Jewish and Arab students, reflecting their complex experiences during and after the 7 October events, while faculty members played themselves.

The primary goal of these simulations was to provide participants with strategies to foster a safe learning environment for all students, ensuring an inclusive space conducive to education. Given the national state of emergency, the simulations were conducted synchronously online via the Zoom platform.

2 Theoretical Background

Simulation-based learning is an active learning method that can be applied across various disciplines and with different types of participants. This method facilitates the replacement and enhancement of real experiences with guided, structured experiences replicating or simulating essential aspects of the real world in a fully interactive manner (Lateef, 2010). SBL offers practice-oriented learning, enabling learners to overcome the limitations of real-world learning scenarios (Chernikova et al., 2020).

As an educational tool, simulation creates the opportunity to modify and adapt certain aspects of reality, making learning and practice easier. Examples include practicing extreme scenarios, shortening response times, providing immediate feedback to participants, and more (Chernikova et al., 2020). Simulations have been shown to be particularly effective for teaching complex skills such as communication, critical thinking, decision-making, and problem-solving (Chernikova et al., 2020).

As outlined by Levin (2021), there are several models of SBL, including:

- Digital simulations requiring software and sometimes hardware to represent individuals or learning environments.
- Augmented Reality simulations allowing participants to engage in virtual reality experiences.

- Clinical simulations involving professional human actors trained to simulate conflictual encounters and dynamic scenarios between participants and actors.

In clinical simulations, learning occurs through interactions with the actors, who serve as the main learning medium (Levin, 2021). Using professional actors enhances the authenticity and realism of the simulation and allows for controlled scenario development. The actors receive detailed information about the personas they are portraying and undergo prior training to ensure they can convincingly perform the roles. Their professionalism enables them to respond to participants' actions and provide subjective feedback after the simulation.

3 Methodology

Clinical simulations can be applied across various disciplines and participant types, for example a classroom setting, an office setting, a hospital setting, a call center, a clinic, etc. The participants can be teachers, managers, health care providers, service providers, etc. Accordingly, the actors may portray students, parents, employees, patients, customers, etc. As a result, clinical simulations offer a realistic environment that mirrors actual interactions between service providers and their recipients.

SBL replaces and enhances real experiences with guided, fully interactive settings that replicate essential aspects of the real world (Lateef, 2010). It provides practice-driven training and thus helps to overcome real-world limitations (Chernikova et al., 2020).

Given the numerous benefits of using simulations for learning purposes, the Center for the Development of Quality Instruction at JMC has been employing clinical simulation methods to train faculty for the past eight years. Positive feedback from participants in these workshops highlighted the practical and effective tools gained from the simulation experience, becoming our anchor. This led to the decision to adopt clinical simulations as the preferred methodology for addressing the challenges following the events of 7 October.

These events created an atmosphere of introspection, and it became evident that the academic year would be launched online. Consequently, in line with the prevailing circumstances, it was decided to conduct the simulation workshops in an online clinical simulation format. However, to address needs arising from the eventual return to on-campus learning, most scenarios were designed to be adaptable for both online and face-to-face settings.

3.1 Designing the scenarios

The simulations are grounded in realistic, pre-written scenarios designed to meet the specific needs and learning objectives specified by the department requesting the workshop, which include instilling in lecturers the skills to lead a multicultural classroom in times of conflict and create a safe learning environment for all students.

Each scenario is built around a realistic conflict tailored to the specific needs identified by each department. Since it is impossible to predict how a particular trainee will respond in each situation, the scenarios incorporate a range of possible trainee behaviors. They are designed as flexible roadmaps, enabling actors to respond dynamically while guiding the interaction toward

the predefined learning objectives. This approach ensures that the simulation remains focused and purposeful. A detailed outline of a scenario template is provided in the appendix.

The goal of SBL is to guide the trainees and participants to respond to the presented situation in a manner that aligns with the desired learning outcomes. The simulation evolves based on how closely the trainee's responses approach or deviate from the expected learning outcome. At the end of the simulation, the trainee shares their feelings and experiences, receives subjective feedback from the actors, and engages in a plenary discussion for further analysis of each character's conduct.

As Levin et al. (2025) argue, encountering challenges during SBL plays a crucial role in shaping learning outcomes, particularly in soft-skill development. Their findings suggest that rather than hindering progress, these difficulties serve as catalysts for deeper learning. Experiencing such obstacles is essential for fostering optimal learning conditions. With this in mind, we deliberately designed our training scenarios to be challenging – and in some cases, even extreme – to push trainees beyond their comfort zones. However, all scenarios remained realistic, as they were based on actual cases from college history. Realism was evident in the trainees' reactions, with some displaying physiological stress responses such as accelerated heartbeat, dry mouth, trembling, and cold sweats during simulations.

Between October and December 2023, a total of ten simulation workshops were conducted. These workshops were held in single-discipline or dual-discipline formats for departments with similar characteristics and were specifically tailored to the needs and challenges of each department.

The scenarios addressed the following topics:

- Opening the first class of a course during wartime and creating a safe learning environment for all students.
- Working in pairs in mixed groups (Jewish–Arab students) in laboratories.
- Treating patients in college clinics who refuse treatment from a student of a different ethnicity.
- Managing provocative virtual backgrounds during synchronous online classes.
- Addressing challenges faced by clinical students struggling to work with patients from another ethnicity.
- Conducting political discussions in the classroom during wartime.
- Managing personal attacks between students in the classroom based on political or racial grounds.
- Identifying post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) symptoms and handling anxiety attacks in a post-traumatic student.

While the scenarios addressed diverse topics, the success of SBL lay not in the topics themselves, but in the meticulous design and preparation that preceded them.

3.2 The structure of the simulation workshops

Each simulation workshop consists of five stages:

1. Theoretical stage – equips participants with the knowledge and skills to navigate complex situations,
2. Experiential simulation activity,
3. Debriefing – explores the trainee’s feelings during the simulation,
4. Subjective feedback from the actors,
5. Plenary discussion involving all workshop participants for reflection and debriefing.

A detailed outline of the workshop structure is presented below.

Stage 1: Theoretical stage. This stage introduces complex situations that participants may encounter in their professional contexts and highlights the soft skills required to navigate them effectively. In parallel, it offers recommended guidelines for managing such situations with clarity and confidence.

Stage 2: Experiential simulation activity.

- I. A volunteer participant (trainee) is recruited to take part in the simulation.
- II. The trainee is provided with the context and relevant information for the simulation, such as:
 - the setting of the simulation (place, situation, background information),
 - the trainee’s goal in the simulation,
 - the time frame for the simulation.
- III. The simulation begins in response to one of the following alternatives:
 - (a) The trainee opens the scene.
 - (b) The actors open the scene.The scene develops into a scenario in which the trainee interacts with the actors.
- IV. The trainee’s course of action dictates the actors’ reaction and the development of the scenario.
- V. If the trainee’s behavior deviates from the desired learning outcomes, the actors exaggerate their reactions to the trainee’s behavior, thereby trying to coax the trainee to take a different approach to tackle the situation.
- VI. The simulation may conclude in one of the following means:
 - The allocated time elapses.
 - The trainee reaches the desired learning outcome.
 - The simulation is stopped by the workshop facilitator before the situation gets out of hand.

Stage 3: Debriefing. Once the simulation has been completed, the facilitator turns to the trainee and asks them to share what they felt during the simulation and how they feel now after it is completed.

Stage 4: Subjective feedback from the actors. Each actor shares with the trainee and the participants their feelings during and following the simulation. When relevant, they suggest what the trainee could have done to make them feel heard and accommodate their needs.

Stage 5: Plenary discussion. The facilitator initiates a plenary discussion, encouraging participants to reflect on the simulation and consider the perspectives shared by both the trainee and the actors. This stage serves as an opportunity to revisit and reinforce the guidelines presented during the initial phase, highlighting the essential role of thorough preparation in effectively addressing complex situations.

3.3 From face-to-face simulations to online simulations

One of the significant advantages of using simulations as a learning method is the transformation of theoretical discussions into vivid, practical debates. These discussions highlight the relevance of the issues being addressed in real-life, everyday situations. This shift in perspective helps to reduce resistance among participants to engage with the topic while immersed in their subject matter, the desired course of action in such situations, and the necessity of being prepared in advance.

Due to the emergency conditions in Israel at the time, the workshops could not be held in person and were instead conducted synchronously online via Zoom – a necessary compromise from the organizers' perspective. Research suggests that online clinical simulations are generally perceived as less effective than in-person simulations (Levin, 2024). With this in mind, we made critical adjustments to both the scenarios and the overall setting to enhance their effectiveness in an online format. To achieve this, the following measures were implemented:

- Ensuring the scenario translated well to a virtual format and remained realistic and impactful.
- Equipping actors with the necessary props to convincingly portray their characters.
- Adjusting participants' Zoom settings to create a sterile environment where only the trainee and actors were visible on screen.
- Ensuring all microphones, except for those of the trainee and actors, were muted.
- Deciding against recording the sessions to maintain a safe learning space and allow open, uninhibited discussion.

Surprisingly, conducting the simulation workshops synchronously online not only preserved their authenticity, but also enabled the creation of a realistic setting for the participants.

4 Conclusions

Ten workshops were conducted over the period between October and December 2023 with the aim of preparing the lecturers to teach their courses in a multicultural classroom in time of war. After each workshop we gathered feedback from participants and conducted postmortems with the relevant head of the department and the actors. We used the feedback as a learning curve to finetune and cater to the specific needs of each of the next workshops. At the end of the first

semester, in March 2024, a questionnaire was sent out to all participants to evaluate the workshops.

The data collected through the questionnaire, combined with our observations during the workshops and the feedback received afterward, were analyzed and led to the following conclusions:

1. The role of actors in the SBL process is pivotal. When actors performed their roles accurately as outlined in the scenario, participants perceived the scenarios as more realistic, leading to in-depth post-simulation discussions. These simulations were also rated as more effective by the participants.
Conversely, when actors deviated from the predefined script, the scenarios were deemed unrealistic, the simulations were perceived as less relevant and less effective, and the plenary discussions were more superficial. For example, in one case, an actress was tasked with portraying a student suffering from PTSD. The scenario had a dual objective: first, for participants to identify PTSD based on observable symptoms, and second, to learn how to manage anxiety attacks in a post-traumatic student. However, the actress exaggerated the symptoms outlined in the scenario, which misled participants and resulted in incorrect learning.
2. Despite initial resistance from some participants during the theoretical stage – who questioned the relevance of managing complex classroom situations to their own teaching contexts – the simulations proved to be a turning point. By presenting these challenges in an authentic and immersive way, the simulations highlighted both their relevance and the critical need for prior preparation. Ultimately, many participants acknowledged the value of engaging with these issues openly, leading to deeper reflection on the importance of addressing such situations directly and proactively.
3. Over the past eight years we have conducted face-to-face simulation workshops and collected feedback from trainees as well as from the plenary discussion stage of the workshops. The trainees and participants cited that the experience of the simulations shook them up. The trainees reported experiencing physiological symptoms of stress, such as dryness of the mouth, accelerated heartbeat, sweating, and shaking. Similar feedback was received after conducting the workshops online. This has led us to conclude that when conducted with the appropriate setup, online simulations can be as meaningful as face-to-face simulations.
4. SBL introduces a powerful experiential component by requiring participants to actively engage with the challenges of interpersonal communication, rather than simply discussing them in theoretical terms. This immersive approach encourages critical reflection and leaves a lasting impression on participants. For example, several lecturers reported feeling well-prepared to respond effectively to similar situations in real-time, drawing on insights gained during the simulation workshops. While a small number of participants initially perceived the simulations as unrealistic, some of them later revised their views – often six months to a year afterward – when confronted with comparable real-life scenarios in the classroom. In these moments, they recognized the practical value of the simulations and reported feeling confident in their ability to manage the situation successfully.

5 Implications and Applications

Our extensive experience with simulations in faculty training has allowed us to continually refine scenario design, improve actor training, and challenge participants to enhance learning. Encouraged by participants' positive feedback on the practical tools acquired, we have extended the use of this method to additional contexts and applications.

This approach has been expanded to include not only academic staff but also other campus groups who encounter challenges in navigating cultural diversity. Tailored simulation workshops have been developed to meet the specific needs of these groups. The clinical simulation methodology can be adapted to any professional context where interpersonal and soft skills are essential.

5 Summary

Clinical simulations involving professional actors and real-time participation provide realistic scenarios that cannot be replicated by other methods. Our experience has demonstrated the effectiveness of this approach for learning purposes, whether conducted face-to-face or online – provided the actors adhere to their defined roles. SBL is a profound educational method that delivers lasting effects on learners' professional behavior.

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Appendix

Scenario form¹

Coaching topic:	
Trainee population:	
Scenario title:	
Initial information for the trainee: The information the trainee receives before the simulation, to understand what is going to happen (everything they would realistically know in the "real" situation): Who they are meeting, when, and whether there are prior acquaintances, etc. Conversation objective and time limit: The purpose of the encounter/conversation 7 or 10 minutes	
Scenario goal: e.g., gaining cooperation, resolving conflict, delivering difficult news Debriefing points: Guidelines, communication skills model, and anything you want to cover in the post-simulation debrief	
Participants: Trainee – (a volunteer from the group) typically plays himself/herself Actor –	
Context: The broader context of time and place, background for the meeting, whether this is an initial or follow-up meeting. If it's a follow-up, include what happened previously. Is there a prior acquaintance between the characters?	
Actor's character: Autobiographical details and anything the actor needs to portray an authentic character' including: – Name – Age – Marital status – Socioeconomic status – Place of residence – Occupation / Source of income – Support networks	

¹ Designed by Adina David, <https://www.teamtalk.org.il/he/home>.

<p>Terminology (optional):</p> <p>Here you may include specific lines you would like the actor to say. If irrelevant, leave it to improvisation based on the scenario.</p>	
<p>If ... then ...</p> <p>How the actor should respond based on the trainee's behavior:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">– If the trainee uses poor communication, then the actor should resist or refuse to cooperate.– If the trainee communicates effectively and meets the character's needs, then the actor should reduce resistance and strive for cooperation.	
<p>Turning point:</p> <p>The actor is instructed to challenge or surprise the trainee by shouting, crying, storming out in anger, asking a tough or provocative question, threatening to commit suicide, etc.</p> <p>Operational Notes – Set design:</p> <p>Guidance on how to arrange the space for the simulation</p>	

Immersive Virtual Reality in Teaching Geography to Secondary School Students

Abstract

The use of immersive virtual reality (IVR) technologies in education has demonstrated potential benefits in increasing engagement, motivation, and knowledge retention. IVR can also be considered a form of simulation-based learning, especially when designed with interactive, gamified elements. However, its implementation in school settings remains limited due to high costs, organizational challenges, and the lack of individualized learning approaches. This study aims to explore the possibility of applying personalized IVR learning content in geography lessons, to highlight the difficulties encountered, and to propose solutions to the mentioned problems. A prototype IVR learning object (LO) of variable difficulty was developed for use in this study, which indicates that IVR may increase student motivation and is perceived as engaging by most of the surveyed students. The results suggest that students' abilities and learning preferences can vary significantly within the same grade – some become more motivated by challenging tasks while others may feel discouraged. This supports the potential benefits of individualizing learning content. For this purpose, we propose a model that would allow a teacher to automatically generate learning management system-compatible IVR LOs on a chosen topic with adjustable difficulty, depending on the user's level of knowledge. The proposed model aims to support the creation of tailored tasks that match students' individual needs while enabling educators to develop customized educational content without requiring programming expertise.

Keywords: Virtual reality, Learning object, Education, Adaptive learning.

1 Introduction

The rapid development of immersive virtual reality (IVR) technology over the past decade has significantly influenced changes in various fields, from entertainment and gaming to training in medicine and engineering (Freina & Ott, 2015). Naturally, the spread of IVR has also impacted education, allowing for new learning opportunities and promoting active learning experiences, such as conducting physical experiments or allowing students to actively interact with and manipulate virtual objects (Pellas et al., 2021). By simulating real-world environments, IVR encourages experimental learning, merging both theoretical understanding and practical application, hence why IVR has garnered attention as a transformative educational medium and a potentially useful aid in an educator's toolkit (Maroukas et al., 2023).

Although numerous studies conducted on IVR applications in education report improvements in students' learning outcomes (Kaluschke et al., 2023) by increasing their interest (Di Natale et al., 2020), motivation (Bower & Yong, 2020), and knowledge retention (Bae et al., 2020; Krokos et al., 2019), significant challenges remain. These applications often resemble simulation-based or game-like environments, but clear educational integration and personalization remain

key issues. Although many treat IVR as a promising learning tool, unfortunately the technology's maturity in education is questionable, and most of the currently proposed models are still in their experimental stages (Radianti et al., 2020). Furthermore, IVR remains costly for classroom use due to expensive equipment (Maroukkas et al., 2024) and space requirements. Managing multiple headsets simultaneously can be burdensome for teachers and institutions, limiting adoption despite the technology's potential. Therefore, so far IVR has been primarily used in the context of research, mostly in higher education, with university undergraduates making up 45 percent of all studies performed (Maroukkas et al., 2024).

Among the various fields employing virtual reality as an education medium, chemistry and engineering are the most frequent topics (Maroukkas et al., 2024), and IVR has been most often implemented in medical courses, including medicine, biology, surgery and nursing (Sümer & Vaněček, 2024). For a large spectrum of other domains, including geography, IVR is less frequently used, especially in comparison to other available technologies, such as laser scanning (Fagin et al., 2020).

The application of IVR in geography education primarily revolves around virtual field trips as well as navigation and wayfinding exercises (Huang & Hu, 2025), which allow for immersive learning and improve spatial reasoning without having to leave the classroom. Another common use involves virtual visualizations, used to visualize and explain complex geographic phenomena (Huang & Hu, 2025), such as tectonic plate movements or urban growth models. Notably, IVR can help students to retain geographical knowledge more efficiently while also developing various transferable skills that transcend the boundaries of the field, such as collaborative learning, communication, practical problem solving, and computer-assisted learning ability (Niu et al., 2023).

Despite the widely reported positive effects of IVR on engagement and learning experiences (Fagin et al., 2020), research indicates that IVR in education still encounters challenges that are yet to be tackled, such as high equipment costs, technical problems, and limited instructor training (Fagin et al., 2020), as well as the lack of individualized learning approaches using adaptive learning methodologies for in-class use (Maroukkas et al., 2024). Creating learning content tailored to individual students' needs while also taking advantage of the potential of IVR may improve learning outcomes. Moreover, when combined with adaptive techniques and gamified design, IVR not only provides effective educational experiences but also has the potential to offer "a tailored experience based on skills, learning gaps, personal preferences, cognitive characteristics, prior knowledge and other factors" (Maroukkas et al., 2024).

The objective of this study is to provide more individualized IVR learning content and to assess its usability for both educators and secondary school students. In addition, we propose a model for adaptive IVR content generation, aiming to address the mentioned shortcomings of current experimental implementations.

2 Methodology and Materials

This section outlines the process of transforming an interactive educational application into an IVR LO that is compatible with learning management systems (LMS) in order to evaluate its usability and effectiveness as a simulation-based and gamified educational tool.

2.1 Implementation

The prototype used for this experiment is an educational IVR application designed to familiarize the user with the map of Europe (Figure 1). The goal is to assemble a puzzle of the map of Europe from country-shaped puzzle pieces scattered throughout the virtual environment. Users manually pick up the pieces and insert them in their correct position, which encourages physical movement and promotes kinesthetic learning through physical activity (Jaruševičius et al., 2024).

Figure 1. Screenshots of the IVR LO “Europe VR” used during the study.

The experiment was conducted using several different versions of the IVR LO – initially, only one version containing a ‘full’ map of Europe consisting of 42 countries was used. However, after initial testing it was concluded that it may potentially be too difficult and time-sensitive for secondary school students to complete, so alternative versions were created. These simpler versions each contained approximately 14 countries, grouped by European regions (e.g. North and West, Central and South, East and Southeast), allowing for greater flexibility in adjusting task difficulty.

The IVR application itself was developed in Godot 3.5. It tracks the number of correctly placed puzzle pieces, the number of mistakes made, and the time taken to complete the task. These game-like features aim to encourage engagement through interaction and challenge, in alignment with principles of gamified learning design. The environment contains helpful items, such as the scanner, which aids the user in determining what country is assigned to a puzzle piece or a banner displaying the country’s flag, capital city, or other desired additional information.

If a puzzle piece is placed in the wrong location on the map, it drops to the floor, which is counted as a mistake.

The application was converted into an LO using the SCORM standard, which allows for integration in various SCORM-compatible LMS such as Moodle. To create a SCORM package file, the application is exported in HTML5 format, and the contents are archived into a zip package together with an xml library file, JavaScript function wrappers, and xsd manifest files.

The IVR application runs on HTML5. Once uploaded to an LMS, it can be launched directly from the browser via WebXR, assuming the user has compatible IVR equipment. The user is not required to download or install anything, which makes the use of the LO more accessible and convenient, while also allowing for direct communication with the LMS itself, which automatically registers the results of the game in the LMS, as if it were a test. The results are recorded in the LMS after the puzzle is completed, or once the user tries to exit.

Since LOs are reusable, this activity may be attempted multiple times. Each attempt can be visible in the Reports tab, listing the start and end times of each attempt for each user, their score, as well as more detailed information if requested.

2.2 Experiment setup

Once permission had been obtained, the study was conducted at Santara secondary school in Vilnius in a geography class with supervision from the teaching staff. The participants were all student volunteers from grades 8 and 9 with no prior experience in virtual reality environments. Grades 8 and 9 were chosen specifically because the grade 8 curriculum includes European countries in the study plan (Educational Portal e. mokykla.lt., 2025).

The experiment was performed as follows. The participants were all introduced to the experiment and the purpose of the study. Each volunteer was then briefed on the controls of the VR devices provided, informed about the task they were requested to complete within the virtual environment, and that they would also be asked to fill out a questionnaire about their experience. They were also told that they would be able to opt out of the study at any time. Once informed consent to participate was received, the experiment began.

A total of 32 students participated in the study. The participants were tasked to complete their section of the map of Europe using the country puzzle pieces provided. Each participant was assigned a different version of the LO. The IVR hardware used for the experiment comprised several sets of Meta Quest 2 HMDs (head-mounted displays) along with their respective controllers, running on the default Horizon OS v65. The applications were all hosted on the University Moodle (v4.1) environment, accessed through the Meta Quest Browser.

The supervising geography teacher would assign volunteer students different versions of the IVR application to complete and set a time limit for each attempt. Once the students were finished or time ran out, they would be asked to move on to filling out the questionnaire; meanwhile, the virtual environment would be reset, results of the attempt recorded, and the headset readied for the next volunteer. Following this, a short discussion with the geography teacher served as an informal debriefing session during which students reflected on the activity and clarified any questions. This approach aligns with basic debriefing practices to consolidate learning and gather experiential feedback (Crookall, 2023).

2.3 Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis of the questionnaire responses was performed using IBM's SPSS Statistics software, v29.0. Since the sample size is small ($n = 32$), the exact test was used for comparison, and nonparametric correlation analysis was used to assess relationships. The Fisher–Freeman–Halton Exact Test was used to compare categorical variables between groups. The relationship between ordinal variables was assessed by calculating Spearman's correlation coefficient. Statistical significance level was set at $\alpha = 0.05$.

3 Results

The results in this section can be classified into two categories. The category presented first concerns students' performance in the experiment, such as time elapsed and number of correct answers. The second category concerns the participant survey results. This article focuses only on responses related to students' experience with virtual reality.

In Tables 1–3, the columns have been titled using the following abbreviations: Number of countries (NoC), minimum number of recognized countries (Min NoRC), maximum number of recognized countries (Max NoRC), average number of recognized countries (Avg NoRC), average time spent (Avg T), and percentage of correct choice (% of CCh).

At the beginning of the experiment, students were asked to construct the map of the whole of Europe, consisting of all 42 countries. Table 1 shows that both grade 8 and grade 9 students achieved relatively low scores, even when no time limit was imposed. Although the differences between the two classes were not great, grade 8 students achieved slightly better results. Students of grade 9 took 13.5 minutes on average, while students of grade 8 took 18 minutes on average. The minimum number of correctly chosen states was 14 and the maximum number was 42. All students in grade 9 made at least one mistake, while 13 percent of grade 8 students completed the task without any errors.

Table 1. Grade 8 and 9 results, full map of Europe (42 countries).

Region	NoC	Grade	Time limit	Min NoRC	Max NoRC	Avg NoRC	Avg T	% of CCh
Europe	42	9	No limit	14	37	25.5	13.5	0%
Europe	42	8	No limit	28	42	35.5	18	13%

Table 2 shows the results for the tasks divided by region. The results have improved, although there was a time limit (6 minutes for grade 8 and 5 minutes for grade 9 students). For North and Western Europe, no students from grade 9 managed to place correctly all 14 countries, while 83 percent of students from grade 8 succeeded in this task. For Southern and Central Europe, 33 percent of grade 8 students and 44 percent of grade 9 students successfully completed the puzzle with all countries correctly placed.

Table 2. Grade 8 and 9 results for regions of Europe.

Region	NoC	Grade	Time limit.	Min NoRC	Max NoRC	Avg NoRC	Avg T	% of CCh
North and West Europe	14	9	5 min.	8	13	11.3	5	0%
North and West Europe	14	8	6 min.	13	14	13.8	5.5	83%
South and Central Europe	14	9	5 min.	5	14	11.1	4.7	44%
South and Central Europe	14	8	6 min.	11	14	12.1	6	33%

Table 3 shows the results of the best-ranked students (3 from grade 8 and 3 from grade 9) who were asked to fill in all 42 states, but with a time limit (12 minutes for grade 8 and 20 minutes for grade 9). Only one student from each class succeeded in filling in all 42 states. On average, each student from grade 8 filled 34.5 states, and each student from grade 9 filled 33.6 states. Only one of the students used the full time limit.

Table 3. Results of best-ranked students, regions of Europe.

Region	NoC	Grade	Time limit	Min NoRC	Max NoRC	Avg NoRC	Avg T
Europe	42	9	12	17	42	33.6	7.8
Europe	42	8	20	27	42	34.5	19.5

After completing the geography-related tasks, the participants were asked to fill out a questionnaire. Figures 2–5 contain the aggregate results of said questionnaire.

Figure 2. Views about lessons with IVR.

Figure 2 shows that majority of the students liked the lesson with IVR, and this proportion stayed mostly the same for both classes (Fisher–Freeman–Halton Exact Test = 0.283, $df = 2$, $p = 1.000$).

Figure 3. Views concerning immersiveness of IVR.

Figure 3 shows that majority of the students considered the IVR-based tool to be immersive. Furthermore, the distribution of views on this question was mostly the same in both grades (Fisher–Freeman–Halton Exact Test = 0.274, $df = 2$, $p = 1.000$).

Figure 4. Views about wanting to use IVR.

Figure 4 shows that schoolchildren in grade 8 were more enthusiastic about the use of an IVR-based tool (Fisher–Freeman–Halton Exact Test = 6.866, $df = 3$, $p = 0.032$).

Because students in grades 8 and 9 showed similar levels of liking IVR-based tools but differed in their desire to use them in the future, the relationship between these two variables was analyzed separately for each grade. In grade 8 (Figure 5 left), a moderate and statistically significant positive correlation was found between liking IVR-based tools and wanting to use them in class (Spearman's $r = 0.653$, $p = 0.008$). In other words, the more students liked the tools, the more they wanted to use them. However, in grade 9 (Figure 5 right), this relationship was weaker and not statistically significant (Spearman's $r = 0.299$, $p = 0.243$).

Figure 5. Relationship between liking IVR-based tools and wanting to use them in grades 8 and 9.

4 Proposal

The proposed model (Figure 6) outlines a system for generating individualized IVR LOs with adjustable difficulty. While the current paper focuses on design and rationale, a working prototype is planned for future development and evaluation.

Figure 6. Conceptual schema of the proposed IVR learning object generation model.

The system begins with a user-facing website interface, where educators input metadata for the learning object – such as course title, topic, and task description – and select options including difficulty level, target environment, task type, and whether to enable hints. Educators may also upload custom 3D models representing the educational content.

These uploaded models are then processed by an AI-based module which segments the object according to the selected difficulty. A language model assigns metadata to each segment and generates corresponding task descriptions. This supports the creation of varied, simulation-based learning scenarios that can be tailored to different learner profiles.

A VR learning object is then assembled by integrating the segmented models and metadata into a predefined game-based VR template. This package is exported in HTML5 format and wrapped into a SCORM-compliant package, allowing seamless integration with LMS platforms such as Moodle.

By automating the generation of adaptive, gamified IVR content, this framework aims to enable teachers to create engaging learning experiences without requiring programming expertise. Un-

like many existing approaches, this system allows for scalable content creation based on any user-uploaded 3D model, supporting diverse curriculum areas beyond geography.

While the current model remains in the design phase, the implementation is planned to use the Godot 4 engine for runtime generation of scenes and SCORM packaging via a Python-based backend. Metadata input and 3D segmentation logic will be handled server-side using Node.js and Python scripts, with LLM-based prompt processing integrated via an API. A prototype will be made available as an open educational resource (OER) in a future publication via GitHub.

5 Discussion and Conclusion

The results of the experiment show that on average the grade 8 students performed slightly better than the grade 9 students. This may be because the eighth-grade curriculum has a stronger focus on European countries, making the material easier to recall for those students, whereas ninth-grade students may have had more difficulty retrieving that information. However, this may also indicate that while current learning tools and materials may be effective in the short-term, the effects of retaining information are not very long lasting. This highlights the need for future research evaluating and comparing the long-term retention outcomes of traditional teaching methods versus the proposed immersive VR-based approaches.

Creating different versions of the IVR LO with varying difficulties allowed more students to briefly interact with the virtual reality environment and complete the task successfully. This provided a quick refresher on the topic without overburdening students, while also demonstrating how simulation-based and gamified tasks can be adapted to different ability levels. The results show that students have a much higher success rate and are more likely to complete the assignment if tasks are split into manageable chunks.

Based on the results of the questionnaire, the majority of the students enjoyed experiencing the lesson content in IVR and agreed that the technology was immersive. The distribution of views stayed consistent across both grades.

However, Figure 4 shows a divergence of opinions – students from grade 9 were noticeably less enthusiastic about using IVR technology in the future. This may be related to their performance levels or lower familiarity with the content. Since motivation is often linked to academic achievement (Mahdavi et al., 2023), this suggests that adapting content difficulty through individualized, gamified tasks could enhance engagement. Similar effects were observed in prior adaptive learning studies, where challenge adjustment significantly influenced learner motivation and persistence (Maroukias et al., 2024).

Even though the applications themselves did not have a way to dynamically adjust the difficulty based on individual skill, performing the study with different versions available allowed the supervising geography teacher to more flexibly assign students tasks based on their knowledge. This explains why some students completed the ‘full’ 42-piece map faster and with fewer mistakes than other students who attempted the simpler versions. By having access to similar tasks of varying difficulty, an educator can personalize the educational content by giving more difficult tasks to more knowledgeable students, further allowing for individualized learning approaches. Presenting the learning material in a gamified format – without assigning grades

based on performance – can help students to feel more engaged in the challenge instead of being discouraged, especially when tasks are matched to their level of ability.

However, the challenges of integrating IVR in schools remain – even standalone ‘inside-out’ HMDs which do not require a connection to a computer to function still need an ample amount of physical space for learners to move around in and act freely without fear of injuring themselves or damaging the equipment, which is difficult to implement in a classroom setting. One possible solution is to develop IVR applications that allow seated interaction, though this would reduce the kinesthetic benefits that IVR is uniquely suited to provide (Jaruševičius et al., 2024; Zielasko & Riecke, 2021).

Organizing the experiment with IVR technology proved logistically challenging. Even with three active headsets and three supervisors, there was little downtime: inexperienced volunteers needed guiding, devices needed calibrating, and sessions had to be reset. This highlights not only technical challenges, but also organizational ones, which must be addressed to allow broader adoption, that are consistent with concerns noted in the literature (Fagin et al., 2020). Between assigning tasks, explaining the controls, noting down the results, solving calibration issues, etc. there was a constant stream of things to do to keep the experiment running as smoothly as possible. Conducting a class in virtual reality with no prior training would most likely be too challenging for most educators. To enable sustainable classroom adoption, future efforts should also explore curriculum alignment strategies and school-level policy recommendations, such as centralized hardware sharing models, teacher training modules, and support for including IVR-based LOs in national digital textbook repositories.

In addition to the costs of the gear, another issue is battery life. The Meta Quest 2 headsets only supported around 4 hours of non-stop use before their batteries were drained and needed recharging. As a result, a full charge lasts only about half a school day, complicating lesson planning and requiring teachers to work around charging cycles when integrating IVR into their instruction.

One limitation of the present study is the absence of a control group using traditional teaching methods, which prevents direct measurement of learning improvement. Future studies should aim to include comparative conditions to validate IVR’s added value empirically. Additionally, since the findings suggest that knowledge retention may decrease over time, it would be valuable to assess how well information or competencies are maintained after a longer period following the IVR intervention.

The study results show the potential of IVR as a learning tool and indicate that individualization of learning materials in IVR environments enhances student motivation, engagement, and performance. However, the focus should not be limited to improving learning material or software solutions. Other challenges such as limited device battery life, physical space requirements, and high organizational demands should be also addressed if the aim is to expand practical IVR application in school settings. Future research should focus on optimizing IVR for classroom use by improving device sustainability and creating more accessible applications.

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Bettina Schwenger

Fostering Digital Literacies with Elements of Game-Based Learning

Abstract

This paper reports on the use of game-based elements for active teaching and learning with a low-key digital infrastructure. One of the research aims was to find out how to harness the qualities of online learning in an institutional learning management system (LMS) for a design that encourages the development of digital information literacy. How to use game-based elements for active teaching and learning was a vital consideration for the study, which was set up to support students tasked with an ePortfolio assessment. This article shares the design process while highlighting game-based elements and practices that have the potential to enhance learning in an environment with little resources for learning design.

Keywords: Digital literacies, Active learning, Game-based elements.

1 Introduction

Based on the experience of two teachers in the Bachelor of Teaching (Early Childhood Education; ECE) program, this paper explores how they introduced more active online learning with game-based elements into their teaching practices in a first-year course. Their focus was on achieving this in an environment with restricted technology and design expertise, having this as an essential consideration. The low-tech design is based on pedagogical principles, as Chen (2025) recommends, and focuses on fostering digital information literacy (DIL).

This research forms part of a larger study which took place in two iterations of an ECE course at a tertiary institution in Aotearoa New Zealand. The main research question was: How can teachers design blended learning for first-year undergraduate students to develop DIL? An additional aim was to examine how elements of game-based practices could support active learning in the online space.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Design for learning

Through its active involvement of participants, game-based learning is an effective way to teach adults, may it be skills or knowledge (Lubbe et al., 2024). Game-based learning aligns with adult learning principles, as it encourages participation and enables the development of skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and communication while fostering motivation (Ritvanen, 2021). Active learning and immediate feedback are both part of game-based learning (Pho & Dinscore, 2015) and vital adult learning concepts.

Teachers can be unsure how to achieve active learning, though, particularly in online environments, in ways that reflect the course outcomes and the type of learning required for students' study success. In a systematic literature review of 640 sources, Boelens et al. (2017) identified potential course issues, such as lack of interaction and opportunities for students' self-assessment to identify and understand their personal learning progress. Challenges include choosing the appropriate technology and designing effective learning to achieve a particular outcome (Ako Aotearoa & Synapsys, 2018). For any learning design, teachers should consider the students, their resources, the type of learning required, and the subject that is learned (Bates, 2019; Rapanta et al., 2020), with a focus on what students are doing to learn (Biggs & Tang, 2011).

How can online tools support a focus on students' activities? They can enhance the learning process by providing a multi-modal approach to education. Furthermore, active learning can be supported through technical qualities that allow elements of game-based learning such as automated responses for formative feedback (Rapanta et al., 2020). An online environment might offer opportunities to enhance learning outcomes for students from different backgrounds through individualized options. Some situations in ECE work can require students to step through several decisions; therefore, students can benefit from practicing scenario-type activities, for example. Inquiry questions integrated into LMS resources can enable valuable self-assessment and reflection for students.

2.2 Indigenous context in educational design

In Aotearoa New Zealand, educators engaged in curriculum and learning design need to incorporate Indigenous ways of knowing and consider appropriate support for Indigenous learners due to their commitment to Te Tiriti o Waitangi/the Treaty of Waitangi, the foundational document (Barnes, 2013). The Māori dimension of the ECE program is based on values embodied in Te Tiriti o Waitangi/the Treaty of Waitangi and Te Whāriki, the Aotearoa early childhood curriculum (Ministry of Education, 2017).

More work is still required to integrate culturally inclusive practices into higher education and to promote Māori student equity (Rātima et al., 2022; Green et al., 2023). Finding ways of successfully navigating these subtleties in the design of learning environments is crucial for educators in Aotearoa New Zealand and is therefore part of the design considerations. Our project was designed to support the partnership and such practices at the institution where this research took place. This context is critical for understanding the pedagogical nuances of the present study.

2.3 Digital information literacy

Since Gilster's (Gilster, 1997) original definition of digital literacy, the scope of the term has expanded and more nuanced understandings of various digital literacies have emerged. These related literacies comprise abilities for effectively finding, evaluating, and using information, and are referred to as information literacies (American Library Association, 2012). DIL is integral for developing study-specific knowledge and for learning (Maybee et al., 2018). This study focuses on students' DIL because of its links to "high-level intellectual operations such as critical thinking, problem-solving, question framing and independent learning" (Secker & Coonan, 2013, p. xxi). Considering the rise of artificial intelligence and the need to evaluate fake information, these skills continue to be essential.

As part of first-year DIL practices (Gosling & Nix, 2011), learners are required to:

- be aware of key information resources,
- identify a need for information,
- plan and search for information from appropriate sources, and
- critically evaluate and organize information.

Students are likely to see expectations shifting in higher education, including their digital literacy skills (Schwenger, 2019). One indicative example in the context of ECE, as reported by the ECE teachers, is that students underestimated the literacy demands of the degree and of the practical work in placements.

3 Methodology

3.1 Background

Work in ECE requires educators to engage with DIL in multiple ways, for example by developing child literacies and capturing children's development using ePortfolios. In line with the institutional principles for learning and teaching, the program aims to enable authentic experiences through applied learning. The ECE Bachelor of Teaching program attracts a mix of students, including Māori (the Indigenous people of Aotearoa New Zealand), Pacific Islanders, and Pākeha (New Zealanders of European descent/non-Māori) as the largest ethnic groups. The ages range from 17 to 40 years, with students often being first-in-family to participate in formal tertiary education.

3.2 Methods

The methodological approach taken aligns with the process of educational design research that addresses real-life issues (Plomp, 2013). A three-phase model based on Plomp (2013) included preliminary research, development, and evaluation (Figure 1). Identifying as a supporter of change for Māori, the researcher applied kaupapa Māori researcher guidelines (Cram, 2001) to achieve a culturally appropriate study context for Māori and non-Māori participants. Examples of practices included treating participants respectfully, listening, and sharing knowledge.

The study received ethical approval, and the students had a channel to contact the researcher using an opt-in approach. Thirteen students and two teachers participated in the study. Students shared their thoughts through initial and final questionnaires and focus groups, while teachers did so through an initial questionnaire, reflections, emails, and interviews. Interviews and focus groups were digitally recorded and transcribed.

The findings were generated using an inductive approach, examining the experiences of the research participants and related studies in the literature (Bryman, 2021). Participants' voices provided evidence of identified themes and were indicators of the overall results. The qualitative research design helped to create rich, in-depth descriptions in this small-scale study.

In the first study phase, an extensive literature review was undertaken. To gather information about educators' and students' understanding and challenges, we used multiple data sources

(questionnaires, focus groups, interviews, library, and course websites, assessments, and other course documents). We identified the existing course design and resources. Based on these findings, the first two resources were conceptualized and developed as prototypes. A second design iteration then took place (second phase), with formative feedback. In the third phase, the design was fine-tuned and evaluated. Throughout all phases, the feedback from Māori colleagues was essential. Consulting, drafting, responding to feedback, and ongoing collaboration were key.

Figure 1. The three research phases in this study.

3.3 Development process

Central to the approach in each of the three phases were ongoing discussions with the teachers. While these conversations covered pedagogical practices for the entire course, the research proper focused on design to foster DIL with game-based elements online in support of the ePortfolio assessment.

Taking into consideration existing resources, the design intentions were defined in order to create resources to provide practice, reflection, and feedback opportunities through online mechanisms. Some students struggle to manage the growing flexibility and independence of studying online, so it was important that these resources helped to scaffold learning. By using screenshots, step-by-step instructions, and structured reflective elements to support self-assessment, the project aimed to offer comprehensive support online and face-to-face in this first-year course.

In the first phase, we connected DIL development to assessment (Gosling & Nix, 2011) by identifying areas where students struggled with the ePortfolio. Findings from the students' questionnaires and focus groups indicated their difficulties with evaluating, analyzing, and synthesizing to create new information. Student feedback was used to create and subsequently fine-

tune the resources. Findings about student needs and the resources were shared with the ECE team to support further development in other courses.

Based on the DIL actions required for first-year study (Gosling & Nix, 2011), the researcher with feedback from the team then created as a first resource the underpinning process called “How do I use information to develop an ePortfolio?” Using this process as foundation, four customized resources were tailored to the course demands and were available to students on the course webpage.

The resources offered students opportunities to apply, practice, and reflect upon using DIL in situations where they are required to create new information. These resources included:

1. The visualized six-step process, titled “How do I use information to develop an ePortfolio?” (Figure 2). Students familiarize themselves with the process using integrated questions for reflection (Figure 3) to reflect on their work in their writing for the ePortfolio.
2. Scenario (Figure 4): Students apply the six-step process and receive automated feedback on decisions they made related to ECE situations. They reflect on DIL practices in an ECE situation to create an entry.
3. A quiz with formative feedback helps to practice DIL for the ePortfolio.
4. The six-step process with pop-up questions for reflection.

Figure 2. Resource 1: The Process “How do I use information to develop an ePortfolio?” (based on Gosling & Nix, 2011).

Figure 3. Reflection Questions for Students to Consider for Step 5 (“I analyze information”) in the “How do I use information to develop an ePortfolio?” Process.

How do I interpret and analyse the information I have found?

- How does the information I have found inform the situation in my reflection?
- Do I need to find other information?
- Do I need to include additional information from any of my sources?
- Have I used/synthesised the main ideas that I have identified in the literature to show my own understanding?

Figure 4. Resource Two: Step 1/6 from the Scenario “Laura’s Situation”.

Laura's situation

Laura works with a group of four year olds. The children are exploring different colour combinations and textures when two of them start to argue about sharing the used equipment.

Laura tries to help the children sort out the situation but the children do not listen and continue to get upset.

She reflects on what happened and decides to use this situation for a reflection in her ePortfolio.

What information does Laura need for her reflection?

4 Discussion

4.1 Creating active learning opportunities with game-based elements

The design process for the four resources aimed to integrate various perspectives on student engagement, e.g. how people learn (Beetham, 2013), and to identify learners’ preferences and resources. The design focuses on the skills and knowledge that students require to complete their assessment successfully, in particular to construct new information and meaning (Mayes & de Freitas, 2013). The design is informed by the ideas of Biggs & Tang (2011) on how students can show that they have achieved the course learning outcomes. The findings of the research confirm that course design can benefit from an approach that is centered on “what the student is actually doing, placing learning [...] at the heart of the process” (Ministry of Education, 2017, p. 18) to achieve a design that includes active learning (Biggs & Tang, 2011).

The resources used online qualities to offer active learning for developing DIL. They were designed to provide initial advice with reflective questions to consider, to apply in a situation, and

to correct through automated feedback. The Moodle Quiz and Lesson resources offered unlimited practice opportunities and automated feedback for students to experience timely formative “feedback during learning” as “the most powerful enhancement to learning” (Biggs & Tang, 2011, p. 97). Through online qualities, such feedback was gathered without adding to teachers’ marking time, which can be a strong barrier to providing formative feedback. The resources utilized automated feedback and unlimited practice opportunities to enable effective learning and teaching strategies online, as recommended for Māori learners in the classroom (Rātima et al., 2022; Curtis et al., 2011). The resources were designed to complement the strategies reported by the teachers. The teachers used interactions in emails and timely feedback as “low-tech” options to support students in their learning (Garner & Rouse, 2016).

All learning resources were based on previously identified learning challenges. They were designed to support learning with questions for reflection and prompts. These technical affordances can be used to scaffold self-assessment and active learning, and to encourage students to practice and learn independently. Therefore, they afford strategies that have been identified to support the learning of Māori and non-Māori students (Curtis et al., 2011; Green et al., 2023).

Although the resources were not as fully utilized by students and staff as planned, students and teachers confirmed that the online resources assisted with preparing assessment tasks. This indicates that the resources offered some scaffolding to develop students’ independence, as suggested by Curtis et al. (2011), and that automated feedback can support this.

Through the resource features, the study identifies examples of how online qualities of LMS tools can enable game-based learning elements and foster the development of practices relevant for the assessment in this course and others in ECE studies. The study results demonstrate one way of utilizing certain online mechanisms such as automated feedback to develop DIL and support independent learning. The research confirms, though, that online qualities can provide new learning opportunities to support assessment and DIL development in a first-year undergraduate course. Prior to the study, the online qualities of the Moodle course site were underused, as it was a static course page and there was potential to design for active learning online.

4.2 Summary of feedback

Although this article does not report the evaluation of the study, the following section outlines some of the formative and summative feedback received from students and teachers. Teachers appreciated the explicitness of the resources and felt that connecting development with the assessment supported students’ assessment success. The resource design addressed the identified needs, according to both teachers. Both reconfirmed during the research that they appreciated the online qualities of the resources on an otherwise mostly static course site. They were unsure though if one quality had been more useful than others to increase flexibility for students. More research is needed, therefore, to identify to degree to which particular qualities such as automated feedback are useful for Māori and non-Māori students.

The teachers reported anecdotal feedback from six students in the first semester who found the tools helpful in preparing their ePortfolio. Feedback given on ePortfolio assessments to

students at the end of semester 1 reflected a positive development in the use of literature in the ePortfolios. Teacher A reported that the literature in the assignments in semester 1 was overall of better quality. Feedback from seven students in semester 2 indicated that the resources had been useful for their independent study, and for developing their ePortfolio. The teachers explicitly confirmed several times how much they valued the integrated online resources for their teaching and for students' individual practice. Both teachers reported that DIL was more explicitly discussed in the classroom, including during the introduction to the online resources, and it might have made students more aware of the importance of finding reliable information.

5 Conclusion

The findings of the current study show that a course design with integrated DIL development and game-based elements can support the current trend in Aotearoa New Zealand's tertiary and higher education towards active learning approaches. These require students to know how to find information, develop digital skills, and use information critically, ethically, and creatively. The study findings indicate that integrated DIL and elements of game-based learning can offer a way to strengthen students' content learning through thinking about practices, interaction, and reflection.

Māori and non-Māori students can benefit from additional learning opportunities in a design with integrated, contextualized DIL development that is aligned with assessment demands and takes advantage of technical online qualities. However, the study confirms that further research in designing and facilitating active learning online with more participants is needed, as recommended by Ako Aotearoa and Synapsys (2018) and Boelens et al. (2017), to appropriately scaffold independent learning and integrate further feedback options.

The key priority of the design process is to identify what activities need to be created so that students can practice, experience, and show what they have learned, using online qualities that allow game-based elements. Increased expertise is needed in designing and facilitating face-to-face and online learning with a focus on students' activities that support learning outcomes. In addition, staff appreciate guidance when reviewing existing courses to explore how they can better integrate active learning (Schwenger, 2019). In short, staff expertise impacts on how learning is designed and applied in courses. Ongoing institutional technical and pedagogical support is required but should be complemented by multiple ways of engaging teachers – that allow teaching staff to experiment and experience, through social interactions, conversations, and by playing and reflecting.

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Disclosure of Interests

The author has no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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Luke Alexander West

Farm Your Way to Fluency: Designing and Assessing a Digital Game for Reinforcing Linguistic Perceptual Skills

Abstract

For language learners, differences between their native language(s) and the target language often lead to significant perceptual challenges. These often include linguistic skills that are foundational but remain underdeveloped even for advanced learners. For speakers of non-tonal languages (e.g. English) who are learning a tonal language (e.g. Chinese), tone is one such challenge: Pitch movement indicating word meaning is essential for speaking, but acquisition requires immense input – even advanced learners struggle to distinguish tones. The problem-solving focus, adaptivity, and media embedding capability of digital games and simulations make them ideal for reinforcing these perceptual skills through targeted, persistent exposure. In this case study, I present the design and assessment of one such game. Design involves collaboration with native speakers to select language content spanning the range of the target perceptual skill, while selecting a suitable game genre and problem-solving context. I describe the resulting farming simulation game FarmWing and present an assessment of 73 adults' gameplay, revealing that more problem-solving using vocabulary to solve in-game problems – and not simply more exposure to vocabulary – was associated with more vocabulary learning. Based on the game design, development, and assessment I suggest six best practices for designing and assessing game or simulation interventions targeting specific perceptual skills in linguistically and culturally relevant problem-solving contexts.

Keywords: Game-based learning, Language learning, Computer-assisted language learning, Chinese as a second language.

1 Introduction

For many language learners, fundamental linguistic differences between their native languages and the target language lead to significant perceptual hurdles. These include linguistic skills that are foundational but remain underdeveloped even for advanced learners. The adaptive and problem-solving nature of digital games makes them ideal for targeting these linguistic skills in future-oriented language learning. In this paper, I present the design of a learning game followed by a preliminary learning effectiveness analysis. I aim to demonstrate the application of a Serious Games design model in the field of language learning, specifically for reinforcing foundational perceptual skills.

For speakers of non-tonal languages (e.g. Hindi, German, English) who are learning a tonal language (e.g. Mandarin Chinese), tone is one such challenge: Pitch movement indicating word meaning is essential for speaking Mandarin, but successful acquisition requires immense input. Class intervention research has shown that targeted tone training can enhance learners' tone

perception (Hao & Liu, 2019), yet even advanced learners struggle to distinguish tones (Han & Tsukada, 2020; Ling & Grüter, 2020; Pelzl et al., 2019; Pelzl et al., 2021). This suggests that more exposure to targeted language content is needed to support learners’ perceptual growth, particularly in areas such as tone learning.

2 Game Design

2.1 Identifying the foundational perceptual skill: Tone

The tonal system of standard Mandarin includes four full lexical tones (1: high flat, 2: rising, 3: dipping, 4: falling) and one neutral tone (0: short low), each of which is associated with a specific syllable. For simplicity, I use the standard Pinyin writing system in this document to portray Mandarin pronunciation and tone. While the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA, 1999), uses both tone symbols and diacritics over vowels (e.g. má) to represent tone, in this study I use Pinyin tone diacritics to mark tone in a specific Mandarin word, and I refer to the tone number and simple description of the tone when referring to the tone category. Table 1 presents the four main Mandarin tones, based on Yip’s (1980) phonological analysis including register (upper: high pitch; lower: low pitch, creaky phonation) and tone target (L: low, H: high).

Table 1. The Four* Tones of Mandarin. Phonological Analysis Based On Yip (1980).

Tone number	Simple description	Phonological target	Pinyin example
T1	High	Upper H	ma ^ˉ
T2	Rising	Upper LH	má
T3	Dipping	Lower L	ma ^ˇ
T4	Falling	Upper HL	mà

For children acquiring Mandarin as their L1, lexical tone categories emerge by age two (Li & Thompson, 1977) and are acquired by age three, though children will not yet sound adultlike (Xu Rattanasone et al., 2018) – some confusion between certain tones (e.g. T2 and T3) is normal.

2.2 Choosing the game genre and mechanics

Selecting the game genre requires consideration of both game mechanics and learning mechanics. Game mechanics comprise the rules of a game along with the actions that these rules allow the player to perform (Järvinen, 2008; Sicart, 2008) – these mechanics along with the game narrative (game characters, story, world) are the fundamental elements of gameplay (Ke, 2016). Following Arnab et al.’s framework for Serious Game design (2015), the first and essential step for designers is to create a mapping between game mechanics and the learning mechanics, which include the learning strategies based on didactic and learning theory principles. Designing the present game, I first based the learning mechanics on Morton & Jack’s interaction hypothesis (2005): I thus looked for a genre where the game mechanics would let language learners engage in (1) negotiated interaction with an agent, while also receiving (2) immediate, relevant feedback to their input. Role-playing games (RPG) and simulation games both regularly

put players in situations where they must interact with agents in the game, and both typically include narrative elements that situate and support these interactions. Table 2 below shows a mapping of common game mechanics found in these genres with the learning strategies of the interaction hypothesis (Morton & Jack, 2005) mentioned above.

Table 2. Mapping Between Selected Game and Learning Mechanics.

Game mechanic	Learning mechanic
Interaction with Non-Player Character (NPC)	Negotiated interaction with an agent
Shop/trade system	Negotiated interaction with an agent
Verbal response from NPC	Immediate, relevant feedback to input
Achievement tracking	Immediate, relevant feedback to input
Visual feedback of resource management	Immediate, relevant feedback to input

2.3 Choosing a game context and language content: Farming

Next, I simultaneously looked for a gameplay context to foster meaningful interaction for language learning, while looking for language content where the target skill is used (e.g. words which exemplify different tones and can occur together in a coherent context). First, the game context should foster activities with a broad vocabulary range and persistent interaction with certain game items to achieve short and long-term goals, so that players regularly interact with vocabulary that exposes them to the target perceptual linguistic skills. Farming simulation RPGs such as *Harvest Moon* or *Stardew Valley* allow for regular player interaction with certain items (e.g. crops) as players must purchase, plant, water, harvest, and then sell crops, focusing on a certain subset of crops for around 30 in-game days before the next season comes. This gameplay cycle motivates regular interaction with certain game items, while the rich achievement systems of these games also incentivize players to buy new crops when they are available. To foster more effective language interaction (Morton & Jack, 2005), I switched the role of the player from farmer to farming instructor: (1) The player communicates with the farmer (the agent) through typed language commands, and receives (2) immediate feedback through the farmers' reformulations and the immediate in-game consequences. Second, parallel to the choice of game context was the consideration of which vocabulary would represent the full range of the target foundational perceptual skill. Items that one might purchase in a store, find as buried treasure, or synthesize in a lab can be diverse, but are more limited in what actions the player would perform. Crops that one could grow on a farm include a wide range of possible vocabulary (e.g. vegetables, fruits, grains, flowers), and each necessitate regular interaction by the player. Because of the range of possible vocabulary and elements associated with the game genre, I chose a command-based farming sim as my target game to design.

2.4 Refining game content with native speakers

While much of the in-game dialogue is in English (e.g. interactions with the non-player characters (NPCs) providing support to the player), including explanation of the plot, all nouns and verbs used in language commands require careful selection to ensure high-quality experimental

materials. As such, I collaborated with five native speakers of Mandarin as language consultants in the selection and finalization processes of lexical item materials to be used in the game-based learning environment (and word recall portion of the post-test). Language consultants were each graduate students studying in the US at the time of consultation, and were selected based on their having native fluency in Mandarin as well as their each representing a unique province of mainland China – this was to ensure that region-specific words less relevant for learners would be avoided. Each target language command the player can produce to enact game progression is of the same structure (V1-N1-V2-N2), and selection of the Mandarin words possible for each component was confirmed with the language consultants (e.g. “go [to the] orchard [and] plant apples” was translated to “qù guǒyuán zhòng píngguǒ”). Mandarin words used for the noun 2 (N2) component in language commands (i.e., the crop upon which the farmer enacts a game action) were selected such that exactly two lexical items were included in the game for each of the twenty 2-syllable tone combinations in Mandarin (4 first-syllable options x 5 second-syllables options = 20 unique combinations x 2 words per combination = 40 unique lexical items).

First, I individually carried out a round of word selection of possible 2-syllable Mandarin words from several sources, prioritizing (1) relevance to the L2 problem-solving context (i.e. farming), and (2) alignment with game content in commercial games of a similar farming simulation genre. Sources used to select the initial list of language game content (e.g. plants, tools, locations, player actions) include the Standard Chinese translation of the commercial farming game *Stardew Valley* (Xīng Lù Guǒ Wù Yú) (ConcernedApe, 2016), in addition to direct consultation with native speakers and the following three online resources: the HSK vocabulary list (level 5), Google Translate, LTL-Beihai.com (fruits: LTL Mandarin School, 2021a; vegetables: LTL Mandarin School, 2021b), and YieldGap.org/China. This initial selection stage yielded a total of 102 farm-related 2-syllable Mandarin words.

Next, in order to narrow down possible word options further, I organized all words by tone combination type, and for any combinations with more than eight word options I independently narrowed the selection down to eight options based on utility for early learners of Mandarin (i.e. prioritizing words which occur on all levels of the HSK (Hanyu Shuiping Kaoshi – “Standardized Test of Mandarin”) over those that do not, and prioritizing lower HSK-level words over higher ones). I consulted the freely available HSK vocabulary to determine the utility of each item. This selection stage yielded a list of 91 vocabulary items.

Lastly, to narrow the 2-syllable words down to a finalized list of 40 (2 per tone combination), I presented each of the five language consultants with the list of items to elicit a rating of 1–4 using the “suitability” construct (i.e. 1=“suitable”, 2=“so-so”, 3=“not very suitable”, 4=“Chinese people more-or-less do not use this word”), as well as optional responses concerning their rating, such as additional comments, caveats, or suggestions for a more suitable 2-syllable word. An example of the resulting ratings sheet during this process is seen below. As Figure 1 exemplifies, for some tone combinations (e.g. T2-T2) average suitability ratings of the five native speakers converged on two specific lexical items, whereas for others (e.g. T2-T1), an additional final decision was needed. In these situations, the final word or words were selected based on the aforementioned (1) relevance to the game context, this time specifically aiming to balance crops that the players can plant across regions of the farm (i.e. ensuring that enough crops are

available relevant to the field, garden, etc.), (3) utility for early learners (prioritizing HSK items), and (4) choosing among equally rated items the item most consistently correctly parsed by ASR.

If two other unanimously high-rated items were not available on the original list which consultants suggested, I selected a high-rated item from another list. I also ensured that the suitability rating was 1 and that at least one rater from another province gave the same rating when asked. This final selection stage yielded 40 items, the average suitability rating of which was no higher than 1.8. Table 3 below presents example target words beginning with tone 1.

Table 3. Example Target Words/Phrases For Each Combination Starting With Tone 1 (High).

Tones	Target word	Tones	Target word
T1-T1	hua ¹ sh ¹ eng (peanut)	T1-T1	x ¹ i gua ¹ (watermelon)
T1-T2	y ¹ ing táo (cherry)	T1-T2	fa ¹ n qié (tomato)
T1-T3	ya ¹ o guo ³ (cashew)	T1-T3	ba ¹ jia ³ o (star anise)
T1-T4	sh ¹ eng cài (cabbage)	T1-T4	xia ¹ ng cài (cilantro)

After finalizing the list of 40 in-game crop items, I developed visual game assets accordingly using crop images freely available online. This entailed creating images displayed in-game as crops growing in soil (e.g. stalk of corn growing), the yield of a crop after it has been harvested (e.g. a corn cob), and a bag of seeds labelled with the crop image, which players can buy in the in-game store and afterwards view in their inventory. A native speaker of Mandarin recorded pronunciation of the 40 in-game crop items, and for the remaining in-game items, such as tools (watering can, sickle, etc.) and destinations (shop, field, garden, etc.), I used JavaScript speech synthesis, freely available as a built-in tool in common web browsers.

2.5 Testing the game

Phase 1: Online pilot using voice input (Spring 2023). During this phase, two undergraduate students played the game online, using the voice input feature. Many of the input commands were not correctly recognized by the web browser's voice recognition, so the game was then updated to use typing input, especially for players with little or no Mandarin learning background. One native speaker of Mandarin Chinese also tested the game during this phase and offered feedback on more natural ways to formulate commands to the farmer.

Phase 2: Online pilot with typing input (Summer 2023). During this phase, two more adults tried the game using typing input. Players were sometimes lost with regard to the next step in game progression. The game was then updated to include a pedagogical agent (the cat) whom the players can ask at any time what to do next if they are unsure.

Phase 3: Thorough playtesting (Fall 2023). Before collecting gameplay or learning data, one adult with both gaming and Mandarin learning experience was selected to test the game thoroughly. This included time required for game completion, intuitiveness of user interface, loading screen times, and length of the assessment. During the cumulative 30 hours of this testing, feedback was iteratively incorporated into the game, so that the tester could see updates as

soon as possible. The following sections report on the resulting version of the game, including a description of core game elements (Section 3) and an assessment (Section 4).

3 Game Description: FarmWing

3.1 Plot

In FarmWing, a player takes on the role of a chicken who lives on a farm in a virtual game world. The farmer's previous owner can no longer run the farm and has passed on ownership to his grandchild. However, the new owner of the farm knows nothing about what to farm, or how to farm it, and the mayor of the town is considering whether the farm is worth maintaining – if the farm is no longer producing crops, the once flourishing farming paradise will need to be paved, perhaps to put up a parking lot. This leaves the farm animals, of which the player's farm chicken avatar is one, understandably concerned. The farm animals, who interact with each other in English, are now in a situation where they must directly tell the farmer, who speaks only Mandarin, where to go and what to do to help the farm thrive again. The farm cat is very familiar with both the farm's regular operations and the farmer's language, but is not on friendly terms with the farmer, rendering the farm chicken the main agent of communication with the farmer. The farmer diligently carries out commands given, as long as they are clear in their content and pronunciation. By communicating with the farmer, the farm chicken can operate the farm, accumulate profits, customize the farmhouse, and convince the mayor that the farmstead should not be decommissioned.

3.2 Game actions: Language commands

The player executes all game actions through interaction with the farmer NPC, which take the form of 4-part commands, telling the farmer to go somewhere and do something to/with something: V1-N1-V2-N2. The player has freedom to create numerous possible commands using these building blocks: verb 1 (V1) (i.e. qù [go]), noun 1 (N1) (i.e. the destination the farmer should go to for completing an action: shaṅgiàn [store], huāyuán [garden], tiánlǐ [in [the] field], guōyuán [orchard], hǎibiān [seaside], or péngzi [shed]), verb 2 (V2) (i.e. the action the farmer should enact regarding a crop: mǎi [buy], mài [sell], ná [fetch], zhòng [plant], or jǐāoshuǐ [water]). If any of the four components of a command are not detected, on-screen feedback shows which components were detected clearly (cf. Wang & Johnson, 2008), displaying an icon of each detected keyword and the “?” symbol for any parts of the command not recognized (i.e. not parsed as any of the actions, destinations, tools, or 30 2-syllable crop items). Figure 1, for example, shows four icons at the top of the screen, signaling that the last typed command included correctly spelled keywords for each part of the command: [go] [field] [water] [wheat].

3.3 Game interface

As seen in Figure 1, the game world of FarmWing is presented in a simple, 90's nostalgia aesthetic, with a rich, ever-present user interface, interactable through mouseclick/touch. Players can click on the action icons (i.e. all actions the farmer can be asked to carry out), item icons (i.e. tools, seeds, or harvested crops in the player's possession), destination icons (i.e. sign

pointing toward the town market for buying/selling, signs marking areas for planting crops), store icons (i.e. the four crops available for purchase on a certain day), or any currently planted crops. This format accomplishes two goals. First, the graphical simplicity allows all relevant linguistic information for the player's problem-solving to be readily accessible on-screen in iconic form, reducing the need to open extra windows or menu screens, while also encouraging players to form L2 typed commands based on iconic rather than text scaffolds. Simply put, because players can only view the Pinyin text of words in feedback and self-initiated support situations, they can never read directly from text while enacting the core game actions via typing input. This helps focus the L2 problem-solving task on command formation (rather than reading pronunciation).

Second, this format (Figure 1) facilitates linguistic interaction with the environment through "highly contextualized graphical representations of context" (Morton & Jack, 2005): The player can view on-screen all actions they may want the farmer to perform, all places where they might want the farmer to perform these actions, and all tools needed for these actions. Such a rich graphically contextualized environment would be difficult to present to players using a realistic 3D aesthetic, considering the immediate problem-solving context. For example, in a simulated L2 task of ordering an item from a menu, a player may need the visual information of the menu, the waiter attending to their speech, and perhaps the amount and format of money available (e.g. paying by cash or card), a visual context well-suited to 3D realism. In the case of instructing a virtual farmer, however, the player need also be aware of additional information to succeed: What tool the farmer is equipped with, what seeds are available for planting, whether space is available for planting a crop, whether a crop has been watered on a given day, and whether a crop is ripe for harvest. Players' ready access to this information, along with the freedom to command various actions at any time, preserves the agency expected in a RPG, and the graphical context allows for each encounter with novel or recently learned linguistic items to be situated in the immediate problem-solving context.

Figure 1. View During Main Gameplay. The Player Avatar Is the Chicken.

3.4 Game progression

An adaptive content presentation module, implemented back-end via Python, is built into the game which automatically tracks player interactions with words of each possible 2-word tone combination and updates the daily four crops available for purchase in the store based on the number of each player's past interactions with the crop. In-game availability of items is adjusted in this way to preserve player agency by allowing free choice, while also subtly encouraging the player to interact with each unique 2-syllable target word (an in-game crop) at least three times – e.g. once when trying to learn the spelling of the crop's name for the first time, once when checking which crop is planted in a certain spot, and once when checking the spelling before harvesting or selling the crop, all of which require grammatical, successfully typed commands, where the target word is spelled correctly. Once a player has interacted three times with a specific crop, the crop is no longer available in the store until the player has completed the post-test. This discourages players from interacting with the same crops over again rather than continuing on with the other target game items.

4 Assessment of Gameplay

Frequency measures were automatically recorded while 73 adults played the game between 60 and 90 minutes. Most were undergraduate students ($n=40$), and the remaining were between ages 18 and 48 ($n=28$). The three frequency measures made were when a player viewed vocabulary support (i.e. whenever a player clicks on a crop in the game to see and hear the pronunciation and meaning), when a player attempted a farming game action (i.e. whenever the player types in a command to try to make the farmer do something), and whether the game action was successful (i.e. correctly typed commands that lead to progress in the game).

Overall, players attempted an average of 77.2 ($SD=43.1$) game actions (i.e. typed commands to the farmer), 47.7 ($SD=32.6$) of which were successful game actions, meaning that the average game action success rate was 61.3%. The other ways players could interact with the game was by clicking on certain crops, destinations, or tools to see and hear the English meaning and Mandarin pronunciation. These "support" events were triggered an average 118.8 times ($SD=25.6$) per player.

4.1 Emerging playstyles

To understand the high standard deviations in performed game actions by players, I considered the possibility of different gameplay styles. Interacting with in-game support was referred to as "research" in the game world, and led to progression in the gameplay session, but did not lead to progress on the player's farm. Some players spent more time clicking items to view these supports, rather than typing commands to the farmer. This play style difference was observed most clearly for 20 players, who made 45 or fewer command attempts, while others made at least 50 command attempts. For an overview of players' gameplay styles, I categorized players using 50 as the threshold for attempts, and median values as thresholds for command accuracy (median: 67.3%) and supports viewed (median: 114). Grouping players based on these thresholds for three gameplay measures yielded 8 categories. 55 of the 73 players fit into one of four categories with at least 10 players in each. Among the "farmers" (i.e. those who made 50 or

more farming command attempts), most players fit into the playstyle of the “resourceful farmer” (n=17) who viewed many supports and made many accurate commands. Next, the “active farmers” (n=16) showed low command accuracy but frequently attempted both farming commands and support. The “precise farmers” (n=12) viewed less support but were still able to maintain high command accuracy. Among the 20 players with a “research” playstyle, the majority belonged to the “casual researcher” category (n=10), showing few and inaccurate farming command attempts and also relatively low engagement with support. Only 3 out of the 20 “research” players showed high accuracy and high support engagement.

4.2 Association with learning

In order to assess which aspects of gameplay are most beneficial for learners, I looked for associations between gameplay measures and learning. The 73 players either had no prior tonal language experience (n=68) or had previous Mandarin language experience (n=5). As a preliminary measure of learning, I used results of a word recall post-test (15 items total, corresponding to the in-game crops). On average, learners with no Mandarin background could identify the meaning of 6.9 words which they heard audio pronunciation for, and learners with Mandarin background remembered meanings of 12.2 words.

To confirm which aspects of gameplay might have benefited learners more, I conducted linear regression analysis three times, using one of the three gameplay analytics as the independent variable and the number of words learned after gameplay as the dependent variable.

Learners with no previous language experience

First, looking at exposure to vocabulary, a linear regression analysis tested whether the frequency of players viewing vocabulary support predicts the number of words remembered. The results indicate that the predictor has a very weak and statistically nonsignificant effect ($p=0.195$, $F(1, 66)=1.71$), with only 2.5% of the variance in words remembered explained by the viewing frequency ($R^2=0.025$). Next, looking at the total number of game action attempts the players made (i.e. typing commands to the farmer), a linear regression analysis revealed a statistically significant positive relationship ($p<0.0001$, $F(1, 66)=19.38$), with the frequency of game action attempts explaining 22.7% of the variance in words remembered ($R^2=0.227$), and each additional game action attempt associated with a 0.048 increase in words remembered. Finally, looking at the number of successful game action attempts (i.e. those which the farmer understood and progressed gameplay), results of the linear regression analysis showed a statistically significant positive relationship ($p<0.0001$, $F(1, 66)=19.85$), with successful game action attempts explaining 23.1% of the variance in words remembered ($R^2=0.231$), and each additional successful game action attempt associated with a 0.060 increase in words remembered. In sum, at least for learners with no prior Mandarin language experience, successful game action attempts and total game action attempts significantly predict word learning, while frequency of viewing vocabulary support does not.

Learners with previous language experience

An additional five learners who played the game and took the vocabulary post-test had some Mandarin language background, so their results were analyzed separately. A linear regression

analysis for these five players showed that the frequency of supports viewed ($p=0.259$), total game action attempts ($p=0.228$), and successful game action attempts ($p=0.240$) do not significantly predict word learning, despite explaining 39.1%, 43.2%, and 41.6% of the variance, respectively. However, these results are complicated by the low number of participants ($n=5$) and the lack of a pre-test which could have controlled for how many words they knew prior to gameplay.

5 Discussion

5.1 Assessment

First, in terms of playstyles, most players who focused on “researching” crops (making few game action attempts) still had lower engagement with supports compared to most of the players with a “farming” playstyle, suggesting that “researching” playstyles were less engaged with the game overall. For the players who engaged with farming, most players either made frequent use of support ($n=33$) or showed high accuracy ($n=12$), reinforcing the notion that engagement with the core game action of farming commands was associated with a more engaged playstyle.

In terms of learning, in the context of simulation games, interaction with target language content – and thereby target perceptual skills – is sometimes associated with better vocabulary learning for words which use the target perceptual skills. Assessment of gameplay patterns and vocabulary learning outcomes for 73 players of the FarmWing farming simulation game suggest that vocabulary learning is predicted by frequency of interaction with target language content while performing game actions (i.e. game action attempts) but not necessarily while learning about the language content (i.e. vocabulary support). This pattern seems to hold for successful and unsuccessful game action attempts.

Gameplay results revealed high standard deviations in how frequently players performed game actions, which revealed that the task design encouraged very different playstyles. For designers of educational simulation games, it is good to have learning support available, but game task design should focus on encouraging the player to attempt core game actions. This could be motivated through a compelling narrative and game progression system, and through intrinsically enjoyable game actions with clear consequences. In this way, players engage with the target language content to solve problems, reinforcing foundational linguistic perceptual skills for them in a condensed, targeted way.

5.2 Limitations

This study primarily involved adults with no prior Mandarin experience, with only a preliminary analysis of five learners with prior knowledge, making it unclear whether the observed gameplay patterns hold for more experienced learners, or for learners in K-12 contexts. Causation also remains unclear, as factors such as player motivation could influence both game action attempts and vocabulary learning. Rigorous experimental study is needed to better identify which gameplay patterns are most associated with learning and how they can be naturally encouraged. Finally, this paper focuses on best practices for linguistic perceptual skills. Designers

interested in targeting non-linguistic perceptual skills should consider in what ways the game genre, context, and content would differ.

5.3 Recommended best practices for designers

Identify the foundational perceptual skill. Identify skills that your learners struggle with broadly, which serve as building blocks for other core skills. Focus on those which are not easily trained through traditional classroom methods and available resources. This process should be informed by first and second language acquisition research to better understand what elements of naturalistic language use might be missing in the curriculum.

Select the game genre where the skill can be enhanced. First, select a learning framework to identify learning mechanics relevant to the target perceptual skill(s). These include strategies from second language acquisition, learning sciences, and instructional design. Then, select several game mechanics that might link intuitively to the skill(s). Lastly, select a game genre or combination of genres associated with the chosen game mechanics.

Select the game context and language content. From the possible game mechanics in your selected genre(s), choose the core game action(s) which the player will perform most often in the game in order to progress. Try to align these with the target learning actions as much as possible (Ke, 2016). Ideally, the player should be exposed to the target perceptual skill during performance of all or most core game actions. Lastly, based on typical game tasks associated with your chosen game genre(s), identify tasks that involve words which exemplify the target perceptual skill. These tasks should require the player to perform the core game actions in order to succeed.

Update language content with subject matter experts. Involve subject matter experts early in the game design process. Be willing to adjust the language content, game context, and game environment based on their feedback. In the case of linguistic interventions, remember that language is a culturally situated entity, and insight from native speakers is essential to this process.

Prepare the game for assessment. While creating functional prototypes of the game, the core game mechanics should already be clear, and understanding how players interact with the game will be helpful for improving player experience and assessing how well the intervention benefits learning. For this reason, it is good to keep track of game actions made by players in a way that is unintrusive yet transparent and respectful of individual privacy. Some recommendations include making sure players are aware of what data is collected, using a secure server in a secure location to store gameplay data, and collecting gameplay data rather than “learning analytics”. In other words, data should be descriptive (i.e. how the player interacts with the game) rather than qualitative (i.e. how “well” does the player perform). For any data that could be considered learning-related, or performance-assessing, I recommend using a clear post-test: If players consent to participate in a study, then gameplay patterns and learning assessment can be connected, but otherwise gameplay patterns should be stored anonymously and securely.

Test and incorporate feedback. Test with players as much as possible, including those within the target learner population and beta-testers who can explore game elements deeply with

detailed feedback. Iteratively change the game, removing elements that distract players or which players consistently ignore. Be willing to adjust the game input, mechanics, and environment based on player feedback. Set yourself up to fail fast and effectively during iterative game development and testing: Learn richly from failures and remember that unsuccessful features of the game do not reflect you as a designer, but rather the areas where the game or simulation can improve, facilitating better learning with more enjoyable gameplay.

Disclosure of Interests

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Chapter

Organizational Systems & Process Management

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Application of Systems Thinking and Gamification for Improving Scrum Acceptance Among Decision-makers

Abstract

This paper explores the integration of systems thinking and gamification to enhance the acceptance of Scrum among decision-makers. Despite its benefits, Scrum often encounters resistance among decision-makers due to its perceived complexity, unfamiliarity, and misalignment with traditional organizational goals. An empirical study highlights the significance of decision-maker involvement, clarity of roles, and effective communication for successful Scrum adoption. Findings reveal that structured feedback mechanisms, clear communication strategies, and alignment with organizational goals are critical for overcoming resistance.

Systems thinking provides a holistic framework to address these challenges, emphasizing interdependencies, iterative processes, and the alignment of practices with broader objectives. Gamification complements this approach by fostering engagement and motivation through interactive learning experiences.

To address these issues, a gamified simulation based on the impactation® method is proposed, enabling decision-makers to explore Scrum's dynamics, visualize interdependencies, and understand its iterative nature in a dynamic and interactive environment. The impactation® framework is based on systems thinking and helps illustrate how visible elements such as processes are linked to deeper factors such as culture and team skills.

This combined approach provides practical strategies for overcoming resistance, promoting strategic alignment, and ensuring sustainable Scrum adoption, effectively connecting high-level strategy with operational execution.

Keywords: Scrum, Systems thinking, Gamified simulation, Decision-makers

1 Introduction/Background

This paper aims to explore how systems thinking combined with gamification can address decision-makers' resistance to Scrum by enhancing their understanding and commitment to the framework, and to propose a gamification concept that fosters Scrum acceptance.

1.1 Research methodology

The research methodology includes a literature review on Scrum, systems thinking, and gamification, followed by an empirical study using an online questionnaire. The survey investigates decision-makers' perspectives on Scrum as well as the views of Scrum participants on how decision-makers influence Scrum effectiveness. It tests hypotheses on involvement, complexity,

feedback, and communication. Based on these findings, a gamified training simulation for decision-makers is proposed, leveraging the impactation® method (iCONDU GmbH, n.d. b).

1.2 Literature review

1.2.1 Scrum

Scrum is an agile framework designed to enhance collaboration and productivity in project management (Schwaber & Sutherland, 2020). Rooted in the Agile Manifesto, Scrum emphasizes iterative development, self-organizing teams, and continuous feedback. Key artifacts include the product backlog, sprint backlog, and increment, while events such as sprints, sprint planning, and retrospectives structure the workflow (Cervone, 2011).

1.2.2 Strategic role of decision-makers

Although not explicitly defined as a distinct role in Scrum, decision-makers play a critical strategic role by ensuring alignment with organizational goals and providing essential resources to support project success (Maximini & Pilster, 2023). Their engagement bridges the gap between high-level strategy and operational execution by establishing structures, defining overarching objectives, and driving organizational change beyond the scope of Scrum teams. Unlike product owners, who focus mainly on tactical project management, decision-makers prioritize strategic decisions and resource allocation (Wiechmann & Röpstorff, 2022). They complement the roles of product owner, Scrum master, and development team by providing disciplined leadership to address impediments and foster development, process-oriented leadership to enhance team dynamics and align processes with goals, and technical leadership to clarify requirements and offer strategic input, as shown in Figure 1 (Maximini & Pilster, 2023).

Figure 1. Integration points of decision-makers' influences. Action description inspired by Maximini and Pilster (2023).

1.2.3 Resistance from decision-makers

The adoption of Scrum is often met with resistance from decision-makers. Concerns include the disruption of established processes, perceived risks, and uncertainty associated with iterative methods (Hoda & Murugesan, 2016; Stock et al., 2021). Decision-makers' hesitation often arises from a focus on delivering the end product and a reluctance to disrupt workflows, compounded by cultural and organizational barriers such as distributed teams and rigid processes. While their support is essential for any successful implementation of Scrum, they will often demand evidence of successful outcomes before considering full endorsement (Hoda & Murugesan, 2016; Schwaber & Sutherland, 2020).

Challenges also include insufficient understanding of Scrum principles, inadequate communication, and perceived complexity, highlighting the need for continuous training and robust communication structures (Cohn, 2005; Stock et al., 2021). Further resistance can arise from decision-makers' demand for heavy documentation and frequent status updates, which conflicts with Agile's emphasis on minimal documentation (Hoda & Murugesan, 2016). To address these issues, organizations should align Scrum practices with business goals, provide transparent updates, and foster stakeholder trust through engagement and role clarity (Gloger, 2013; Schiller & Heider, 2022).

Table 1. Decision-maker resistance and acceptance aspects in Scrum implementation.

Resistance aspects	Options to gain acceptance
Concerns about disrupting established processes or perceived risks (Hoda & Murugesan, 2016)	Provide evidence of successful agile implementations and positive project impacts (Gloger, 2013)
Hesitation due to focus on final product delivery and fear of disruption (Hoda & Murugesan, 2016)	Demonstrate how Scrum aligns with organizational goals and delivers business value (Schwaber & Sutherland, 2020)
Perceived uncertainty and risk in iterative nature of Scrum (Stock et al., 2021)	Clear communication and transparency (e.g. progress updates, KPIs) (Virag, 2021)
Continued demand for heavy documentation and status reports (Hoda & Murugesan, 2016)	Educate decision-makers on cultural implications and Agile philosophy (Cohn, 2005)
Need for proof of successful project deliveries before endorsement (Hoda & Murugesan, 2016)	Support incremental adoption to ease transition and reduce resistance (Cohn, 2005)
Existing organizational culture and distributed teams (Hoda & Murugesan, 2016)	Ensure decision-makers understand their roles and available resources (Schiller & Heider, 2022)
Reluctance due to need for long-term support and developer adaptation (Overhage & Schlauderer, 2012)	Engage decision-makers in planning and rollout for ownership and trust (Cohn, 2005)
Inadequate coordination and structured communication (Stock et al., 2021)	Adapt communication strategies to project needs and culture (Stock et al., 2021)
Lack of understanding of Scrum principles (Cohn, 2005)	Offer training and continuous support for decision-makers (Schiller & Heider, 2022)
External pressure from clients unfamiliar with agile methods (Conboy & Fitzgerald, 2010)	Provide clear change management and structured controls (Cohn, 2005)
Fast-paced markets and competition hindering focus on Scrum (Boehm & Turner, 2005)	Highlight tangible benefits such as efficiency and stakeholder satisfaction (Conboy & Fitzgerald, 2010)

A structured approach to change management, coupled with incremental adoption strategies, can significantly ease the transition to agile practices. Highlighting the tangible benefits of Scrum through measurable outcomes, strategic alignment, and active stakeholder involvement helps to reduce resistance and win long-term support from decision-makers (Cohn, 2005; Schiller & Heider, 2022).

Table 1 provides a comprehensive overview of the literature on resistance and acceptance among decision-makers, highlighting its relevance to Scrum implementation.

1.2.4 Systems thinking: Application in organizations and Scrum implementation

Systems thinking is a holistic approach that emphasizes an understanding of complex systems as interconnected wholes, examining their interactions with the environment (Senge, 1990). It focuses on causal relationships and feedback loops within systems, offering insights into how components influence one another (Ross & Wade, 2015; Chowdhury, 2024; Nordby et al., 2024).

Unlike traditional analytical methods that prioritize specific details, systems thinking highlights the dynamics of change and broader contexts, enabling a transformative perspective for addressing problems (Gharajedaghi, 2011; Monat & Gannon, 2023). It further reveals how visible events are shaped by underlying systemic structures and mental models, offering deeper insights into root causes and interdependencies (Monat & Gannon, 2023).

In organizational contexts, systems thinking offers a comprehensive perspective on dynamics by emphasizing relationships, feedback loops, and systemic structures, using tools such as the casual loop diagram (Gharajedaghi, 2011). Recognizing organizations as open systems, it emphasizes their continuous interaction with market trends, regulatory changes, technological advancements, and other external factors, requiring adaptability to maintain competitiveness (Sterman, 2000; Clawson, 2008; Zürn & Joe, 2024).

Moreover, systems thinking drives innovation and learning by integrating new ideas and examining how mindset, behavior, and systemic interactions influence outcomes. This leads to improved transparency, accountability, and collaboration, enabling better alignment with organizational objectives (Norqvist & Ärlestig, 2021; Zürn & Holzner, 2025).

In the context of Scrum, systems thinking extends beyond viewing the framework as a process, positioning it as an interconnected system influenced by team dynamics, stakeholder interactions, and external pressures. It helps to identify how changes in one area, such as roles or market demands, can impact the entire system, enhancing proactive management of complexities (Rajagopal et al., 2024). By encouraging teams to consider their contributions within a larger organizational context, systems thinking promotes alignment with goals and customer satisfaction while fostering a deeper understanding of Scrum components such as roles and events (Flemm, 2020).

A comprehensive systems thinking approach enables decision-makers to better understand Scrum's internal dynamics, manage boundaries, and align strategies with evolving environments, fostering adaptability and continuous improvement.

1.2.5 *Systems thinking-based gamification in the Scrum context*

Gamification integrates game-like elements into non-game contexts to enhance engagement and motivation (Deterding et al., 2011). It leverages motivational elements such as feedback, rewards, and challenges to engage participants (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990). Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 1985), Flow Theory (Conboy & Fitzgerald, 2010), and other approaches highlight the psychological foundations of gamification. These frameworks emphasize the importance of autonomy, competence, and relatedness in fostering intrinsic motivation.

Gamified simulations provide an engaging way to understand new frameworks or methodologies, reducing resistance and fostering deeper understanding (Krath et al., 2021; Najjar et al., 2021). These simulations allow participants to experience core practices and enhance their understanding of adaptability and value (Aparicio et al., 2012). Features such as immediate feedback and progressively challenging tasks improve learning outcomes, making complex practices more intuitive and encouraging organizational adoption (Mulhern, 2013). Even though this approach has not yet been applied to Scrum specifically for the role of decision-makers, the required elements for fostering decision-makers' acceptance of Scrum are similar. Gamified learning material for Scrum already exists.

The combination of systems thinking and gamification creates a comprehensive learning experience by combining organizational integration with sustained motivation and practical understanding (Deterding et al., 2011; Nordby et al., 2024; Senge, 1990). Systems thinking offers a framework to address Scrum's complexity, interactions, and organizational integration, tackling resistance and aligning practices with business objectives. Tools such as system analysis and feedback loops highlight Scrum's iterative nature and the impact of decisions on outcomes (Gharajedaghi, 2011).

Because they enhance engagement by fostering active participation and reducing apprehension, gamified simulations enable decision-makers to interact with Scrum concepts in realistic scenarios, aligning learning with intrinsic and extrinsic motivations.

1.3 Scrum training simulation

1.3.1 *Simulation game design*

In the simulation, Scrum's dynamics are built upon the impactation® framework – mapped into four critical impact areas: Capacities and Culture, Processes and Organization, Short-Term Impacts, and Long-Term Impacts (see Figure 2).

This framework adopts a systems thinking perspective, highlighting how apparent elements such as processes and methods interact with foundational, less visible factors such as organizational culture and team skills. This approach emphasizes the importance of addressing both surface-level, measurable outcomes and the deeper systemic structures that drive them. The success of Scrum depends not only on visible processes and immediate results but also on the alignment of overlooked systemic factors, such as organizational mindsets and structural dynamics, which are crucial for sustainable, long-term success (iCONDU GmbH, n.d. b; Monat & Gannon, 2023).

Figure 2. Impactation® method based on iCONDU GmbH (2024).

Building on this foundation, the simulation serves as an interactive platform that bridges theoretical understanding with practical application. It empowers decision-makers to engage with Scrum's core principles by allowing them to visualize interdependencies, modify variables to observe systemic impacts, and comprehend Scrum's iterative processes (Zürn & Holzner, 2025).

1.3.2 Structural features

Dynamic scenario design

The simulation, following an approach outlined by Rajagopal et al. (2024) and expanded upon by Zürn and Holzner (2025), incorporates real-life challenges including resource constraints, stakeholder conflicts, and external disruptions. Engaging with such unpredictability fosters decision-making agility, enhancing participants' understanding of iterative processes.

Participants interact with the simulation through several tools designed to illustrate systemic dynamics:

1. *Predefined contextual actions*: Participants select from actions tailored to specific project scenarios, each with associated short- and long-term consequences. This mechanism encourages thoughtful trade-offs between immediate benefits and future risks, while challenging players to interpret and respond to indirect outcomes.
2. *Impact matrixes*: Visual tools map the relationships and pathways of influence within the system, aiding participants in identifying leverage points and systemic interconnections.
3. *Impact chains and feedback loops*: These tools enable participants to track and analyze cause-effect relationships over time, offering insights into iterative decision-making.
4. *Manual state adjustments*: By modifying variables, participants can experiment with system states to observe direct and cascading impacts, enhancing their understanding of systemic dynamics.
5. *Holistic thinking*: The simulation's adaptive design, grounded in the impactation® method, fosters systems thinking by highlighting interdependencies and feedback mechanisms. Par-

ticipants gain insights into leverage points within Scrum's processes, enabling them to anticipate systemic changes and align their decisions with strategic objectives.

1.4 Objectives of the study

Today's business world is increasingly driven by software innovation and dynamic user interactions. Organizations must therefore adapt quickly to changing demands. This transformative shift emerged as traditional methods were unable to keep pace with the accelerating demands of modern systems and markets (Dong & Zhang, 2024). Consequently, effective project management has become crucial in navigating the high-pressure environment of constant innovation. Agile methodologies, and Scrum in particular, provide a framework for managing complex projects through iterative cycles and continuous feedback (Boehm & Turner, 2005). Despite Scrum's widespread adoption, decision-makers often resist its implementation due to unfamiliarity, perceived risks, and misalignment with organizational goals (Hoda & Murugesan, 2016).

Systems thinking – a holistic approach that examines systems as interconnected entities – helps decision-makers understand the broader impact of Scrum on organizational goals and dynamics (Nordby et al., 2024). Gamification, which incorporates game-like elements into non-game activities, enhances engagement and motivation, making it an effective tool for training and adoption (Norqvist & Ärlestig, 2021).

To explore the factors influencing Scrum adoption and deepen the understanding of how decision-makers' perceptions and involvement impact its success, the following six hypothesis were tested in a survey:

- H1: Decision-makers' involvement positively influences Scrum adoption.
- H2: Perceived complexity of Scrum acts as a barrier.
- H3: Alignment of Scrum benefits with organizational goals encourages adoption.
- H4: Continuous feedback fosters decision-maker support.
- H5: Transparency in roles and responsibilities fosters acceptance.
- H6: Optimum communication improves decision-makers' perceptions of Scrum.

2 Method

2.1 Survey design and respondent demographics

To understand the challenges decision-makers face when implementing Scrum and how systems thinking and gamification can encourage participation, an empirical study was conducted using an online survey. The survey gathered insights from decision-makers and non-decision-makers, identifying barriers to Scrum adoption and potential solutions. By analyzing the hypotheses, the study highlights key areas for improvement to foster greater decision-maker engagement and facilitate Scrum adoption.

The questionnaire was designed to ensure convenience, broad reach, and quick response times (Van Selm & Jankowski, 2006). An initial filter question tailored subsequent questions to the respondent's role in relation to Scrum, branching into paths for decision-makers (executive &

senior/middle managers) and non-decision-makers (project managers & Scrum team members). An even-numbered scale was used to eliminate neutral middle ground, to encourage clear positions and to provide clearer insights (Ortmanns & Sonntag, 2023).

The survey included a small sample of 51 participants, which is insufficient for a detailed statistical analysis (Lund, 2023). However, the focus was on validating the gamification elements through feedback from project managers and decision-makers. Of the participants, 57 percent were decision-makers and 43 percent non-decision-makers, providing a balanced representation and diverse insights into Scrum adoption challenges. Among decision-makers, familiarity with Scrum varied, with 47 percent reporting they were very familiar and 17 percent indicating limited knowledge.

2.2 Scrum training simulation – Integrating systems thinking and gamification

The resistance factors and gaps in expertise among decision-makers, identified through the literature review and survey, are incorporated into the Scrum training simulation. The design, structural features, and practical application of a Scrum training simulation that integrates systems thinking and gamification are examined, highlighting how the simulation overcomes challenges, promotes engagement, and strengthens decision-maker support for Scrum adoption.

3 Results

3.1 Survey results

3.1.1 Hypothesis testing details

Six hypotheses derived from the literature review were validated by the responses of the questionnaire.

- H1: Decision-makers' involvement positively influences Scrum adoption. 48 percent of decision-makers reported a moderate level of engagement, aligning with Scrum's guidelines. However, 22 percent cited missing involvement as a barrier. Non-decision-makers also emphasized the importance of decision-maker support, with 34 percent stating that increased acknowledgment and engagement would enhance their comfort and participation in Scrum initiatives. Training and role clarification were recommended to enhance their participation.
- H2: Perceived complexity of Scrum acts as a barrier. While 62 percent of decision-makers rated Scrum as moderately complex, only 17 percent identified complexity as a primary barrier. Non-decision-makers shared similar views. Complexity appears to be a secondary issue, with other barriers such as role clarity playing a more significant role. Simplifying terminology and improving transparency might mitigate these concerns.
- H3: Alignment of Scrum benefits with organizational goals encourages adoption. Alignment with organizational goals was a key motivator, cited by 48 percent of decision-makers, who emphasized measurable benefits such as improved KPIs. Respondents highlighted the need to demonstrate quick wins, align priorities, and emphasize successes to build trust and foster adoption. This is aligned with the designated strategic role of deci-

sion-makers in the Scrum process and highlights the necessity of structured communication and measurable benefits to foster decision-maker buy-in.

- H4: Continuous feedback fosters decision-makers' support. Continuous feedback was deemed essential, with 62 percent rating it "very important". Suggestions included incorporating decision-makers' perspectives and emphasizing quick wins to build trust. Structured feedback mechanisms, such as progress updates and KPI tracking, emerged as essential for maintaining support.
- H5: Transparency in roles and responsibilities fosters acceptance. Role clarity was identified as crucial, with 72 percent of decision-makers rating it "very important". Lack of role clarity was the most frequently cited barrier among non-decision-makers (25 percent). Training, role definition, and clear communication were highlighted as priorities to reduce resistance and foster alignment.
- H6: Optimum communication improves decision-maker's perceptions of Scrum. Balanced communication was preferred, with 57 percent of non-decision-makers favoring moderate involvement with regular feedback. Effective communication strategies were identified as critical for reducing uncertainty and fostering engagement.

3.1.2 Findings

Key findings reveal that decision-maker involvement positively impacts Scrum adoption, but their current level of involvement is often inadequate.

Clarifying roles and providing continuous feedback are essential to gaining their support, as unclear responsibilities and poor communication were identified as significant barriers.

Simplifying the perceived complexity of Scrum through accessible terminology and transparent processes can address reluctance, while aligning Scrum practices with organizational goals and demonstrating measurable benefits, such as improved KPIs and quick wins, can increase acceptance.

Structured feedback mechanisms and clear communication strategies were also highlighted as critical to reducing uncertainty and maintaining the confidence of decision-makers. To address these challenges, targeted training, role definition, and strategic alignment should be prioritized. By focusing on these aspects, organizations can encourage the active participation of decision-makers, create a supportive environment that aligns Scrum adoption with strategic goals, and ultimately enhance its success and long-term sustainability.

3.2 Scrum training simulation

Drawing on insights from the literature review and empirical study, the Scrum training simulation was developed. It provides a holistic representation of Scrum dynamics, addressing the central question, How can decision-makers effectively support Scrum's success within an organization? (iCONDU GmbH, n.d. a, b)

The simulation's main screen presents the four impact areas, their corresponding goals and initial states, and how they interrelate (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Scrum training simulation Simcision.

The goals of the Scrum training simulation were chosen to address the key barriers identified through the literature review and survey findings, ensuring an effective approach to fostering decision-makers’ engagement and reducing resistance (see Table 2).

Table 2. The Scrum training simulation’s 12 goals.

Goal	Description
1. Agile mindset and collaborative culture	A mindset that is aligned with agile principles and a collaborative organizational culture
2. Organizational readiness for change	Preparedness of the organization to embrace structural and cultural shifts for Scrum adoption
3. Awareness of Scrum roles and responsibilities	Clear understanding of Scrum roles, responsibilities, and expectations among all stakeholders
4. Process enablement and transparency	Clear, transparent processes supported by adequate resources and workshops
5. Customer enablement and preparation	Alignment and readiness of customers to engage with the Scrum framework
6. Workflow integration and communication structure	Effective integration of workflows and communication structures within Scrum practices
7. Clear, consistent Scrum processes	Standardized and well-defined Scrum processes across the organization

Goal	Description
8. Team productivity and customer satisfaction	High-performing teams delivering satisfaction and value to customers
9. Visibility of progress	Clear visibility of progress and results, with outcomes effectively communicated to stakeholders
10. Value delivery and sustainable business value:	Delivery of tangible value while fostering long-term business sustainability
11. Strategic alignment and continuous improvement	Alignment of Scrum practices with strategic goals and ongoing process improvement
12. Organizational resilience and adaptability	A resilient organization capable of adapting to change and thriving in a dynamic environment

3.3 Practical outcomes

By combining systems thinking and gamification, the simulation provides decision-makers with the tools to foster agile principles within their organizations. Participants develop a practical understanding of Scrum dynamics, enabling them to support transparent processes, improve communication, and enhance team productivity.

The simulation includes various practical gamified elements, such as relationship analysis tools, realistic events and decision-making actions, and evaluation models that simulate the outcomes of their choices. All of these elements are derived to clarify decision-makers' key barriers to adoption.

3.3.1 Analyzing relationships

The simulation provides tools such as Cross-Impact matrixes to analyze relationships between system elements. The Cross-Impact matrix shows how elements influence each other and identifies which elements can be intentionally adjusted, providing insight into the most relevant levers for changing the current system state. Element states can also be changed manually, allowing users to observe how their influence and sensitivity evolve outside a simulation. The Chain of Effects feature further enhances analysis by allowing users to explore relationships and pathways between selected elements (see Figure 4) (Rajagopal et al., 2024).

Together, these tools provide a comprehensive understanding of system dynamics, helping decision-makers identify critical levers and optimize performance.

Figure 4. Impact Chain in the Scrum training simulation.

3.3.2 Events and actions

As outlined by Rajagopal et al. (2024), the Scrum simulation includes events and actions, each influencing the system's dynamics. Actions are manually planned interventions designed to directly impact specific elements, often used to respond to events, mitigate negative effects, or enhance positive dynamics. By contrast, events occur automatically within a predefined framework, simulating real-world impacts on elements and resources without user intervention that create immediate systemic effects (iCONDU GmbH, n.d. a; Rajagopal et al., 2024).

Figure 5. Event in the Scrum training simulation.

Appendix 1 highlights the different events which can occur during a simulation, such as: "Shift in market demand – A sudden change in market trends requires rapid reprioritization of the product backlog" or "Customer requirement change – Mid-sprint a customer changes requirements, requiring backlog refinement" (see Figure 5). Each event poses a challenge or opportunity for decision-makers, whose choices determine whether these events drive successful Scrum outcomes or result in project delays. Appendix 2 lists the various actions available in the simulation, such as: "Facilitate cross-department meetings to break down silos and foster collaboration across departments" or "Provide internal agile training sessions" (see Figure 6).

Figure 6. Action in the Scrum training simulation.

By integrating these actions into the simulation, users are empowered to interact with the model, enabling strategic decision-making and adaptive responses to changing conditions. This dynamic interplay of actions and events equips decision-makers with the skills to navigate complexity, respond effectively, and enhance Scrum implementation success.

3.4 Evaluation of decisions

The simulation offers tools for conducting a sensitivity analysis, as outlined by Rajagopal et al. (2024). This analysis evaluates the strategies and measures implemented by users, projecting performance improvements over time and assessing system behavior across various scenarios and dynamic conditions. It provides critical insights into the robustness and adaptability of decisions, helping users to optimize their strategies for long-term success. Example evaluations, illustrating these capabilities, are presented in Figures 7 and 8.

Figure 7. The “Strategic alignment and continuous improvement” target with and without actions taken (screenshot of evaluation dashboard of a simulation run).

Figure 8. Evaluation of targets in a spider chart (screenshot of evaluation dashboard of a simulation run).

In the context of the Scrum training simulation, this analysis provides decision-makers with critical insights into the potential outcomes of their decisions. It allows them to test the robustness of their strategies, identify potential risks, and adapt measures to achieve optimum results.

4 Discussion

The integration of systems thinking and gamification provides a compelling framework for addressing the challenges decision-makers face when adopting Scrum. Systems thinking promotes a holistic understanding of agile dynamics and their alignment with organizational goals, while gamification increases engagement and motivation through interactive learning. Together, these approaches address critical barriers such as perceived complexity, resistance to change, and lack of role clarity.

The proposed simulation game, based on the impactation® method, provides decision-makers with an engaging platform to visualize interdependencies, experiment with iterative processes, and understand how strategic decisions affect overall outcomes. Empirical findings underline the importance of continuous feedback, structured communication, and demonstrating measurable benefits to align decision-makers with Scrum principles.

By fostering collaboration and enhancing understanding, this approach holds significant potential to improve decision-makers' acceptance and support the long-term success of Scrum in dynamic business environments.

It is worth noting, however, that the study on which the simulation concept is based has some limitations: As it relied on voluntary participation in an online survey, there is a risk of self-selection bias, as participants who already have a good understanding of or interest in Scrum or gamification may have been more likely to respond. Combined with the relatively small sample size, this could bias the results towards a more positive perception of Scrum, and certain aspects of the simulation approach may have been overlooked. Furthermore, the proposed simulation has not yet been empirically tested in real-world settings, limiting the depth of the present analysis.

To fill this gap, future research should aim to refine the simulation design by assessing its effectiveness in different real-world organizational contexts, using pre- and post-simulation surveys to measure its impact.

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Appendix

Appendix 1. Selected Events featured in the Scrum training simulation.

Events	Description
Shift in market demand	A sudden change in market trends requires rapid reprioritization of the product backlog
Sudden team resignation	A key team member leaves, impacting sprint progress
Customer requirement change	Mid-sprint, a customer changes requirements, requiring backlog refinement
Critical feature identification	A new high-impact feature is identified mid-sprint
Budget constraint	A company-wide budget constraint
Equipment/Tool update request	The Scrum team requests improved tools to increase productivity
Customer concerns	Customers express concerns about delivery delays or changing priorities

Appendix 2. Selected Actions featured in the Scrum training simulation.

Actions
Conduct organizational readiness assessment to evaluate the organization's preparedness for adopting Scrum
Provide internal agile training sessions to educate teams on Scrum principles and agile mindset
Facilitate cross-department meetings to break down silos and foster collaboration across departments
Set strategic KPIs
Standardize Scrum frameworks – Provide templates and guidelines for consistent practices across teams
Reprioritize product backlog/ revision of the story/ goals

Maren Schaal, Gesine Hilf & Wolf Wenger

Field Report on the Implementation of the ERPsim Business Simulation in Higher Education

Abstract

Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems allow companies to handle various core processes through a common software and database shared across different business departments. The use of these systems requires practice. To support the learning process, ERP systems can already be introduced in higher education to train future professionals. DHBW Stuttgart is currently implementing the ERPsim business simulation developed by Hautes Études Commerciales (HEC) Montréal. First implementations of the software-based game have already taken place with students of different study programs and different semesters. Data was collected, comparing the simulation game to courses teaching SAP with case studies, indicating positive effects of the ERPsim simulation on the perceived learning experience. According to the survey, students found the interactive way of exploring the software to be a positive aspect. However, further data is needed to confirm the preliminary assumptions.

Keywords: Simulation and gaming, Game implementation, Evaluation, Business administration, Higher education.

1 Introduction

1.1 The use of simulation games at DHBW Stuttgart

Business games are very important at the Baden-Wuerttemberg Cooperative State University Stuttgart (DHBW Stuttgart). Their use was institutionalized by the university's teaching and research center (ZMS) more than 15 years ago. Over time, the portfolio of games has grown considerably and is continuously adapted to the needs of the study programs. Usually, simulation games are tested in elective courses and, if feedback is consistently high, incorporated into the curriculum on a long-term basis. The new simulation game ERPsim, whose potential for use at DHBW was discovered by Professors Gesine Hilf and Wolf Wenger, has been subject to testing since September 2024. They are currently piloting the game in their own courses. ERPsim deals with business management processes in a competitive market. These are experienced in a real ERP system. The function of the system is briefly explained below.

1.2 ERP systems

Enterprise Resource Planning systems (ERP) are integrated software systems that manage and optimize business processes in companies. They cover areas such as finance, human resources, production, sales, and supply chain management. By managing data centrally, they enable more efficient communication and collaboration between departments. ERP systems improve transparency and decision-making by providing real-time data and comprehensive reporting. They are particularly important for larger companies in order to stay competitive and simplify

complex processes. The following figure illustrates the widespread use of ERP software solutions.

Figure 1. The Widespread Use of ERP Systems.

ERP systems are complex and require user training and regular practice in order to be used efficiently. Due to the large number of functions and deep integration into all business processes, users need a good understanding of the systems and their capabilities. Since almost all larger companies rely on such systems, it is reasonable to familiarize university students with them. In this way, students can gain practical experience at an early stage and are better prepared for their (future) workplaces.

1.3 ERPsim game

ERPsim is a simulation game developed by the École des Hautes Études Commerciales (HEC) Montréal (2025). It is based on the SAP S/4HANA software. With SAP solutions being one of the most commonly used business software solutions, the game aims to provide a learning experience close to the real use of such systems.

To access the game with the original SAP S/4HANA interface (see Figures 2 and 3), users need a software client provided by the SAP University Competence Center (UCC). These centers host various SAP solutions for research and education. Currently, UCC Magdeburg (2025) at the Otto-von-Guericke-Universität is providing DHBW Stuttgart's client to access the SAP system.

In comparison to SAP case studies as a teaching method, which can also be done on a real SAP host, the game-based approach focuses even more on learning by doing. Other business simulation games also follow this strategy, mostly on fake softwares that can differ widely from real-life software.

ERPsim offers various game settings with different foci and levels of complexity. Besides an introduction game called Maple Game equipped only with a price-handling feature, games with a focus on logistics, retail, or manufacturing including sustainability aspects can be played in varying complexity. One didactical approach is to start the introductory setting for a softer entry into the system. After several rounds of learning the final game setting can be introduced.

The demands placed on the teams remain complex, especially under time pressure. Open protocol data (OData) enables participants to access real-time data from SAP and display it in their own planning dashboards in familiar systems such as MS Excel or PowerBI. This provides another teaching opportunity especially for students specializing in data or computer science.

The game, which has grown over the years, is increasingly being looked at from a variety of research perspectives. Positive learning experiences have been documented, such as increased knowledge of enterprise systems and a significant improvement in soft and hard skills. The game also appears to increase learners' willingness to learn, their creativity and their self-efficacy (Faisal & Chadhar, 2024). Other studies look at the use of the software and find that college students are satisfied with the usability of the system. In addition, the usefulness of the system is rated positively, which in turn leads to a positive rating of the game's usefulness (Shim, 2024). The didactic double-decker, in which users are introduced to content and system simultaneously, has already been identified as an opportunity at other universities and integrated into existing teaching concepts (Kremer, 2022).

In this project, however, the promising aspects of the game will also be examined in connection with other teaching methods. The question arises as to whether it is worth replacing existing teaching methods. In particular, the question is whether the simulation can keep up with ERP case studies, and whether, in direct comparison, it adds value to teaching production planning methods.

2 Pilot Testing

2.1 Implementation

Pilot testing took place in classes with business engineering and business information technology students. The theoretical methods of material requirements planning are taught in these classes beforehand and students are familiar with the principal use of ERP systems. To compare teaching SAP S/4HANA using ERPsim or classical case studies with click instructions, students took part in an evaluation after the course. In the following, the setting, the evaluation, and the results are shown.

2.2 Evaluation

To evaluate the first applications of the ERPsim game, a questionnaire was distributed following the seminar. Thanks to direct processing on site, the response rate was high. The survey period started in September 2024, with data up to 1 July 2025 included in this paper. The sample consists of 80 participants.

For better comparability, the classic lecture format (the SAP case study) was also included in a questionnaire with identical items. This provides the first set of comparable data, although the sample (43 participants) is still quite small at this stage.

The questionnaire itself consists of closed quantitative questions and a section with open qualitative questions. They address the gameplay experience and handling as well as students' understanding of the theoretical background of production planning.

3 Results

3.1 Quantitative insights

The quantitative dimensions were measured on 5-point Likert scales. The following topics were covered.

Table 1. Closed Questions.

Dimension	Question	Scale points
Interest beforehand	"My interest prior to the <i>simulation game/case study</i> was..."	[1] very low – [5] very high
Understanding afterwards	"I have understood how the <i>simulation game/case study</i> works."	[1] does not apply at all – [5] fully applies
Comprehensibility	"The results of the <i>simulation game/case study</i> are easy to understand."	[1] does not apply at all – [5] fully applies
Practice-Orientation	"The <i>simulation game/case study</i> was close to practice."	[1] does not apply at all – [5] fully applies
Level of Difficulty	"The level of difficulty of the <i>simulation game/case study</i> was for me..."	[1] too low – [5] too high

The results of the students' respective assessments of the two methods are compared below.

Figure 4. Survey Results Comparing the Game and Case Study Experience.

On average, both the case study and the use of ERPsim received similar ratings. When asked about their interest in the specific event in advance, the business game as a method aroused slightly more interest. This is presumably due to the interactive nature of the format.

There are no significant differences found when it comes to the understanding of the methods themselves. However, participants rated the case study results as slightly easier to understand. This could be due to the different levels of complexity. The difficulty of the business simulation game is also rated slightly higher than the case study, which could underline this assumption. Given the differing level of complexity of the two methods, the minor variation in terms of perceived difficulty is remarkable. The students seem to be able to handle it very well.

The biggest difference emerges when students are asked if they have learned something important and useful.

Only in terms of practical orientation does the case study score slightly better. This could be due to the fact that the scenario of the game is fictitious and works with deliberate exaggerations and simplifications, e.g. the duration of a day that lasts only one minute, and an increased pressure to act.

Overall, it can be seen that the game can compete with traditional teaching methods and in some respects it even seems superior to them. However, the differences in the quantitative data are not as high as expected based on the observation of the events and engagement during the courses.

3.2 Qualitative insights

In order to get a better feel for the actual experience of the method, open questions were included in the questionnaire. In a next step, the topics identified served as the basis for in-depth interviews (see Section 3.3 below). The qualitative approach helps to talk about the learnings in detail. The main topics of software usability, process understanding, and production planning were addressed first.

SAP user interface

Operating the real SAP S/4HANA interface was initially a challenge for some students, especially as some functionalities were available that were not essential for gameflow. At the same time, students reported quick learning effects on the platform. With a little practice, the most important moves were in place after the first few rounds. The following experience is an example of this:

“At first it was difficult to navigate. You learn over time. However, it takes time to understand and get an overview of everything.”

Process understanding

In the survey, students positively emphasized that process interrelationships within the system were easy to understand. However, there was also feedback pointing out that assigned roles within their group meant that students could only build up expertise in their own area of responsibility. So far, however, positive experiences that praise the breadth of insight have dominated.

“The individual steps made it possible to recognize a connection between the company’s internal processes. It was possible to understand the effects of decisions almost in real time and thus identify further actions. This view covered all process steps (ordering, production planning, sales, ...).”

Production planning

Many students named the procurement of materials as a major challenge in the game. Experience shows that this became easier as the game progressed, partly due to increased experience and better planning tools.

“Production planning was a key challenge in the simulation, as it requires precise coordination between demand, stock levels, and production capacities. One of the biggest challenges was to provide the right amount of material in time to avoid both overproduction and material shortages.”

Finally, the students had the opportunity to provide information on what they had learned in general as well as suggestions for improvement.

In addition to the mentioned topics, communication and teamwork emerged as key factors for success. Another focus was on the relevance of planning tools and the adaptation of individual dashboards to maintain an overview. Above all, there was a greater understanding of how complex the interdependencies of processes can be.

Finally, suggestions were made for increased learning success, such as longer gameplay with less time pressure, more interaction with other groups, and more unforeseen external events.

3.3 Interview study

To deepen the insights gained from the survey results, a qualitative component was added in line with a mixed methods design. Three students were interviewed, each of whom had participated in both the case study and the ERP simulation. This unique perspective allowed for comparative reflections on both learning formats. The interviews revealed key findings that were clustered into four thematic categories: Interaction and engagement, Learning effects and sustainability, Confidence and system familiarity, and Complexity and suggestions for improvement.

a) Experience of interaction and engagement

The interviews revealed a clear contrast in perceived engagement between the case study and ERPSim. While the case study was described as passive, ERPSim demanded active participation and focus, which led to a more immersive and motivating learning experience.

“The method of the case study didn’t seem very sophisticated to us, as if anything would stick in the long term. We were just clicking through without actively controlling the application ourselves.”

“The simulation required more concentration.”

“ERPSim was much more engaging. During the case study, no one was eagerly looking at their laptop – more like eagerly watching the clock.”

Perceived learning effects

ERPsim was perceived as a more effective and lasting learning method. The hands-on nature of the simulation, combined with trial-and-error experiences, helped students internalize complex processes, apply theoretical knowledge, and better understand the system's structure and relevance.

"At the beginning, we were overwhelmed. [...] But then the learning curve became much steeper, as we had to actively figure out where to find things in SAP."

"ERPsim is more sustainable. You definitely retain more."

"What you learn through ERPsim: coordination of complex processes, teamwork, and transfer. The simulation helped transferring lecture knowledge into practice. I now also better understand the relevance of certain things we learned in theory before."

"I often clicked on things I didn't mean to. But because of that, I now know the interface better than I would have if those mistakes hadn't happened."

Increase in confidence

Participants reported a significant increase in confidence in working with SAP after using ERPsim. The simulation helped to reduce initial fears and created a sense of familiarity that made the idea of using SAP in a professional context feel more approachable.

"After the case study, I wouldn't have said I had any idea about SAP. ERPsim helped take away some of that fear. If a job description said I had to work with SAP, I'd be okay with it now because I roughly know how it works."

Teaching suggestions

Students offered constructive feedback on how to optimize the ERPsim experience. They suggested shortening the duration, providing clearer guidance, and integrating background explanations.

"Three days for ERPsim is too long. The content could be covered in one and a half days."

"A better, more systematic introduction could save a lot of time."

"Tips between rounds would help, as well as background knowledge on why the system or market is reacting the way it is."

4 Limitations and Outlook

The simulation game, which is currently still in its testing phase, has received mostly positive feedback so far. Due to the positive response, the initiators are planning to apply for further funding for the project in the coming year.

If funding is secured for another year starting summer 2025, further uses of the simulation can be evaluated. The aim here is to supplement the existing questionnaire with guided interviews. These interviews offer the opportunity to gain deeper insights into the advantages and disad-

vantages of the game as well as various aspects of the learning experience in open discussions with the students.

A particular strength of the game lies in its potential for interdisciplinary collaboration. ERP systems affect many different departments within a company. It is therefore important that students from different faculties, such as the Faculty of Engineering and the Faculty of Business Administration, can work together with the system. The simulation game makes it possible to simulate and explore this interdisciplinary collaboration. Interesting research is conceivable here.

The game also offers different modes and flexible lengths of implementation that can be aligned with different learning objectives and schedules. These adaptable game modes support a wide range of didactic approaches and facilitate the integration of the game into the curriculum.

Overall, the simulation game shows great potential to yield important insights both in teaching and in interdisciplinary research.

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Siegfried G. Zürn & Barbara Holzner

A Systems Thinking Simulation Game Based on the Impactation Method: StarsEngines

Abstract

The StarsEngines simulation game represents a state-of-the-art approach to project management education. Integrating systems thinking and the impactation® Method, StarsEngines immerses participants in realistic scenarios where they engage in collaborative problem-solving and adaptive decision-making. This experiential learning tool enables participants with essential skills to manage the complexities of modern projects. By fostering systems thinking, teamwork, communication, and strategic foresight, the game enhances critical competencies needed for success in real-world project environments. Applications in academic courses at several universities have shown remarkable results, with participants reporting improved understanding of project interdependencies, decision-making under pressure, and reflective learning.

Designed with flexibility, the underlying structure and simulation mechanics of StarsEngines support the transfer across various industries and project contexts, including manufacturing, IT, and service sectors. Its modifiable and customizable scenarios ensure relevance to diverse educational and professional settings. Ongoing adaptations for agricultural business projects and health management projects further demonstrate the simulation's versatility.

With potential use in academic teaching, corporate training, and interdisciplinary team development, StarsEngines and its derivatives could become a cornerstone of innovative project management education, bridging project management learning with systemic thinking and professional practice.

Keywords: Project management, Systems thinking, Simulation-based learning, Experiential education, Collaborative problem-solving.

1 Introduction

Modern project management education increasingly emphasizes experiential learning tools to prepare professionals for the VUCA (Volatile, Uncertain, Complex, Ambiguous) world, where technical, organizational, and social dimensions intersect in intricate ways to simulate real-world complexity (Arnold & Wade, 2015). Hence, StarsEngines is introduced as a simulation game built on a systems thinking approach using the impactation® Method to provide an immersive environment for learners. The game's overarching objectives include developing participants' strategic and operational competencies, promoting deep insights into project interdependencies, and enhancing decision-making under uncertainty. Typically designed for 4–8 participants and lasting between 120 and 180 minutes, StarsEngines also incorporates debriefing sessions to consolidate learning. Developed as a project at Hochschule Esslingen, its unmodified use is free for public education institutions and its flexible format allows it to be played face-to-face, fully online, or in hybrid settings.

1.1 The complexity of projects

Effective project management today demands more than traditional approaches, requiring professionals to adapt to complex systems characterized by an intertwining of technical, organizational, and social dimensions. Modern projects operate with interdependent components and external influences, making strong planning, communication, and technical skills essential for navigating challenges such as resource constraints, cultural diversity, and unforeseen disruptions. Bakhshi et al. (2016) identify key dimensions of project complexity, including context, diversity, and connectivity, underscoring the intricate interplay of project elements.

Figure 1. Complexity of Complexities Paradigm according to Maurer (2017).

Similarly, Morcov et al. (2020) stress the importance of managing both beneficial and adverse complexities, advocating strategies to enhance strengths while mitigating risks. These insights emphasize the need for project managers to combine technical proficiency with strategic and interpersonal skills to address the demands of modern projects. The accelerating pace of globalization and technological advancement further amplifies these challenges, forcing organizations to adapt and innovate. Success now depends on the ability to balance the complexity of competing priorities, anticipate ripple effects, and foster team collaboration (see Figure 1).

1.2 Training to manage complex projects

Recognizing that project environments function as complex systems, educational approaches rooted in systems thinking and gaming simulation have a long tradition. Pioneering works by Duke (1974) and Greenblat (1988) established foundational principles for using simulations and highlight system interdependencies and feedback loops. Their contributions illustrated how interactive gaming can facilitate deeper learning about systemic complexity. This perspective res-

onates strongly with modern project management challenges, immersing learners in realistic project scenarios where they can practice critical skills such as resource allocation, risk management, and stakeholder communication.

The simulation model used for StarsEngines, developed at Hochschule Esslingen, builds on these foundations, introducing an interactive and cooperative approach to project management training. Importantly, its design reflects the systems-oriented modeling tradition that has been central to many simulation games in the ISAGA community. By connecting well-established systems thinking concepts with modern project management frameworks, it demonstrates how the legacy of systems sciences and gaming can be updated for contemporary educational needs.

A defining feature of the design was the use of the impactation® Method, a goal-oriented systems thinking approach. By simulating events and actions within interconnected systems, the model enables learners to understand the broader impact of their decisions. This holistic approach emphasizes not just the “what” of project management but also the “how” and “why”, as it integrates the ICB4 competencies (IPMA, 2015), thus fostering the development of critical skills such as adaptive thinking and strategic foresight (Drews et al., 2021).

By way of its dynamic scenarios, participants engage in decision-making processes that highlight how project success is dependent on the interplay of technical, planning, and communication elements (Zürn & Brunner, 2021). In this way, the simulation provides a safe yet challenging environment for experiential learning. Its innovative design supports the training of future-ready project managers equipped to handle the complexities of global and technical projects effectively. This paper explores the methodological and didactical focus and practical applications of the simulation model used in combination with the StarsEngines case scenario, underlining its value in project management education and training.

2 Methodology

Effective project management in today’s dynamic environments requires a robust understanding of complex systems and the ability to navigate their interdependencies in practice. Systems thinking emphasizes understanding the feedback loops within systems rather than focusing solely on isolated elements. This perspective is deeply rooted in the early work of systems sciences, exemplified by Forrester’s system dynamics (Forrester, 1961) and the later contributions by Meadows (2008). This approach is particularly relevant in project management due to its ability to model complexity, as large projects often operate as systems comprising technical, organizational, and social elements that interact in unpredictable ways. By mapping these interactions, systems thinking allows for the identification of leverage points – key areas where targeted actions can produce significant improvements (Ison et al., 2018). It provides a holistic framework for decision-making by enabling project managers to anticipate how changes in one component might ripple through the entire system.

Building on systems thinking principles, the impactation® Method offers a structured, four-phase approach for tackling project complexities.

1. Clarify stakeholder expectations & objectives. This is where teams identify critical success factors and begin aligning multiple viewpoints. Although such clarification can seem like

standard project practice, the impactation® Method frames it as an explicit “system boundary” exercise that maps out possible feedback loops among stakeholders.

2. Map interdependencies & model system dynamics. Teams work collaboratively to evaluate causal links, resource flows, and potential bottlenecks.
3. Explore potential scenarios & implement adaptive strategies. Guided by a system-based model, teams simulate “what-if” scenarios, thereby anticipating risks or unintended consequences. This includes selecting game actions or “measures” that strategically address identified pressure points.
4. Reflect, learn & iterate. Frequent debriefing cycles between gameplay phases enable participants to evaluate the outcomes of their actions, adjust strategies, and refine their models based on new insights. By emphasizing iterative learning, the method acknowledges that large-scale projects rarely follow a linear path.

Its strong focus on bridging the gap between strategic and operational perspectives enables us to develop a holistic view of projects, thus making it particularly effective for project management education (iCONDU, n.d.). The building elements of the impactation® model can be grouped into four areas (see Figure 2). In line with the systems-oriented modeling tradition, each phase encourages participants to consider how local changes might have system-wide consequences – an insight similarly underscored by Klabbers (2009) in designing effective simulation games.

The StarsEngines simulation game, developed at Hochschule Esslingen, is built on the impactation® Method and creates an immersive learning environment where participants address realistic project challenges. By embedding the method’s principles into the gameplay, StarsEngines fosters systems thinking, collaboration, and decision-making under uncertainty. Participants clarify objectives, simulate potential actions, and evaluate their systemic impact, effectively bridging theory and practice in project management education.

Figure 2. impactation® Framework (iCONDU, n.d.).

3 The Case: StarsEngines

The fictional business case StarsEngines exemplifies the complexities of managing high-stakes technology projects in a dynamic and resource-constrained environment. It describes an ambitious R&D project to manufacture a hybrid engine control unit for a major automotive OEM. StarsEngines's goal is not only the successful development of the control unit. The project offers a unique opportunity for StarsEngines to demonstrate its capabilities and to become a competitive provider in cutting-edge technology.

3.1 Project context

The project represents uncharted territory for StarsEngines. Despite its expertise in control unit design, the new hybrid technology has not been tested at scale. The CEO has entrusted overall project management to a promising project lead who must balance technical challenges with organizational demands. The goal is to deliver a fully functioning control unit that meets high expectations for quality and innovation within 12 months.

3.2 Team and resources

The project team is a diverse mix of experienced professionals and highly motivated graduates, but only few have prior experience with the new technology. The initial team includes the project manager, a technical co-project lead, and eight employees working within their respective departments but dedicated to project priorities. Additional contract workers can be hired, but their costs must be managed within the existing budget. The allocated budget of 950,000 credits covers all staff and resources.

3.3 Challenges and constraints

The project faces significant challenges, including the untested hybrid control unit technology, which dictates a steep learning curve for the team. Adding complexity, the OEM recently underwent a major restructuring, leaving gaps in communication and clarity due to role changes. Furthermore, the budget and timeline leave little room for error, requiring exceptional planning, adaptability, and efficient use of resources.

3.4 Project management goals

The project manager is responsible for achieving the three critical project goals: delivering a high-quality product, staying within budget, and completing the project on time. Balancing these objectives amidst technical and organizational challenges requires innovative solutions and effective leadership, ensuring the project meets its ambitious targets.

4 Simulation Game Design

Simulation games are a proven tool for experiential learning, enabling participants to engage with complex, real-world scenarios in a structured and controlled environment. In project management training, such games help learners to develop critical skills such as decision-making, resource management, and adaptability, while also fostering a deeper understanding of sys-

temic interdependencies (Rumeser & Emsley, 2019). These findings illustrate the necessity for project managers to develop a comprehensive skillset that encompasses technical proficiency, strategic planning, and effective communication in order to successfully navigate the complexities inherent in modern projects.

The StarsEngines design offers a rich, immersive environment where participants can engage with project complexities and develop competencies that are critical for success in real-world management scenarios. By combining systems thinking, collaborative problem-solving, and scenario-based learning, the game prepares learners to navigate uncertainty and achieve project goals effectively. The following key principles and structural features are at the heart of this learning experience, based on systems thinking principles of the impactation® Method.

4.1 Key design principles

- **Realistic scenario:** The game is designed to simulate authentic challenges that occur in technical and organizational project environments. Through a combination of predefined and conditional events, participants simulate potential outcomes of various strategies. This feature enables them to anticipate risks, evaluate alternatives, and refine their decision-making while faced with standard tasks such as allocating resources, meeting stakeholder expectations, and coping with unforeseen interruptions.
- **impactation® approach:** Drawing from the principles of the impactation® Method, players have to progress in two areas – Competencies and skills, and Processes, methods, tools, and organization – to secure the Project result in order to achieve the desired Impact.
- **Systems thinking:** A fundamental element of the concept is its focus on interdependencies within the project system. The players have to analyze how decisions in one area influence results across the entire system and thus work towards a holistic understanding of the project dynamics.
- **Collaborative gameplay:** The simulation favors teamwork and expects players to work together towards a specific goal. This approach encourages the development of communication, coordination, and problem-solving skills within the team.
- **Iterative learning:** By structuring the game into several rounds, participants have the opportunity to refine their strategies and adapt them to changing conditions. This iterative process promotes continuous improvement and resilience.

4.2 Structural features

- **Objective-based challenges:** The players are tasked with achieving certain project goals, e.g. adherence to the budget, satisfaction of those involved, and optimization of the use of resources. These goals evolve over the course of the game based on previous decisions and reflect real-life project conditions.
- **Dynamic events:** The inclusion of scenario-based events such as technical setbacks, conflicts between interest groups, or resource scarcity leads to unpredictability in the course of the project. This dynamic element requires participants to remain flexible and effectively balance competing priorities.

- Action and impact analysis: Participants choose from a series of predefined actions, each with potential consequences. Not all consequences are obvious, so players also need to recognize them indirectly. This gameplay element encourages players to weigh up short-term benefits against long-term consequences and thus develop strategic foresight and risk management skills.
- Interconnected decisions: Players explore the connections and feedback loops between different project elements, identifying key leverage points where actions can drive significant improvements. The measures taken by the stakeholders in return influence several aspects of the project system. For example, prioritizing team training can improve performance but reduce the resources available for other tasks. The interplay of these decisions helps participants to understand cause-and-effect relationships within the system.

5 Application of the StarsEngines Game in Teaching

The StarsEngines simulation game has been implemented in various educational settings to provide students with a hands-on, experiential learning opportunity in project management. By embedding systems thinking and real-world dynamics in a controlled environment, the game offers students a practical platform to apply theoretical knowledge, explore decision-making strategies, and understand the complexities of managing a project.

5.1 *Gameplay in curricular practice*

In academic courses, such as those in vehicle technology and systems engineering, StarsEngines has been integrated into project management and scientific methods curricula. Students are introduced to the simulation through a briefing session where the case is presented in a short video supported by AI. This allows for a highly motivating, short, and efficient presentation of the company, the framework conditions, and challenges.

General simulation setup

Each participant works within a small group, replicating the team-based structure typical of real-world projects. The game is structured into 12 rounds, with participants addressing challenges such as resource constraints, dynamic stakeholder requirements, and unexpected events. Participants are tasked with selecting from more than 30 different measures to achieve predefined goals linked to 12 project elements (see Figure 3).

This structure ensures that no two simulations are identical, underlining the importance of adaptability and critical thinking. The timeline and complexity of the simulation are adjustable, with durations ranging from 60 to 180 minutes, making it suitable for diverse teaching contexts.

Figure 3. Overall View of StarsEngines With 12 Elements and Interconnections Based on the impactation® Framework (Screenshot of the Initial View of the Simulation).

Events and Actions

The StarsEngines simulation implements a dynamic interplay of events and actions modeled on the principles of systems thinking and scenario-based learning. Various events (an example is shown in Figure 4), which occur based on element status, prior actions, and to a minor degree on chance, expose the participants to real-world project dynamics. Events are designed to reflect the complexity of project environments, including resource bottlenecks, shifts in stakeholder priorities, and unforeseen technical challenges. The effects of an event can be hidden or made visible to adjust the level of difficulty to the participants' experience and previous training.

Figure 4. Example of an Event (Screenshot of a Simulation Run).

Figure 5. Example of an Action (Screenshot of a Simulation Run).

Participants can respond through a diverse set of actions (see Figure 5 for an example), ranging from operational adjustments, such as reallocating tasks, to strategic decisions like revising project timelines or introducing additional resources. Especially, encountering conditional events triggered by their prior decisions immerses learners into situations requiring strategic foresight and immediate problem-solving at the same moment. This interactive approach fosters critical thinking and adaptive management skills. The level of difficulty can be adjusted by either showing the participants the potential effects of their actions or by having them gauge the effects on their own.

Analysis and debriefing

The analysis phase in StarsEngines combines system-driven metrics with participant-led evaluations. System-driven analysis tracks KPIs, e.g. resource utilization and goals such as customer satisfaction or project result, providing an assessment of the impacts on the project as a system. Participants engage with these metrics via dashboards that visualize trends and comparative analyses (see Figure 6).

Given the critical importance of debriefing for learning, StarsEngines integrates both in-game and post-game debriefing sessions. During gameplay, short qualitative analysis after each round invite participants to reflect on system metrics, discuss alternative strategies, and propose immediate course corrections.

After the simulation concludes, a longer debriefing session is conducted, often facilitated by an instructor or game-master trained in debriefing techniques (see, e.g., Crookall, 2023).

At the end of the simulation, an in-depth team debriefing gives students the possibility to discuss their experiences, challenges faced, and strategies employed during the game – a key for learning motivation (Bilgin et al., 2015). Teachers/facilitators should guide these discussions to connect the simulation game activities with the learning objectives. Incorporating feedback

mechanisms allows students to critically assess their performance and identify areas for improvement.

Figure 6. Example of an Evaluation Dashboard (Screenshot of a Simulation Run).

5.2 Learning outcomes and findings

The outcomes of using StarsEngines in student classes have been overwhelmingly positive. Students report enhanced understanding of systems thinking and project dynamics, and of the impact of project decisions in particular. The game enables them to see the impacts of their choices, fostering a deeper appreciation for planning, communication, and strategic foresight.

The feedback from participants in Bachelor Programs at three applied sciences universities across Germany – Esslingen University (class-room sessions), Ostfalia University (hybrid sessions), and Konstanz University (online-only sessions) – as well as MBA programs at Esslingen University and Peradeniya University, Sri Lanka (both classroom sessions) highlighted specific key insights:

- Systems thinking: Systems thinking in project management gamification helps to understand how decisions in one area impact the entire project and see the “bigger picture”. Students saw it as an engaging way to develop problem-solving skills and prepare for managing real-world complexities.
- Decision-making under pressure: The simulated environment with its tight budgets and timelines provided a realistic sense of the pressures faced by project managers. Students found that these constraints heightened their focus and decision-making accuracy.
- Critical reflection: After the simulation, students engaged in structured debriefings where they analyzed the outcomes of their decisions. Many expressed a newfound awareness of the importance of balancing technical achievements with team well-being and stakeholder satisfaction.

- Team dynamics: The collaborative nature of the game encouraged improved communication and teamwork. Students recognized the importance of balancing individual responsibilities with collective goals.

In the evaluations, more than 70 percent of students stated that they had never participated in a simulation-based learning activity, but almost all respondents were strongly in favor of including it in academic courses (Zürn & Brunner, 2021). The simulation was recognized as promoting self-discipline, collaboration, and the necessary change of perspective – qualities that are highly valued in professional project management. Although the overall response was positive, some students suggested that a longer simulation period with several review phases and additional theoretical input during the game could further improve learning success.

6 Conclusion and Outlook

With its innovative approach to project management education, StarsEngines bridges the gap between classroom learning and professional practice. By engaging with realistic scenarios and leveraging collaborative problem-solving, students gain valuable insights into the complexities of managing real-world projects. It is recognized as an effective methodology for enhancing management education, offering learners the opportunity to apply theoretical concepts in practical settings, in accordance with the findings of Zwikael et al. (2012).

The integration of systems thinking and the impactation® Method into StarsEngines fosters a comprehensive understanding of project interdependencies, enhancing decision-making and strategic foresight. Feedback from student classes highlights the simulation's ability to improve teamwork, communication, and adaptability – essential competencies for modern project managers. Moreover, the simulation's emphasis on iterative learning and scenario exploration prepares participants to navigate uncertainty and respond effectively to changing conditions.

Looking ahead, StarsEngines demonstrates strong adaptability across industries, settings, and project management tasks, making it a versatile tool for both education and professional development. Its flexibility allows customization to address specific challenges in sectors such as manufacturing, IT, or services, enabling tailored learning outcomes that support interdisciplinary collaboration and specialized training. The simulation's flexible design has already been seen in the ConnectRollout simulation (Zürn & Dias-Costa, 2023) that is rooted in the same methodology and principles that guided the development of StarsEngines. Further modifications for specific applications are already underway; for instance, adaptations for agricultural business projects in collaboration with Peradeniya University and health management projects with Zürich University of Applied Sciences are in progress. These initiatives highlight the potential of such simulations to address unique challenges across different sectors, fostering relevant skills and broadening the reach of experiential learning.

By continuously evolving and offering customizable scenarios, StarsEngines ensures that learners and professionals alike benefit from a robust and practical project management tool. This forward-looking approach not only enriches project management education, it also positions StarsEngines as a catalyst for innovative practices in a variety of fields, bridging the ever-present gap between knowledge and actual implementation.

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Chapter

Methods, Tools & Applied Practices

Maria Lorena Flórez Rojas

“You Are Hired!” A Simulation Game for Experiential Learning in Legal Technology

Abstract

This paper presents an experience report on the implementation of “You Are Hired!”, a simulation game designed to provide hands-on, experiential learning in the field of legal technology. Developed as a core component of the Legal Technology Challenges master class that is part of the Technology, Law and Innovation program at Groningen University, the game simulates a real-world consultancy environment with real Dutch organizations. Through challenge-based learning, students engage in practical tasks such as preparing advisory reports and presenting their findings. The simulation emphasizes the importance of effective communication, interdisciplinary collaboration, and the application of legal and technical knowledge. Feedback from students indicates that the game not only enhanced their understanding of complex regulatory frameworks but also improved their professional skills, including team collaboration and client interaction. The paper discusses the game’s design, key learning outcomes, and the integration of gamification elements – such as a badge system and a leaderboard – to foster motivation and engagement. Additionally, the paper outlines best practices for incorporating simulation-based learning in academic programs, offering practical guidance for educators aiming to bridge theory with real-world practice in legal technology education.

Keywords: Experiential learning, Legal education, Simulation game, Challenge-based learning, Technology.

1 Introduction

Legal professionals need more than just deep legal knowledge – they must also develop practical skills, technological literacy, and the ability to collaborate across disciplines (Pistone, 2022). The increasing role of automation, and digital decision-making in the legal field is reshaping the expectations placed on lawyers. As highlighted by Connor, modern legal professionals must go beyond traditional legal expertise and integrate skills such as creativity, innovation, and strategic thinking into their practice (2020). In this regard, the rise of new technologies – accelerated by the pandemic – has significantly transformed legal education, professional training, and legal practice. As a result, the competencies required for future lawyers now extend beyond traditional legal knowledge to include a combination of legal, business, and personal development skills (Graben, 2021).

Unfortunately, most of the competencies required for modern legal practice are not reflected in undergraduate law curricula (Edwards, 1992). This gap makes it essential for future lawyers to complement their education through specialized programs that allow them to adapt their training to the demands of the legal market. Lawyers who develop interdisciplinary skills – including legal-tech proficiency, business intelligence, and communication strategies – will have

greater career opportunities and a distinct advantage over colleagues with traditional legal training (Toohey et al., 2022).

To address these professional demands, this paper presents the "You Are Hired!" simulation game, an experiential learning tool implemented in the Legal Technology Challenges master class at the University of Groningen. The game is designed to equip Master's law students with practical problem-solving skills, real-world communication abilities, and hands-on experience working with Dutch organizations. By integrating challenge-based learning and gamification, the simulation replicates a consultancy environment where students must navigate complex legal and technological issues, collaborate with industry professionals, and present strategic solutions.

The "You Are Hired!" simulation is designed in alignment with modern legal education models, emphasizing interdisciplinary learning, adaptability, and client-centered legal practice. The aim of the paper is to show that this practice – experiential learning through simulation games such as "You Are Hired!" – effectively improves law students' communication skills and professional engagement with industry stakeholders, particularly in international and technology-driven legal environments. The paper is structured as follows: First, the methodology section will describe the theoretical foundation of the simulation, drawing on various models for future lawyers and the learning outcomes of the master class. Next, the design process will be described, detailing the need for such a course, the conceptualization of the idea, and the iterative improvements made. Following this, the paper will present initial results from the first cohort, highlighting student feedback and adjustments introduced based on evaluation reports and participant reflections. Finally, the conclusion and recommendations section will discuss how integrating more practical training into legal education, even at the undergraduate level, could help legal educators address emerging challenges such as the integration of generative AI in legal practice.

2 Methodology

The Experiential Challenge-Based Gamified Learning (ECGL) methodology combines experiential learning, challenge-based learning, and gamification to create an interactive and practice-oriented educational experience (Gallagher & Savage, 2023). In the "You Are Hired!" simulation, students engage in real-world legal advisory roles, tackling authentic legal-tech challenges presented by industry partners. The challenge-based structure encourages students to analyze legal and technological issues, propose strategic solutions, and present their findings in a professional environment. Through gamification mechanics such as badges, leaderboards, and structured feedback loops, the simulation fosters motivation, engagement, and continuous skill development (Erenli, 2015). By integrating legal expertise, interdisciplinary collaboration, and real-time problem-solving, ECGL provides a dynamic learning framework that bridges the gap between legal theory and professional practice, preparing students for the evolving demands of legal-tech professions.

2.1 Skills and mindset for the future tech-driven lawyer

Legal departments and law firms now require lawyers to engage in project management, business analysis, and risk prevention – tasks that were once seen as the domain of engineers and business professionals (Toohey et al., 2022). Connor updated the T-Shaped Lawyer model, emphasizing the need for lawyers to adapt to new technologies and be flexible in different work environments. Both in literature and in practice, various models attempt to describe the competencies required of the lawyer of the future (Drapezo et al., 2022; Koruts et al., 2020). According to Connor and Smathers, traditional legal education produces "I-shaped" lawyers, who hold deep legal knowledge but lack interdisciplinary skills (Smathers, 2014). They propose an alternative, the T-shaped lawyer, where the vertical bar represents expertise in law, while the horizontal bar extends into non-legal competencies crucial for modern legal practice, such as non-legal skills, teamwork, and communication.

Beyond the T-shape model, Dan Kayne, General Counsel for Network Rail UK, introduced the O-shaped lawyer model (Kayne, 2021). This framework aims to create more well-rounded lawyers, focusing on competencies beyond technical legal skills. In 2020, Kayne brought together a significant working group across the UK legal profession to launch the "O-Shaped Lawyer" program. Its goal is to demonstrate that by placing greater emphasis on a more holistic approach to legal education, the profession can provide better service to clients while fostering a more diverse, inclusive, and sustainable legal industry (Kayne, 2021).

In 2019, a group of academics in the US conducted empirical studies confirming the critical need for lawyers to develop non-legal skills and competencies (Moon, 2024; Runyon & Carrel, 2019). They formed a working group to create a competency model applicable to anyone in the legal ecosystem, regardless of role or career stage. This led to the development of the Delta Model, which builds on the T-shaped concept (Carrel & Moon, 2021). Though still evolving, the Delta Model introduces three key dimensions (Figure 1): i) Practice, which encompasses legal expertise, research, analysis, and writing; ii) Process, which includes business fundamentals, project management, and data analytics; and iii) Personal effectiveness, which focuses on relationship management, an entrepreneurial mindset, emotional intelligence, communication, and character.

The "You Are Hired!" simulation was built on the Delta Model, embracing its three-dimensional skill framework, as it not only strengthens legal expertise but also enhances process-oriented and interpersonal skills. By integrating gamification mechanics – such as leaderboards, structured feedback, and team-based challenges – students are encouraged to develop personal effectiveness while navigating realistic legal-tech scenarios. This approach ensures that law students move beyond theoretical knowledge and develop practical, adaptable competencies that reflect the evolving legal industry.

Although the Delta, T-shaped, and O-shaped models offer different perspectives on legal education and professional development, they share a common goal: to shift legal training beyond pure legal doctrine to include business, technological, and personal development skills (Connor, 2020). Ultimately, what matters is not which framework is superior, but how effectively it meets the objectives of legal education and professional training. Whether a law student seeks to improve specific skills or undergo a complete professional transformation, structured methodologies such as those embedded in the "You Are Hired!" simulation can provide targeted devel-

opment opportunities. The future of legal education lies in creating programs that not only embrace digital transformation but also facilitate human transformation. By incorporating experiential, challenge-based, and gamified learning approaches, we can ensure that the lawyers of the future are not just legal experts but also strategic thinkers, problem solvers, and adaptable professionals ready to navigate the evolving legal landscape (Toohey et al., 2022; Erenli, 2015).

Figure 1. “The Delta Model combinations” by Caitlin Moon (Moon, 2024).

2.2 Aligning the learning framework with the master class objectives

The Legal Technology Challenges master class is designed to equip students with practical knowledge and interdisciplinary skills essential for modern legal practice. This course builds on the legal training students receive in their Bachelor’s programs and the first semester of their Master’s studies, and moves beyond traditional legal education by creating an immersive learning environment that integrates legal expertise, business intelligence, and interpersonal effectiveness.

A key feature of this course is its diverse student body, composed of individuals from different social and cultural backgrounds, many of whom are international students unfamiliar with the Dutch legal and business landscape. This diversity brings a unique perspective to legal problem-solving, making the simulation more than just an academic exercise – it becomes a real-world application of cross-cultural legal practice, where students must adapt, collaborate, and effectively communicate across legal traditions and professional expectations.

The second key objective is enhancing communication skills. The simulation requires students to prepare client reports, deliver legal-tech recommendations, and present findings to industry professionals. This aspect is emphasized in the Delta Model, which provides a structured approach to interpersonal development by integrating relationship management, emotional intel-

ligence, and entrepreneurial thinking into the learning process. Since students come from different legal and cultural backgrounds, effective communication and adaptability are not just desired skills but essential components of their success in this course.

Finally, the course encourages international students' engagement with Dutch organizations, a distinctive feature that sets this master class apart from conventional legal-tech courses. By collaborating with industry stakeholders, students gain firsthand exposure to the European legal-tech landscape, learning how to navigate cross-border legal challenges and regulatory differences. This experiential approach aligns with the Delta Model, which prioritizes professional adaptability and the ability to integrate into different legal and business environments. The simulation ensures that students not only learn about technology and law but also actively apply their knowledge in diverse, international settings in preparation for global careers.

2.3 Gamification as a learning catalyst

The "You Are Hired!" simulation goes beyond traditional legal education by incorporating gamification principles to enhance student engagement. Gamification involves applying game mechanics to learning environments, making complex legal challenges more interactive, competitive, and rewarding (Erenli, 2015). In the "You Are Hired!" simulation, students are placed in highly immersive, scenario-based environments where they take on professional roles, respond to legal-tech challenges, and compete in client advisory tasks, all within a structured game-based framework.

The simulation applies two primary forms of gamification to enhance the learning process. Structural gamification is embedded in the course design, using leaderboards, badge systems, and milestone achievements to track progress and reward participation (Serice, 2023). These elements encourage students to actively engage with the content, ensuring they remain motivated to complete assignments, refine their analytical skills, and improve their performance over time (Yuratich, 2021; Lillo & Burelli, 2021). The competitive aspect of leaderboards fosters healthy competition, pushing students to strive for excellence while reinforcing key legal concepts through continuous engagement.

Beyond structural elements, the simulation also incorporates content-based gamification, which immerses students in realistic, scenario-driven challenges. Instead of passively learning legal principles, students assume professional roles, simulate real-world advisory tasks, and navigate legal-tech issues in a consultancy-style setting (Aprea & Ifenthaler, 2021). This practical application of legal knowledge enhances critical thinking, problem-solving, and adaptability, all of which are essential for future legal professionals working in an increasingly technology-driven legal landscape.

Gamification in legal education has been recognized for its ability to transform passive learning into an active, engaging experience (Yuratich, 2021). By framing legal challenges as interactive experiences, gamification helps students internalize complex regulatory frameworks, governance principles, and technology law issues more effectively. The feedback and peer-review mechanisms incorporated into the game allow students to assess their performance after every challenge, make necessary adjustments, and develop a strategic approach to legal problem-solving.

Thus, by integrating gamification, experiential learning, and interdisciplinary collaboration, the “You Are Hired!” simulation offers a transformative approach to legal education. Rather than simply memorizing legal doctrines, students apply their knowledge in dynamic, high-pressure scenarios, in preparation for the complexities of modern legal practice (Flórez Rojas, 2023). This methodology not only improves learning retention and adaptability but also helps law students build the professional competencies needed to navigate the legal-tech industry and engage effectively with industry stakeholders.

3 Design Process of the “You Are Hired!” Simulation

The design process was structured to gradually immerse students in real-world legal consultancy scenarios, mirroring the interdisciplinary nature of modern legal practice.

3.1 Conceptualization of the “You Are Hired!” simulation

The simulation was conceptualized as a progressive, hands-on legal advisory experience that follows a structured timeline combining preparatory training, client interaction, independent work, and iterative feedback loops. However, beyond its academic structure, the simulation was also designed with mobility and professional immersion in mind, given Groningen’s favourable geographical position which offers students a unique opportunity to travel across the Netherlands and engage directly with stakeholders.

The master class was specifically structured to encourage students to step outside the classroom and experience the Dutch legal-tech ecosystem firsthand. Recognizing that modern legal professionals must be adaptable and globally minded, the course integrates travel and direct engagement with industry leaders as a fundamental learning component (Aprea & Ifenthaler, 2021). By exposing students to real-world legal and technological challenges in diverse professional settings, the program ensures that they gain practical experience in different legal environments while building a professional network that extends beyond the university.

To achieve this nationwide engagement, the program coordinator partners with key industry stakeholders from various regions of the Netherlands, ensuring that students collaborate with diverse organizations. Each partnership is tailored to create a meaningful learning experience where students are challenged to apply their knowledge to real industry needs. The process begins early, with the coordinator working closely with partner organizations to co-develop industry-relevant legal challenges that reflect the current technological and regulatory landscape. These partnerships ensure that students are not only confronted with practical legal issues but can also observe, analyze, and contribute to the decision-making processes of major legal-tech players in the Netherlands. The following table lists some of the main industry partners that have collaborated with past master classes, reflecting the breadth of professional engagement and the geographical diversity of the program’s stakeholder network.

Table 1. Master class partnerships 2023–2025.

Partner	Type of stakeholder	Type of challenge
RDW (Rijksdienst voor het Wegverkeer)	Public body: Organization that handles the registration of motorized vehicles and driving licenses in the Netherlands	2023–2024: Implications of the future AI Act 2024–2025: Regulatory framework for remote operators of connected & automated vehicles (CAVs)
DPA (Over de Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens)	Supervisory Authority	2023–2024: International transfers for international organizations 2024–2025: Political advertising on social media platforms
Deloitte	Law firm (industry)	2023–2025: Health Tech law and cybersecurity issues
Bits of Freedom	Civil society	2023–2024: Freedom of Information requests
Meta	Technology company (industry)	Digital Service Act and Meta ad products
Microsoft	Technology company (industry)	2024–2025: Integrating Zero Trust methodology with regulatory compliance

The opportunity to travel, engage with experts, and immerse themselves in different legal ecosystems across the Netherlands makes this master class a pioneering initiative in legal education, one that prepares students for the realities of modern legal practice far beyond the classroom.

3.2 Core elements of the program

Crash course week

The program begins with an intensive one-week crash course equipping students with essential professional skills such as time management, communication techniques, and research methodologies. This preparatory phase ensures that students – especially those coming from diverse cultural and academic backgrounds – are equipped with the necessary tools to engage confidently and effectively with industry partners.

A key aspect of this initial stage is the introduction to the simulation game structure, where students learn the rules of the game and the expectations regarding their participation. The first session is dedicated to team-building and self-assessment, where students are introduced to the Hexad Player Type Model, a framework that categorizes different gaming personalities based on motivation and engagement (Sipone et al., 2025). This exercise helps students understand their own role within the game and how their personal strengths can contribute to team dynamics, whether as achievers, socializers, disruptors, or strategists.

The second session focuses on gamification mechanics, where students are introduced to the different types of badges they can earn and how their performance will be evaluated throughout the game (Figure 2). This session also establishes the internal communication framework, which is a crucial part of the simulation. Students are introduced to *Slack* as the primary com-

munication platform, both within their teams and with the coordinator (who acts as the "employer" in the simulation). The use of Slack ensures that students develop professional communication habits that mirror real-world corporate environments, where internal messaging platforms play a key role in team collaboration and project management.

A major component of the crash course week is the initial communication training session, which is designed to prepare students for high-pressure speaking scenarios that they will encounter in client interactions. Public speaking is a fundamental skill in legal practice, and to help students overcome scenario fear and develop effective voice management, the course includes practical exercises focused on building confidence in public speaking (Ferguson, 2016; Rimanelli & Gurba, 2019). Students participate in structured activities aimed at improving clarity, composure, and persuasive delivery, which will be reinforced through two additional communication training sessions later in the program.

Figure 2. You Are Hired! badges.

Initial client meeting: Defining real-world legal challenges

This was introduced in the second cohort of the simulation in response to student feedback from the first iteration. Students emphasized the importance of having direct interaction with the client early in the process, particularly to clarify the scope of the challenge, understand expectations, and ask critical questions before beginning their research and analysis.

During this first online meeting, students are introduced to their assigned client and can discuss in detail the legal-tech challenge they were given at least 2 weeks prior to this first meeting. This meeting provides students with an opportunity to gather crucial insights, ask clarifying questions, and better understand the needs of their client, which ultimately enhances the quality and strategic relevance of their advisory work.

Autonomous research and report preparation

Students then transition into the autonomous research and report preparation phase, where they apply their legal knowledge, problem-solving abilities, and strategic thinking to develop client-oriented recommendations. While students are expected to work independently within their teams, they are also responsible for managing professional communication with their employer – the course coordinator, who acts as the supervising authority within the game. This added layer of realistic workplace dynamics teaches students how to navigate hierarchical structures, manage their time effectively, and seek guidance when necessary. Students are encouraged to proactively reach out to their "employer" for clarification, advice, or feedback, simulating the professional responsibility of consulting senior colleagues or supervisors in a real legal environment.

This phase also introduces the challenge of space management, as students must decide how and when to coordinate their research activities. While they have autonomy over their schedules, they are also expected to balance team collaboration with their own research contributions. This level of responsibility helps students develop essential project management skills, ensuring that they meet deadlines, distribute tasks effectively, and integrate multiple perspectives into a well-structured legal advisory report.

Throughout this process, the course coordinator (acting as the employer) maintains an active but non-intrusive role, overseeing research progress and providing guidance when necessary.

On-site client visits

One of the key experiential components of the simulation are the on-site visits to Dutch organizations, where students transition from theoretical analysis to real-world professional engagement. These visits serve as a critical test of their communication skills, allowing them to present their findings, defend their legal reasoning, and receive real-time feedback from industry professionals. However, the value of these visits extends far beyond public speaking; they also provide a unique opportunity to navigate professional networking, adapt to different corporate cultures, and refine interpersonal skills essential for legal practitioners working in diverse environments.

A key challenge of these visits is that not all organizations are headed by or composed of lawyers. Many of the stakeholders in these legal-tech challenges come from business, engineering, or policy backgrounds, requiring students to translate complex legal concepts into clear, actionable recommendations. This forces participants to move beyond legal jargon and develop a more natural, accessible way of communicating, ensuring that their legal expertise is understood and valued across disciplines.

In addition, the on-site visits also help students to develop their professional presence, including how to dress, act, and conduct themselves in different professional settings. Since each organization has its own culture, expectations, and corporate structure, students must quickly adapt their performance and communication style to different workplace environments.

Iterative improvement and gamification elements

After each on-site client visit, students receive immediate feedback from the organizations they present to, allowing them to gauge the effectiveness of their communication, legal reasoning, and strategic recommendations in real-time. However, the reflection and improvement process does not end there. The following week, students participate in a structured feedback session⁰ designed to provide a deeper analysis of their performance, highlight key takeaways from the challenge, and refine their approach for future client interactions (Cathcart et al., 2014).

A designated peer review team, assigned at the beginning of the course to each challenge, plays a crucial role in this process. This team analyses the presentations given during the visit, identifying each team's strong points as well as areas where the presenting teams can improve their clarity, argumentation, or delivery. In addition to peer evaluations, the course coordinator (employer) takes up an active mentoring role, guiding students on how to process and respond to corporate feedback effectively.

Since corporate feedback in legal practice often requires immediate adjustments and strategic thinking, these sessions teach students how to remain adaptable under professional scrutiny. They learn how to refine their responses, adjust their communication approach, and ensure their legal arguments remain persuasive in high-pressure environments.

Additionally, gamification continues to play a vital role in reinforcing motivation and engagement. After each visit and feedback session, stakeholders award special badges to recognize outstanding performance in different skill areas, such as clear communication, strategic legal analysis, and innovative problem-solving (Flórez Rojas, 2025). Unlike the first cohort, where badges were awarded only at the end, this new system allows students to earn badges progressively throughout the game, reinforcing their growth and development at each phase.

Thus, the simulation was designed with the goal of bridging the gap between legal education and professional practice, to prepare students for the realities of working in legal-tech consultancy. Through continuous refinement based on student and stakeholder feedback, the simulation continues to evolve into an innovative, experiential learning model, setting a benchmark for how law schools can integrate hands-on, challenge-based education into their curricula.

4 Preliminary Results and Discussion

4.1 Student feedback and adjustments

The first cohort of the "You Are Hired!" simulation provided valuable insights into the program's strengths as well as areas for improvement. The feedback received from students and evaluation reports from the 2023–2024 master class highlighted key learning outcomes, engagement levels, and structural enhancements that have since been implemented. The positive reception of the course confirmed its impact on legal-tech education, particularly in enhancing real-world legal problem-solving skills and professional adaptability (Flórez Rojas, 2022).

Overall, students highly appreciated the hands-on nature of the simulation, in particular the opportunity to engage directly with industry professionals, participate in client meetings, and receive structured feedback. Many students cited the real-world applicability of the course as

one of the main reasons they chose their Master of Law program, emphasizing that the interactive nature of the master class made legal education more relevant to their future careers (Flórez Rojas, 2022).

One of the standout aspects of the program was the diversity of legal challenges presented by the breadth of partnering companies. Students found that working on a diversity of cases, each requiring distinct research and advisory skills, helped them apply their theoretical knowledge in a practical setting. Additionally, the high level of interaction with professionals allowed students to develop a deeper understanding of how legal solutions are crafted in corporate and regulatory environments.

Several participants also highlighted the comprehensive feedback mechanisms as a major strength of the course. Detailed evaluations of their reports and presentations helped them refine their legal writing, strengthen their analytical skills, and improve their oral advocacy abilities. The feedback loop from both instructors and industry stakeholders was particularly appreciated as it gave students a clear roadmap for improvement throughout the course.

4.2 Areas for improvement

While the first cohort's experience was largely positive, students and evaluators identified several areas for improvement, leading to important structural adjustments in the program.

Clarifying the game rules from the beginning

One of the most significant changes introduced after the first cohort came from the need to clearly define the rules of the simulation from the outset. Some students expressed confusion over how the game mechanics worked, particularly regarding the scoring system, performance evaluations, and team dynamics. To address this, the first week of the program was restructured to serve as a formal introduction to the game, ensuring that all participants fully understood the expectations and mechanics before engaging with the simulation.

Using the first week to establish the game framework

Initially, the first week of the course focused primarily on crash courses in legal research, communication, and time management. However, feedback from students suggested that this time could be better used to set up the game mechanics, introduce participants to their roles, and familiarize them with the competitive aspects of the simulation. As a result, the new iteration of the simulation now includes dedicated sessions in the first week to define game rules, introduce gamification elements, and allow students to familiarize themselves with the advisory process.

Developing a more dynamic leaderboard

Another key improvement was the enhancement of the leaderboard system. In the first cohort, students only received personalized performance feedback at the end of the course, which limited their ability to track progress throughout the simulation. Moving forward, the leaderboard now functions as a live ranking system where students can track their standing relative to their peers in real-time, increasing motivation and engagement.

Improving the badge system

Originally, badges were awarded as a final skill assessment tool, recognizing the competencies students gained throughout the simulation. However, feedback indicated that this system lacked visibility during the game, making it harder for students to track their development in specific areas. To improve engagement, badges are now earned at different phases of the game, allowing students to accumulate achievements over time.

The adjustments made – including clarifying game mechanics, improving the leaderboard system, restructuring the badge system, and dedicating the first week to game setup – ensure that the next iterations of the course will provide an even more engaging and structured learning experience.

4.3 Limitations of the simulation

While the "You Are Hired!" simulation has proven to be an engaging learning model, it also presents certain challenges and limitations that need to be addressed in future iterations. These challenges focus on scalability, university-level coordination, student workload, and long-term industry engagement.

Scaling the simulation: Managing larger cohorts

One of the main challenges faced in the second cohort was the increase in the number of students. The first cohort consisted of 12 students, which allowed for smaller teams of three members. This structure facilitated interactive teamwork, effective communication, and more personalized feedback from instructors and industry professionals. However, the second cohort expanded to 20 students, requiring an increase in team size. Larger teams pose coordination challenges, as ensuring equal participation, engagement, and learning opportunities becomes more complex. Additionally, providing personalized feedback to individual students becomes more challenging as the number of participants grows.

For future iterations of the simulation, it will be necessary to explore alternative game elements that can better accommodate larger cohorts while maintaining the interactive and immersive nature of the program. This could include more dynamic role distribution within teams, rotating leadership roles, or implementing new game mechanics to maintain engagement and ensure that all students benefit equally from the experience.

University-level coordination and scheduling conflicts

Another logistical challenge is the organization of travel days for students to visit partner organizations. Since these visits are critical experiential components of the simulation, it is essential to ensure that students have sufficient time to travel to different locations. However, this requires early coordination between the course coordinator and other faculty members to prevent scheduling conflicts with other academic responsibilities.

In the second cohort, some scheduling challenges arose, as students had other mandatory courses or assignments that clashed with travel days. Moving forward, ensuring better synchronization with the broader academic schedule will be essential to prevent overlapping obliga-

tions and to allow students to fully engage with their client visits without the stress of missing other academic requirements.

Balancing the workload for students doing internships

A new challenge flagged by the second cohort was the presence of students simultaneously completing an internship alongside the master class. Balancing academic coursework, client-based assignments, and professional internships created additional pressure and mental health concerns for some students. The coordination team has been monitoring the well-being of these students, ensuring that they have sufficient support and flexibility to complete their responsibilities without experiencing burnout. Future iterations of the simulation may need to establish clearer workload expectations for students pursuing internships.

5 Conclusion

The "You Are Hired!" simulation game can be considered an innovative experiential learning tool for legal education, particularly in the field of law and technology. By integrating challenge-based learning, gamification, and real-world client interaction, the course successfully bridges the gap between academic training and professional legal practice. The experiences gathered from the first cohort of students, along with feedback from industry stakeholders, have led to iterative improvements, refining the methodology and ensuring that students acquire practical, adaptable, and future-ready skills.

The success of the simulation is largely due to its alignment with evolving legal education models, particularly the Delta Model, which emphasizes legal expertise, business intelligence, and interpersonal effectiveness. The combination of theoretical learning and real-world application allows students to develop their legal reasoning skills as well as enhance their ability to communicate with professionals from diverse disciplines, adapt to different workplace environments, and navigate complex legal-tech challenges. Through gamification elements such as badges, leaderboards, and structured feedback mechanisms, the course ensures engagement and motivation, reinforcing learning outcomes in a way that is both interactive and competitive.

Feedback from students has highlighted key benefits of the program, including the hands-on nature of the learning experience, the opportunity to interact with Dutch organizations, and the structured feedback process that fosters improvement. Adjustments made after the first iteration have significantly improved the game's effectiveness and engagement levels. These refinements ensure that students not only apply legal knowledge effectively but also develop critical workplace skills such as strategic thinking, time and space management, and professional communication.

Moreover, the simulation's geographical aspect, allowing students to travel across the Netherlands and engage with diverse organizations, adds a unique and valuable dimension to legal education. The necessity for students to adjust their communication style depending on their audience – whether engaging with policymakers, engineers, business executives, or fellow legal professionals – teaches them how to make legal concepts actionable and accessible across disciplines. This is a critical skill for lawyers working in an increasingly technology-driven and globalized legal market.

Ultimately, the “You Are Hired!” simulation stands as a testament to the power of experiential legal education. By combining practical training, interdisciplinary collaboration, and innovative teaching methodologies, it not only enhances students’ understanding of legal-tech issues but also prepares them for the demands of modern legal practice. With ongoing refinements and adaptations, this approach has the potential to reshape legal education and set a new standard for integrating real-world legal experiences into academic training.

Disclosure of Interests

The author has no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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Heide Lukosch & Maria Freese

From Keynote to Keynote Action: Engaging Conference Participants by Play

Abstract

Scientific conferences historically are places for exchange of ideas, debate, and community building. Keynotes are often used to introduce a specific perspective and (sometimes thought-provoking) line of thought to set the tone of a conference. In our case, we tried something new and instead of having one well-known keynote speaker providing an inspiring yet mainly passive experience for the conference participants, we decided to use a collaborative-competitive game as a keynote action. The game we used was based on a commercial game that was tailored to the conference context. Our observations and feedback from the conference participants show that this approach provided an experience that allowed participants to quickly get to know each other, create a shared experience, and open pathways for continuing communication. We report on our ideas behind this game as well as the observations in this best practice paper.

Keywords: Keynote, Keynote action, Conference, Simulation and gaming.

Introduction

The role of scientific conferences

Scientific conferences serve as hubs for creating and maintaining scientific networks, with conference papers being one communication channel in the scientific discourse (Rowley-Jolivet, 1999), often leading to co-authored (journal) articles (Drott, 1995; Campos et al., 2018). Conferences play an important role in linking the work of a scientific group to others, showcasing its work, and they are an essential tool for scientific communication (Kochetkov et al., 2022). A case study of a marine conference showed that participants valued the conference attendance for its contributions to their own research, communication, and policy making. The conference also had an impact on their techniques, skills, and the development of novel ideas (Oester et al., 2017). Conferences enrich the scientific culture of the participants and reinforce social cohesion within the community (Rowley-Jolivet, 1999). As some researchers focus on rather narrow topics (due to the nature of their research), conferences offer an opportunity to connect with the broader scientific field and a wider intellectual network (Rowley-Jolivet, 1999). "Conferences, in other words, are a strong cement in the social cohesion of a discourse community, making it much more than a disembodied virtual reality concept" (Rowley-Jolivet, 1999, Section 12). Conferences allow for feedback on one's own research, create opportunities to build connections for future research, and play an important role in socializing young researchers (Kuzhabekova & Temerbayeva, 2018). Academic conferences usually are opened by a keynote lecture by a senior researcher or industry expert setting the tone for the conference and introducing thought-provoking topics. Yet a search for the term "keynote action" in Scopus and Web of Science returned no results. The scientific literature mentions similar activities such as ice

breakers, especially when addressing group settings and learning (e.g. Makhmudovna, 2022; Aniranti, 2021; Artati, 2021; Darmayanti et al., 2023) but not their use in conference settings. This paper aims to start a conversation and invite further research in this area.

The annual International Simulation and Gaming Association's Conference

The International Simulation and Gaming Association (ISAGA) holds yearly conferences to exchange new scientific insights as well as practical applications since its establishment in 1970. It represents a community of researchers and practitioners focusing on the development, use, and evaluation of simulation gaming as a participatory method to understand and design complex systems. Since its beginnings, ISAGA has focused on improving social and human conditions in areas of interest to the community (Klabbers, 2009), and has also engaged in debate of its underlying scientific concepts. Throughout its long history, it has been able to establish a strong core of well-connected researchers and practitioners, especially across Europe, Japan, and Australia. These individuals form a stable network maintaining the intellectual exchange and development of the field. However, other regions as well as early career researchers and new technologies are less represented and may find it daunting to connect with the core community.

In 2024, we organized the ISAGA conference in Christchurch, New Zealand, with a smaller than usual group of attendees, including several participants new to the community. We organized the conference as an in-person event only. While we are aware of the environmental impact of long-haul travel for most attendees to the venue, this was a conscious decision (and included the recording and publication of all keynotes and paper presentations after the conference). In-person meetings can better facilitate learning and do not force participants to join an online meeting at an inconvenient time because of the time difference (Kochetkov et al., 2022). An in-person event allows participants to solely focus on the event, minimizing distractions.

As we were aware of the newcomers to the community, in line with our aim to help build a strong community, we thought of ways to set the right tone for the conference from the beginning, and to foster communication and trust-building. From our own experience, we know how difficult it can be to join a close-knit community, especially for early career researchers. The ISAGA conferences usually follow a certain pattern. The conference runs for four to five days, with a conference social program on its third and a conference dinner on its fourth day. As such, events that allow for informal networking are placed rather late in the program. For this reason, we decided to place one event at the start of the conference that would allow participants to connect from the outset – a game named “Happy Dr. Octoludus”.

Happy Dr. Octoludus – A keynote action

The game Happy Dr. Octoludus was named after the ISAGA conference mascot, an Octopus, combined with the Latin word *ludus* for play. We designed this game based on a commercial game called Happy Salmon by Exploding Kittens. Our game was made for the keynote action only and is not publicly available. If readers are interested in emulating the experience, they can play and use the original game.

Design of Happy Dr. Octoludus

We set certain requirements for the game to be used in our keynote action. It would need to:

- foster communication and collaboration,
- be easy to learn and to facilitate,
- be completed within 30 minutes, including debriefing,
- include an element of physical activation,
- be an inclusive game,
- be scalable to accommodate 50–150 participants,
- be playable in groups,
- be quick to develop.

We developed five sets of cards for five groups to play together. Each set of cards contains 96 cards for a maximum of eight players, with 12 cards for each player. The goal of the game is to get rid of all cards as the first player in a group. Each card shows one action to take, and all actions require at least two players to carry out together. Cards are discarded after an action is completed. This way, the game is both collaborative (at least two players need to come together to carry out one action) as well as competitive (the fastest player wins). The cards themselves as well as the adjusted actions were developed by us, in collaboration with a graphic designer. The cards showed one or more octopus along with the title of the action to be performed by the players. Instruction material was also developed. In a pre-test with an interdisciplinary and international group, the game itself was tested, as was the facilitation of the game based on the instructional material. We added a debriefing phase as an additional element to the game that strengthened the idea of using the game for conference participants to get to know each other and build first connections.

The keynote action

At the beginning of the conference, all participants gathered in a conventional lecture hall to listen to a brief welcome address and safety/housekeeping instructions. After this, the keynote action was introduced based on the story of Dr. Octoludus, since not all participants were familiar with the mascot. Participants were asked to gather in front of the lecture hall in a communal area with enough room for safe movement. For this purpose, small icons on the participants' name tags indicated which group each participant belonged to.

This initially led to chaos, but this was intentional so that everyone had the same starting conditions. The participants were asked to raise their hand as soon as there were at least four participants in a group. That was the signal for one of the volunteers to approach the respective group with a stack of cards. The facilitators communicated the rules of the game, which include shuffling the cards for each player, flipping over the stack of cards, and starting the game by shouting out the action displayed on the top card and looking out for another player with the same card. Once at least one other player with the same action card is found, they can carry out the action together, discard that card and move on with the next card until they run out of

cards. Once the first player has discarded all their cards, they shout “Happy Dr. Octoludus” and win this round. After that, all winners were gathered and played the final round. The winner received an extra picture with the mascot of the conference as a prize.

The actual game was followed by a debriefing action and reflection phase. The debriefing action included the facilitators asking the members of their respective groups to gather again and each to perform an activity that represents the personality of the respective participant. After that, volunteers from each group were asked to present their own actions and explain the meaning behind them. A central reflection debriefing was also held to allow players to share their overall experience with the game. Pictures were taken of the winner and the conference mascot, and one group picture of all players (i.e. participants) was taken, too. After that, participants immediately enjoyed morning tea.

Observations and Insights

The game play was observed by the two authors, who did not serve as facilitators and were able to take on an outside-observer view. We observed that participants were first surprised about being asked to leave the lecture hall and engage in game play. However, the fast pace and simplicity of the game made it very easy to engage, and participants soon forgot the first anxiety of having to directly engage with unknown fellow participants. A very lively, happy atmosphere emerged, reflected in the participants’ shouting and carrying out actions in their respective groups. The aim of the game is for one player to be the first to play all their cards, thereby winning the game. This competitive character led to a very distinct dynamic. The authors observed that players felt the pressure to be the first to discard all cards, judging by their hectic shouting and acting. Even though it was a relatively short game, there was a recognizable game flow. All players were immersed in the game and no one “broke out” of the game world. Some groups even played a second round. Winners of the sub-groups were invited to the final round, with all other participants standing by, watching the final round, and encouraging their group member to play and win.

For reflection and debriefing, players returned to their sub-groups, where facilitators asked them to choose their preferred action or create a new one to reflect their personality or personal interests. This newly developed step seemed to be a bit more difficult, as participants were no longer able to follow the easy rules and gameplay of Happy Dr. Octoludus but had to come up with their own rules and actions and talk about themselves. Some participants even expressed that they had difficulties opening up to strangers this way. They then mainly chose the easy way by choosing an existing action and providing little information about why they liked it the most. However, even while being a bit more challenging for some participants, this phase was particularly important from a community building perspective, as its pace was slower and allowed for real connection between the players following the fast-paced game play.

In a centrally held debriefing, players were asked to reflect on their experience, and received some information from the facilitators about the motivation for the keynote action. The feedback from players was – during the debriefing and later on during the conference – overwhelmingly positive. Participants mentioned they enjoyed being actively involved and being offered an easy way to get to know each other. It removed certain barriers, and as players already

showed some vulnerable sides (e.g., being unable to shout as loud as others or find a counterpart to carry out the game actions), it lowered the threshold of doing so in later interactions during conference Q&As or game play. In addition, the feedback we received was that starting with a conference with a keynote action had a positive impact on the rest of the conference program.

Conclusions and Recommendations

What we learned

The development, facilitation, and observation of Happy Dr. Octoludus was an enjoyable and easy task for busy conference organizers. As the game is based on an existing game, there was no need for time-consuming game design. The customization of the game to align with the conference mascot was the only design task that was carried out. We added the debriefing phase to allow players to cool down and build on the connections they established during the easy game play. While the debriefing was reported to be slightly more challenging by some players, we saw that allowing some slower-paced time for connecting added to the goal of establishing first relationships at the beginning of the conference.

The game was easy to implement, as the keynote slot for the first keynote was reserved for it, and the game – in place of a keynote speech – was clearly indicated in the program. All participants were therefore prepared for this to a certain extent. Including the game first-up in the program was an ideal choice in hindsight, as it not only provided an early opportunity for interaction among conference participants but also set the tone for the conference as a whole. It not only allowed participants to interact during the game, but it also opened up possibilities for further discussion and connection. It also removed some of the barriers that usually keep participants from approaching each other, or, as is usual at ISAGA conferences, to engage in further, more complicated game play.

What others can do

We recommend using a game-based keynote activity at the opening of a larger meeting or conference at which participants do not know each other well, or a group of familiar and fresh participants are brought together). A game levels out differences and is a very inclusive and engaging way of interacting. Happy Dr. Octoludus is best played when all players stand in a circle, but it can also be played with players sitting, or by a mixed group. As the cards indicate the actions visually, no (English) language skills are needed to engage in the game play. The characters on the cards represent an animal, so they are gender-neutral and do not depict other personal attributes of humans, either. For others wishing to design a conference game, we recommend paying attention on such inclusive design elements. We realized that it helped to tell a story around the keynote. With the connecting element – the mascot of the ISAGA conference – it was just as much a challenge and exciting for familiar ISAGA participants as it was for first-timers.

It is best to use a game that is easy to produce, as organizing a conference is a huge undertaking in itself. The rules of the game should also be easy to communicate and to learn, so that players

do not need to recall complicated instructions and can start playing immediately. Our game was a mix between collaboration and competition, which in our view worked well to foster interaction in an engaging way.

Adding a debriefing phase is important to allow players to cool down from the intense game play and to establish connections. The debriefing, while still connected to the game play, should include some strong nudges to share information.

Limitations

We are aware that conference travel has a negative environmental impact due to delegates traveling/flying to one venue. It is also not the most inclusive format as some individuals, such as researchers coming from low-income countries or facing travel restrictions, are excluded from this form of scientific discourse. These aspects of scientific conferences are not part of our report here. Our focus is on fostering the in-person experience of scientific conferences. However, online or hybrid conferences could also benefit from an interactive start, allowing participants to establish connections over distances.

ISAGA conferences bring together researchers and practitioners interested and working in and with games. Therefore, the group we played our game with was already familiar with the use of games to foster group processes such as interaction and communication. This surely had an impact on the experience with the game.

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Disclosure of Interests

Both authors were the organizers of the conference.

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Junkichi Sugiura, Franz Renz & Seiji Suzuki

Complementary Roles of Rules and Facilitation in Group Formation and Reconstruction: A Case Study of the Chemical Reaction Game

Abstract

This study intends to express social psychological phenomena related to the formation and reconstruction of groups using the Chemical Reaction Game, a model in chemistry that has been transformed into a set of rules. Players will consider the connection and separation among people based on game experiences. This game aims to enable players to understand the relationship between laws of chemistry and the construction of human relationships. Understanding the laws of chemistry requires specialized knowledge. By devising rules and facilitation methods aligned with participants' level of understanding of chemistry, it is possible to play the game without the support of chemistry experts. When people encounter new people or situations, they realize that certain rules are in place as a code of conduct. If they do not understand a local language, then they will also need to understand the rules of the language. Through case studies, we will show that the role of the facilitator in gaming simulations is similar to that of language interpreters and tourist guides who introduce a culture.

Keywords: Chemical reaction, Facilitation, Group formation.

1 Introduction

1.1 What is the Chemical Reaction Game (CRG)?

For a long time, scholars in the field of social psychology have been formulating theories about groups through experiments (Van Lange et al., 2021). However, these experiments have not always been sufficient in capturing the phenomena of group restructuring, individual participation in groups, and individual withdrawal from groups. If one examines a real society, then one may see that people form, expand, or split groups and occasionally even restructure or dissolve them. Using gaming, we can increase the mobility of group members, who tend to become fixated on laboratory experiments and reproduce the phenomenon of repeated group formation and reconstruction.

The current study uses the CRG, which is based on a chemical model, to represent the formation and reconstruction of groups. The nature of the chemical bond is always formed due to energetic stability, based upon electromagnetic interaction of the atom nucleus and electrons between particle and wave duality. This leads to three strong types of chemical bonds: the covalent, the ionic, and the metallic bond. The covalent bond is stabilized by resonant interference of delocalized electron waves. The ionic bond is stabilized by opposite localized charges described by Coulombs law. The metallic bond is a mix of covalent and ionic bonding, in CRG a multi-human group interaction. In CRG, a single touch, e.g. hand to hand, corresponds to the

creation of a covalent bond in chemistry, a second touch to a double bond. In CRG we can model chemical reaction mechanisms of atoms forming molecules due to bond formation and bond breaking. Ionic interaction scales with distance, the closer you get the stronger the ionic interaction, stabilizing with opposite charges and repulsion of same charges. The CRG interpretation is that if the physical distance to another person diminishes, ionic interaction increases. This fits well for human relationships and can be extended to different models of society.

In CRG, participants play the role of chemical elements in a face-to-face situation and express their joining and breaking up with others using their bodies. Through such activities, they are expected to understand social psychological phenomena. The CRG has been developed as a gaming simulation that enables people to experience bonding (holding hands) and separation (releasing hands) by likening them to chemical elements through collaboration between chemical and social psychology researchers. For participants who know chemistry, these laws are background knowledge rather than explicit game rules; for those who do not, they may be understood as part of the rules.

1.2 Fusion of chemistry and social psychology

Social psychology focuses on the interaction between individuals and society, including changes in attitudes and behavior due to interpersonal influence, the process of group formation, and relationships between groups. In classical studies in social psychology, several proposed theories use metaphors from physics to explain concepts such as *conformity* as an influence exerted by the behavior of others, *consonance* in terms of cognitive dissonance theory, psychological *reactance* theory in resistance to persuasion, and *resilience* (Sugiura, 2025).

Chemistry intends to explain the basic structure of matter and its changes at the microscopic level. For example, carbon dioxide (CO₂, two double covalent bonds) is cited as a greenhouse gas that is considered to contribute to climate change. The chemical reaction pattern of methane (CH₄, four single covalent bonds with greenhouse potential) combining with oxygen (O₂, a double covalent bond, no greenhouse potential) to produce CO₂ and water (H₂O, two single covalent bonds with greenhouse potential) can be replaced by a group process. For example, groups A (CH₄) and B (O₂) interact to re-form into groups C (CO₂) and D (H₂O).

Suppose we apply this type of bonding relationship, which is created by chemical reactions, to society. In this case, the concept of group cohesion can be used to understand the stable molecular structure of a benzene ring, which is difficult to break. What rules and facilitation are needed in the CRG to apply social psychological phenomena, such as conflicts and their resolution, to typical chemical reactions?

1.3 The relationship between game rules and facilitation

Game rules remain the same regardless of participants, but the understanding and interpretation of rules differ according to players. Differences also exist in how people understand behaviors that are not explicitly stated in rules. Applying accumulated theories and techniques of various facilitation methods that support appropriate decision-making and behavior is possible by understanding the rules of the game (Leigh & Levesque, 2024).

The CRG follows the laws of chemistry. For example, H_2O and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) are possible, but HO is not. The laws of chemistry in the CRG are not the rules of the game for those who know them; for those who do not, they can be considered an extension of the rules. They can be positioned in the same manner as language in a game that involves language activities. Players who do not know the laws of chemistry would need support in understanding these laws as a language. In other words, the rules and facilitation of the CRG need to be devised for people who do not understand the laws of chemistry. Figure 1 shows that, out of the total six players, four hydrogen players and two oxygen players first form two groups of water. Then, the two water groups (molecules) are reorganized (electrolysis) into two groups of hydrogen, each with two hydrogen players, and one group of oxygen with two oxygen players. To help players understand this, it is useful to show the structure of water molecules and chemical reactions in a diagram such as Figure 1, or to have a facilitator gather a few people and have three players create water molecules as an example.

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram of the Chemical Reaction.

The CRG implicitly incorporates the rules of chemistry and instructs players to create bonds. A facilitator familiar with chemistry can support the laws of chemistry that are explicitly expressed in the game rules. However, a facilitator who is unfamiliar with chemistry needs to prepare in advance, such that they can illustrate the potential combinations of bonds to players. The role of facilitation is to support implicit rules (in this case, the laws of chemistry). Simply put, one of the roles of the facilitator is to formulate implicit rules that may govern the game explicitly.

Chemistry is a system of laws. Exactly what is the extent to which the laws of chemistry should be incorporated into the rules of the CRG? If participants in a game possess a similar level of understanding of chemistry, then simply indicating in the rules how they should behave in the game is sufficient, but if this is not the case, then facilitation support will be necessary.

1.4 The concept of the CRG

The CRG enables one to experience the dynamics of individuals and groups. The following principles underlie its development:

- (1) To organize patterns of chemical reactions that can be used as models for human relationships and social division/integration, and to create rules for the conditions of chemical reactions, such as combination and decomposition, as metaphors.
- (2) To develop a program that corresponds to chemical reactions and social psychological phenomena and can be used in school education and event workshops.
- (3) To devise a method of expressing chemical bonds through facilitation as professional support or by combining rules and facilitation to pattern the rules of bonding (including demonstrations).

There are several variations with regard to how people can play the role of chemical elements. Participants hold cards with the symbols of elements on them; while showing one another their cards, they decide on whether they can form a group as a molecular compound based on the laws of chemical reaction. For example, during the game, three players meet players A, B, and C holding cards with hydrogen (H), H, and O, respectively. They flash their cards to one another and combine them to make H₂O.

This process could be viewed as a metaphor for social integration, while H₂O electrolysis could be considered social division. Examples of games that utilize division and integration are Marketplace (Sugiura, 2006) and ICHIBA (Interpersonal Comparison for Horizontal Integration by Border Awareness) (Sugiura, 2006; Sugiura & Renz, 2021).

1.5 Gaming for division and integration: Marketplace and ICHIBA

In Marketplace (Kriz, 2007), players walk around a room individually for approximately 30 s, form groups of 3–4 people nearby at the signal of a facilitator, discuss a given theme, and disperse after 3–5 minutes. By repeating this process 3–5 times, it is possible to hold discussions with random members without stable groups. ICHIBA (Kriz, 2007; Sugiura, 2006) is a game in which participants decide whether they want to join the same group based on similarity of opinions. Using these two games, discovering common interests with others and cooperating with them is possible. Both games simulate the process of the gathering and scattering of people, starting from a situation in which people have dispersed due to various factors.

In the CRG, each member holds a card with the symbol of a chemical element, and they determine whether they can form a group as a molecular compound by showing each other the roles that correspond to the properties of the elements. Combining these two makes possible the expression of the process of people gathering and then scattering again as a CRG.

2 CRG Prototype (Case 1)

Participants become one element, experience the formation of compounds by combining with other elements, and learn to view various phenomena in everyday life as social psychological phenomena.

2.1 Prototype rules

Number of players: 3–10 (more are possible)

Materials: Element cards (e.g. C, H, O, and S) (others are possible)

Basic rules

- (1) Play in an open space where players can move freely.
- (2) Provide each player with four element cards.
- (3) Each player selects one card and becomes the element.
- (4) Each player finds other players to combine and form a group.
- (5) All players are encouraged to form combinations that will enable everyone to hold hands (as a cooperative game).

Rule variations that apply chemical knowledge

The following points are ideas for variations of the game from the perspective of chemical laws.

- (1) Increase the number of elements. A system is needed to provide knowledge to help players understand which elements make up chemical substances.
- (2) Consider the number of hands for bonding, such as single and double bonds. A system is required to help players learn about the strength of bonds, such as electronegativity and its effects on the stability of a structure.
- (3) Focus on the weight of compounds (e.g. the fact that the heavier the substance, the higher the score) and acquire knowledge about the weight of elements.
- (4) Set conditions for the creation of compounds, such as oxidation at high temperatures, which represents combustion.
- (5) Set goals for the substances to be created, such as setting restrictions on the creation of CO₂ in relation to real-world issues (e.g. global warming) and ensuring that substances such as H₂O and O₂, which are necessary for human life, are created.

2.2 Lecture at Leibniz University Hannover

On 4 August 2021, the first author presented a 60-minute lecture titled “Experiential learning through games: A comparison between Germany and Japan” at Leibniz University Hannover in Germany as part of the CRG. The lecture was held in-person with a maximum of ten people outdoors due to restrictions enacted to prevent the spread of COVID-19 in Germany (Sugiura & Renz, 2021).

Following the Settoku-Nattoku (SN) game (Sugiura, 2022) that was conducted earlier, each participant was given four cards (labeled C, H, O, and S, among others, written on the margins of the cards used in the SN game).

9–10 cards each were prepared for H, C, and O, which can form many combinations when making molecules. The ten participants selected one card from the set of four cards and created molecules while considering combinations with other participants (e.g. CO₂, H₂O, and CH₄).

After the game, the participants, including the co-researchers, reflected on the game. In relation to climate change, society calls for reductions in CO₂ emissions, but C and O, which make up CO₂, are necessary elements. The researchers shared the idea that various elements make up substances and that they all make sense.

This lecture became an opportunity to try out new practices in the CRG, and discussion among the participants successfully led to fresh insights that helped to develop the game further.

3 Setting Goals: Substituting Facilitation for Rules (Case 2)

3.1 Preparing combination patterns

In Case 1, a chemistry expert was present, and he was able to guide the players to create a target compound. However, without a chemistry expert, this facilitation would be impossible. There is a possibility that the players would not know how to create compounds.

Facilitation can be omitted by providing information on which elements can be combined to make which compounds on cards and by incorporating the target compound into the game rules. Specifically, we used a commercially available game called *Chemistry Game Ion Card* (ZIKI Kenkyukai, 2021). It is a card game in which cards are labeled with positive (e.g. Na⁺) and negative (e.g. Cl⁻) ions, and compounds (e.g. NaCl) are formed by combining them. This card set was used in the CRG. There are eight types of positive ion cards, nine types of negative ion cards, and 20 types of compound cards. The players are given a random selection of ion cards, making compounds in succession while referring to a list of patterns for combinations.

3.2 Practical application in a graduation thesis seminar

In a lecture (seminar) held at the university by the first author, the CRG was conducted in October 2023 as part of a workshop on game development, practice, and evaluation, which was attended by 14 participants and one observer.

Each player was given two cards, one for a cation and another for an anion, and they searched for another player with whom they could form a compound and recorded the compounds they created. As the game progressed, the participants split into two large groups and began forming new compounds within these groups.

3.3 Debriefing

After each participant had written down their observations during the game, learnings, and new rules they would like to suggest, everyone gave comments on the game. The following points were raised for discussion.

- (1) As a cooperative action, it is necessary that each person shows the information on the card that they are actively using.
- (2) While comparing cards in groups can be more efficient in certain ways, it can also make the game similar to a puzzle with cards laid out in a row.

The observers expressed their overall impressions of the game. They suggested ways of developing it from a team management perspective, such as “finding missing members of a group (staff safety standards),” “identifying the strengths of a group (specialized team strengths),” “appropriately forming a fluid project team (development of methods),” and “finding talented people with higher levels of abilities, i.e. people who can easily combine (staff evaluation).”

4 Complementary of Rules and Facilitation Based on the Presence or Absence of an Expert (Case 3)

With the increase in the number of elements used in Case 1 (20 elements) and ion cards used in Case 2 (17 cards), a high level of knowledge of combinations was required. Therefore, in Case 3, the number of elements was limited to three types (i.e. H, C, and O) and rules were set for creating carbon compounds, among others. The introduction of rules that reduce the number of elements in the game also reduces the burden on the facilitator to achieve the game’s objective.

4.1 Implementation with a large group without experts (Japan)

In a lecture at Keio University in Japan, 87 individuals participated in the CRG in January 2024. The game was played according to this rule: the winner pertains to the person who participated in the largest group (molecular weight) as a result of creating groups (compounds) with many people (elements). Although many students undertook chemistry in junior high school or high school, they were not currently studying chemistry as a specialty. Nevertheless, they found that they could create various compounds as long as they understood the simple rules for combining each of the three elements. Because the laws of chemical combination are fixed, the participants commented that “some people are left out because they can’t find a partner” and “when there are people who are needed and people who are not needed, a leader appears and coordinates the people who are needed well.” Although the group was large and no chemical experts facilitated the game, by limiting the elements to three, many players were able to form compounds with large weights by looking up molecules composed of three elements on their smartphones.

4.2 Small-Group implementation with a chemistry expert (Germany)

A workshop was held at Leibniz University Hannover in Germany on 19 January 2024, which was attended by eight participants, including chemistry majors. Although it was a small-scale event, the second author, who is a specialist in chemistry, advised on which compounds could be made, and in the third and last session, all participants were able to make the compound CO_3H_4 . The players were able to combine elements (cards) and link hands to form groups of molecular compounds, with each participant using the remaining elements from the two elements they used in the two previous sessions (H, C, and O):

- We ran around as elements and made compounds as a group; it was fun.
- It might take time and effort to ensure that no one is left behind, but it suggests how we should cooperate to achieve harmony as a society.

- Even if you are different from other people, you can connect with them. Diversity is an important point. By cooperating, you can achieve great results.

The facilitator, a chemical specialist (second author), commented that “CO₂ is often demonized as a cause of global warming, but the earth also needs CO₂” and further explained that it is also possible to create unstable compounds such as CO₃H₄. Comments from the players also confirmed that cooperative relationships are essential if one wants to improve one’s score by connecting with other people.

5 Developing Facilitation for Children (Case 4)

This case presents an example of a CRG event that was held for people who were neither experts in chemistry nor game enthusiasts. The facilitator applied the rules flexibly according to the participants, and the game progressed smoothly.

On 26–27 October 2024, the Japan Science and Technology Agency hosted an event called “Science Agora”, which was announced as a “public square that connects science with a society open to all people.” The first author oversaw an exhibition entitled “Demonstration of a CRG that connects people through human relationships.” More than 5,000 people attended the event over two days. A 3x3 m space was allocated in the corner of a large venue (on the third-floor walkway), where CRG information posters and props (nameplates with chemical symbols and sticks that illustrate the number of bonds of each element) were displayed, and we attracted participants as they walked around.

It was the first time we participated in this event, so when we were planning to run the game, we made predictions about the types of people who would be participating, and we planned to adjust the rules and facilitation flexibly. From a meta-perspective, we were always aware that people were expressing chemical reactions using their bodies, and our goal was to have fun while interacting with visitors. The facilitators recruited participants to play, and the demonstration of chemical reactions was a game in itself, depending on the number of people who gathered. While predicting what would happen in the two days was difficult, the focus of the facilitation was to use our imagination in advance to flexibly address any unexpected events. We did not fix the rules of the game; instead, we changed plans according to a situation if necessary.

5.1 Recruitment of participants and demonstration by a facilitator

We found that many of the people visiting the event were families, followed by staff and parties exhibiting at Science Agora. Over the course of two weekend days (a total of 14 h), ten sociology students and four experts with knowledge of game operation took turns in running the CRG. The main objective of the former was to convey fun in learning chemistry by acting out the roles of elements while providing easy-to-understand explanations of the game rules. For the latter, the main aim was to convey the appeal of the game, which enables people to learn about chemistry while acting out the roles of the elements.

To help children understand the laws of chemistry, we prepared props to demonstrate how many hands each H, C, N, and O element can bond. For example, C has four hands that can be

combined, but humans only have two hands. Thus, we used two V-shaped sticks to represent the four hands, with each hand holding one stick. O has two hands, so we used one stick per hand. Hydrogen (H) has one hand, so we used one stick in one hand. The left panel in Figure 2 represents CO₂, the right panel H₂O. By conveying the rule that the sticks are connected to one another, it is easy to intuitively understand that C (with four hands) combines with four H atoms with one hand to form methane (CH₄). The rules and facilitation techniques used for explaining the laws of chemistry can be supplemented by using props.

Figure 2. Using Sticks to Represent the Number of Hands of Elements (Left: CO₂, Right: H₂O).

At the beginning of the first day, few people were wandering around, so the facilitators observed the situation and gradually began to approach people, who responded shyly. However, their responses differed depending on whether they had any knowledge of chemistry. When we approached small children, parents mainly responded. Parents and students who were seemingly interested in chemistry responded with interest.

In the afternoon of the first day, the number of people gradually increased, and we became increasingly accustomed to recruiting people to participate. Similar to the conventional CRG, the number of participants was limited, so we created a story that would enable us to demonstrate a chemical reaction with the number of people who gathered. Specifically, we recruited nine participants; with the support of the facilitator, the children slipped into the role of the elements to emulate the production of H₂O and CO₂ through the combustion of methane ($\text{CH}_4 + 2\text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}_2$). If the number of people was insufficient, the facilitator would become a player or recruit people to circulate. Demonstrating chemical reactions, we explained similarities and differences between interpersonal relationships and the composition of organizations. In other words, when people form groups, they may or may not join based on their likes and dislikes; in chemistry, however, likes and dislikes are irrelevant. Even in society, people must take on roles regardless of likes and dislikes. In any case, the rules of chemistry are absolute in terms of combining with other elements (players) to create compounds, while groups cannot be formed unless they follow an established method; from this game, one can understand that society can make its own rules. Through the explanations given to the children, their parents were also able to discuss the relationship between chemical reactions and society using their own words.

Kenichi Ito, an associate professor at Nihon University who specializes in chemistry and was participating in a different exhibition project on the day, occasionally visited our event, giving the facilitators advice and answering our questions.

5.2 Debriefing for the facilitators

After the game, the facilitators held a debriefing session to reflect on the activity. By making props to represent the number of hands of the elements, children who were unfamiliar with chemistry were able to enjoy and take an interest in the game. The V-shaped props representing the two hands of C caught the children's attention. A minimum number of players are required due to the nature of the game, but this form of visual performance attracted the interest of passers-by and led to opportunities for strangers to play the game together. By calling out "We're short of O!" when the number of players was insufficient, the facilitators were able to attract participants by tapping into the Japanese tendency to be easily swayed.

As previously described, the facilitators did not simply tell players how to play a game with a fixed format; instead, each facilitator formulated plans on how to explain the game to the people who came to Science Agora, how to make them understand, and what to tell them, and it became a play space where they put these ideas into practice. This time, the flow was to have players form compounds while following the facilitation. However, if players could set rules that would enable them to achieve their goals, then promoting conversations among strangers and experiencing the process of group formation would be possible.

6 Boundaries of Group Formation (Case 5)

In this case, we focus on the formation of groups through the performance of CRG players. Chemical reactions demonstrate how molecules combine and change into other molecules. While the general appearance of individual elements gathering and scattering can be applied to the Marketplace game system, the constraints for combining elements when they gather can be applied to ICHIBA. Therefore, we first played a simplified version of ICHIBA, then prepared a system that enables players to form groups under constraints, and reconfigured the groups by replacing the constraints with chemical reactions.

6.1 Gathering friends: Applying ICHIBA and the CRG

The basic rule of the game is to form groups composed of 5–8 people, according to the goals presented by the facilitator. Four elements (i.e. H, C, N, and O) are present in equal numbers and randomly assigned to players. The group with the most members in a group with a composition that meets the goal within five minutes for each of the following four games is declared winner.

- Game 1 (Birds of a Feather): Group together as much as possible with people of the same type.
- Game 2 (Diversity): Group together as much as possible with people of different types.
- Game 3 (Molecular compounds): Make one or more molecules or compounds.

- Game 4 (Chemical reactions): Make chemical reactions between compounds and other molecules or compounds (including other groups).

6.2 Similarity and diversity

On 19 December 2024, 68 university students participated in ICHIBA and the CRG as part of a social psychology lecture.

In Game 1, cards were randomly distributed at the start, so players had to find other players with the same card to achieve their goals. What do the players feel when they find a group of people with the same card? What do the majority and minority feel when they find a group with multiple types?

The players commented the following:

- In the homogeneous group, I felt a sense of safety because everyone was the same, but in the heterogeneous group, I felt a strong sense of belonging to the “H” role.
- I felt a sense of safety because people with similar characteristics gathered together.

In Game 2, the theme was that people of the same type needed to gather, but then they had to gather with people of different types, so a big need emerged to reshuffle between groups. What kinds of ideas would be needed to gather people of different types evenly? “I teamed up with people of the same type so that I would not be isolated, but I was also desperate not to be left on my own.” So while they were pursuing diversity, concerns about isolation also emerged. The following impressions were also obtained in comparison with Game 1:

- When forming homogeneous groups, we were able to welcome one another comfortably, but when forming diverse groups, it felt difficult to accept people apart from the desired type.
- When moving from Game 1 to Game 2, it is important to have a certain strategy in mind before moving.
- In Game 1, although a sense of camaraderie developed, there was little sense of individuality, and from Game 2 onward, I gradually began to become aware of my role as a nitrogen source.

The theme of Game 3 was to form groups with members who can easily form the molecules and compounds listed in a table. In Game 2, the players were reconstituted as a diverse group of members. This group must be reconstituted in Game 3 to form bonds according to the laws of chemistry. The theme of Game 4 is to strategically find partners by anticipating which elements (molecules) can react with which elements (molecules).

A previously created group may or may not need a certain type to fit into a chemical reaction pattern. In society, a person may be let go in order to transform an organization. Exclusion from a group (making oneself superfluous) is a negative experience for players and can be an ethical issue in gaming (Kriz et al., 2024). However, CRGs ensure psychological safety for unwanted players because groups are formed according to the laws of chemistry. This change in rule type also helps players avoid the negative experience of group exclusion.

In the case of gaming, where many players reconstruct several groups, the facilitator cannot observe the behavior of all players. Nevertheless, the abovementioned rule settings can decrease the control of players through facilitation.

6.3 Differences and similarities between chemistry and human relationships

A difference between the formation of human relationships and chemical reactions is that people form groups based on likes and dislikes in human relationships. By contrast, bonds and chemical reactions occur under certain conditions. Organizations also have a fixed structure in human society, and people are assigned to positions within them daily. In chemistry and organizations, characteristics change according to the combination of people; in human relationships, however, feelings such as likes and dislikes typically play a major role.

In daily life, people casually form groups and adjust relationships with others in organizations. Organizations may be fine because they are in a stable social situation, but in a turbulent society, people become more fluid.

In Case 6, where ICHIBA and CRG are combined, goals change across four phases. Naturally, elements and humans are different. When a human plays the role of an element, the question of what connects “us” with “other people” emerges. If this is viewed as a change in social conditions, then it implies that people should be prepared for change and consider the distance that should be kept from other types of players and what we should prepare for.

7 Discussion

7.1 Relationship between CRG learning outcomes and relevant factors

This paper introduced the rules of the CRG and the development of the facilitation role across five cases. Table 1 shows the relationship among learning outcomes for each case, the chemical knowledge required of facilitators, the importance of the facilitator role, and the clarification of rules for players. The role of facilitator in supplementing chemical knowledge is significant (Case 4). On the other hand, by using cards to clearly indicate the purpose (Case 2), or by first conducting a game aimed at fostering or reintegrating interpersonal relationships (Case 5), the need for chemical knowledge and facilitation decreases, and the rules of the game become clearer for the players. However, in Case 2, no group dynamics were observed, and the game resembled a puzzle-solving activity within a small group.

In other words, Case 5, a game in which the players are presented with a clear picture of what is expected of them in terms of group composition, has a different orientation from the molecular bonding of elements in chemistry or the recombination of one molecule into another through chemical reactions. Focusing on group composition and reconstruction, not limited to chemical reactions, is also a useful perspective on how to use games in a meaningful way.

Table 1. Relationship Between CRG Objectives and Relevant Factors.

Case	Players	Learning outcomes of the CRG	Chemistry knowledge required of facilitators	Importance of facilitator's role	Clarification of rules for players
1	Adults	Create groups by considering combinations of element cards provided	high	high	low
2	University students	Understand patterns of molecular combinations and create pairs	low	low	high
3	University students	Create large groups using many combinations of elements	high	low	high
4	Children (mainly)	Help children gain experiential understanding of chemistry	high	high	low
5	University students	Help players understand the laws of chemistry based on the rules of group composition	low	low	high

7.2 Relationship between the CRG and social psychology

In ICHIBA, which was introduced in Case 5 to contrast with the CRG, players are grouped based on similarities in opinions. In the CRG, players are likened to chemical elements, and compounds are created based on the laws governing chemical reactions. Participants hold cards labeled with chemical symbols and decide whether they can form a group as a molecular compound by showing their cards to one another. At first glance, this may seem to address chemistry, but it is nothing more than the creation of human groups following the laws of chemical reactions. Both games use the Marketplace system based on the framework of gathering and scattering.

In the CRG, the conditions under which compounds are formed can be established in various ways, according to objective. This aspect is the same as describing the real world as the rules of a game. Thus, it can be understood that chemistry as a science is a system of rules for the combination and decomposition of compounds.

7.3 Perception of boundaries in group formation

Participant's evaluations after playing the CRG clearly indicated that they learned about interpersonal and group relationships. For example, because the rules of combination (association) are fixed, situations arise in which "people are left out because they can't find a partner." However, cooperative behavior is also observed, such as "when there were people who were needed and others who were not, a coordinating leader emerged from among the players and helped

determine which group each person should join.” These activities represent interpersonal connections using chemical reactions as a metaphor, while simultaneously simulating a model of chemical reactions.

As an application of this game, it is possible to formulate various objectives regarding which type of compound (group) is created under which conditions. An example is to use the molecular weights of compounds created by players as the score. In this case, the player who creates the most groups with other players wins. In this game, there may be players who are unable to combine with other players based on the laws of chemical reaction. In this case, the psychological safety of the players will be enhanced, because they are not excluded due to interpersonal preferences but due to the rules of chemistry. Depending on the rules established, various applications can be developed through the fusion of chemistry and social psychology.

7.4 Rules as a language for players

When people encounter new people or situations, they realize that certain rules are in place as a code of conduct. If they do not understand a local language, then they will also need to understand the rules of the language. The role of the facilitator in gaming simulations is similar to that of a language interpreter or tourist guide who introduces a culture.

At the CRG presented at the Science Agora, where people with diverse ages, interests, and knowledge gathered and were encouraged to participate, an interpreter and a tour guide were needed to facilitate the game. Ideally, the facilitator can play both roles, but this is not always possible. In fact, different skills are required for the roles of a chemistry expert and a game facilitator. For the interpretation part, the facilitators prepared patterns for memorizing standard phrases (e.g. “The combustion of methane produces H_2O and CO_2 .”) and demonstrated the rules of the bonding law (e.g. “The number of chopsticks is used to clarify the rule.”) by repeatedly amending them to ensure the participants understood. Some of the people who stopped by the CRG booth at the Science Agora had an understanding of the language of chemistry, while others did not. The facilitators experimented with the latter; as a result, they created a form of facilitation. Language and behavior are inseparable, but the CRG highlights this notion. Even among people who speak Japanese, understanding of the language of chemistry differs across individuals. For the CRG, the authors infer that different levels of understanding of the language of chemistry can be potentially incorporated as an element of the game.

An important goal of the CRG is to establish the laws of combination and separation as the laws of chemistry; thus, they cannot be arbitrarily changed at will. By being aware of the differences between elements and humans in the CRG, players will be able to observe the multilayered nature of the rules of chemical combination and group composition.

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The authors have no competing interests to declare relevant to this article's content.

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Citizen Science and Simulation Games: Empowering Urban Transformation

Abstract

This article describes the integration of citizen science and simulation games in participatory urban planning, using the redesign of St. Anna Street in Munich as a case study. Traditionally, citizen science has focused on data collection, but this project extends participation to the interpretation phase, empowering residents to collaboratively analyze and contextualize survey results.

The case draws on Arnstein's Ladder of Participation, emphasizing the role of partnership, delegated power, and citizen control in urban decision-making. Findings suggest that simulation games can serve as effective tools for promoting collaborative data interpretation and generating actionable recommendations for policymakers. The project demonstrates the potential of merging citizen science with simulation games to create more inclusive and reflective urban planning processes, offering a model for future participatory initiatives in mobility and public space design.

Keywords: Citizen Science, Participation, Urban Planning, Scenerii.

1 Introduction

It has become common practice to generate both qualitative and quantitative data on citizen participation. This form of engagement is widely known as citizen science. However, an increasing debate has arisen about whether participants should also be involved in analyzing the data they contribute, to minimize potential distortions of their statements. The St. Anna Street project, focused on redesigning a street segment, serves as an attempt to explore this approach by integrating a simulation game as a methodological tool for participatory data interpretation.

2 Combining Two Trends

2.1 Context of citizen science

Citizen science refers to the active involvement of non-professional scientists in scientific research, encompassing activities such as data collection, analysis, and dissemination. In the context of urban planning or development (Berding et al., 2024), citizen science has emerged as a valuable approach to foster public engagement, gather localized data, and inform decision-making processes. Integrating citizen science into urban planning allows for the incorporation of local knowledge and perspectives, leading to more inclusive and contextually relevant outcomes. For instance, participatory planning models emphasize the importance of engaging citizens in the planning process to ensure that diverse viewpoints are considered, thereby enhancing the legitimacy and effectiveness of urban development initiatives. "Participation in citizen

science is often depicted as a pyramid. At the bottom in the broad base, a very large group of citizen scientists perform a relatively simple and not very time-consuming task. Take for example installing sensor or taking a one-time count of a particular species of animal or plant. At the higher stages of the pyramid, citizen scientists will be more intensely involved in the project” (Veeckman et al., 2021, p. 13).

Technological advancements have further facilitated citizen participation in urban planning. Tools such as Geographic Information Systems (GIS) enable citizens to contribute spatial data, which can be instrumental in environmental governance and urban management. The concept of citizen design science combines elements of citizen science and design science, encouraging public involvement in the design and transformation of urban spaces. This approach leverages the creativity and insights of citizens to collaboratively address urban challenges, leading to more sustainable and user-centered urban environments. In summary, the integration of citizen science into urban planning processes enhances public participation, enriches the planning discourse with local knowledge, and contributes to the development of urban spaces that are more attuned to the needs and aspirations of their inhabitants.

2.2 Role of simulation games in urban planning

Simulation games have become instrumental in urban planning, particularly in managing and interpreting complex data. At TU Delft e.g., simulation games are utilized to analyze and design complex systems, such as sustainable cities and smart infrastructures. These games facilitate the exploration of various scenarios, enabling stakeholders to make informed decisions based on simulated outcomes.

A notable example is SimPort-MV2, a game developed in collaboration with the Port of Rotterdam and TU Delft (Warnerdam et al., 2006; Warmerdam et al., 2007). This game simulates the planning and management of the Second Maasvlakte port expansion, allowing players to engage with data-driven decision-making processes in a controlled environment. Another significant initiative is the ProtoWorld simulation-based gaming environment (Baalsrud Hauge et al., 2016). Developed to model and plan urban mobility, ProtoWorld integrates different simulations and street maps, allowing users to experiment with various mobility options in European cities. This platform is based on the game engine Unity, enabling participants to understand the implications of different planning decisions on urban mobility.

Simulation games in urban planning nowadays could play a crucial role in handling complex data. They provide a platform for stakeholders to engage with and interpret data, leading to more informed and effective urban planning decisions.

3 Citizen Science and Simulation Games

The classical approaches in citizen science are well known and include surveys, mapping, and collaborative platforms such as FoldIt (Curtis, 2015). While principles from the field of gamification are frequently applied, particularly as a motivation for participation, classic simulation games are relatively new in this domain. Nevertheless, parallels can be drawn in that self-explanatory and clear game rules should be prioritized when using simulation games in this domain (Miller et al., 2022).

Several scholarly works have explored the integration of simulation games and citizen science in urban planning. Poplin (2011) discusses the development of serious games to enhance public participation in urban planning, emphasizing their potential to engage citizens in the design process. The game NextCampus, described in detail by Poplin et al. (2017), serves as an example where storytelling and interactive elements are used to involve the public in planning decisions. Similarly, the EquiCity Game proposed by Nourian et al. (2023) is a mathematics-based serious game designed to facilitate participatory design of spatial configurations, aiming to mediate decision-making processes in city planning. These examples illustrate how simulation games can serve as effective tools for incorporating citizen input into urban development projects.

The urban challenge revolves around negotiations with local residents to explore alternative uses for a street segment beyond car traffic, which is still a highly political process. This issue intersects with participatory urban planning, where the focus is on balancing diverse stakeholder interests while reimagining public spaces. Scientific approaches involve evaluating the social, economic, and environmental impacts of proposed changes, alongside assessing public perceptions and needs. Methods such as citizen engagement workshops, surveys, and simulation games can facilitate collaborative decision-making. By integrating these tools in one process, we tried to find an optimal mix.

4 Case Study: St. Anna Strasse

4.1 The background

During construction work, St. Anna Street, a small but central street in an urban quarter in Munich was unexpectedly closed to through traffic. This unplanned traffic trial made it immediately evident for everybody that closing the street permanently was a feasible option. This spontaneous experiment sparked widespread public discussions and led to several formal proposals to the local city district committee. Suggestions ranged from making the closure permanent to introducing alternative uses for the street segment, such as pedestrian zones, recreational spaces, or shared-use concepts. The trial served as a catalyst, demonstrating the potential for reimagining urban streets beyond their traditional role as thoroughfares for car traffic.

This scenario prompted the district committee to initiate a representative survey, aiming to capture a broad and diverse spectrum of opinions from the local residents. The committee took the process a step further by transforming it into a citizen science project. Instead of merely gathering feedback, they invited citizens to actively participate in interpreting the collected data and responses. This approach sought to foster a sense of co-ownership, deepen public engagement, and ensure that the insights generated reflected the community's collective voice.

4.2 The process

The data was collected through an online citizen survey that was accessible for nearly two months. Citizens were invited to participate in an online survey via posters and postcards in local shops, as well as billboards. The visually appealing tool provided by the Dresden-based start-up Scenerii was optimized for short and concise surveys via smartphone. The survey was in three stages and based on a 3D model of the street. Participants initially placed a marker on

the section of the street where they wished to leave a comment. Subsequently, they had the option to annotate this marker with text. This comment function was an open text field without character limits. The third participation stage involved upvoting or downvoting other participants' comments with a thumbs-up or thumbs-down.

Figure 1. Surface intro of the app Scenerii.

Figure 2. Scenerii KonsensMapper: Display showing negative (red), neutral (yellow), and positive (green) comments regarding the removal of parking spaces.

Over 523 individuals participated, leaving 839 text contributions and 8,500 ratings. Data analysis was performed using OpenAI's gpt-3.5-turbo model via its API, which extracted approximately 25 overarching themes from the extensive dataset. In conjunction with Scenerii's KonsensMapper tool, the 839 text contributions or statements were also categorized based on the ratio of votings: green means more than twice as many pro votes as against, red means more than twice as many votes against as pro, and yellow means all ratios in between.

The KonsensMapper tool was made available to both the district committee and participants, enabling them to interact directly with the data. Additionally, DIN A3 print-outs of a selection of the overarching themes, along with their associated comments, were provided at the workshop. This analytical approach facilitated interactive and engaging data exploration for both the district committee and citizens, enabling them to identify initial overlaps and explore creative suggestions.

Nevertheless, the data was still not self-explanatory and required further interpretation. For this, a simulation game was used in which the data was transferred into a game structure. Of the 523 survey participants, a group of 40 individuals were randomly selected and invited to participate in a simulation game designed for collective interpretation of the data and exploration of underlying themes.

Figure 3. Specific topics, by frequency of posts.

Based on the survey results, three main trends or scenarios emerged regarding St. Anna Street: a desire for it to remain closed to car traffic, a push for its complete reopening, and a preference for a partial reopening. We translated the 25 overarching themes into 19 mission cards and

developed a three-stage simulation game. Examples for the mission cards were: “A clean environment is paramount. More green spaces are needed everywhere. Shopping must remain accessible. Public spaces require enhanced safety measures.” Specific proposals such as road surface treatments, raised garden beds, drinking fountains, or ATMs were transformed into icons or 25 different game tokens for specific suggestions. The game board was a reduced-scale Open Street Map of the area, at a scale of 1:300, approximately equivalent to four conference tables. Participants could assume the role of a persona belonging to one of six different age groups ranging from 6 to 99 years.¹ Three individuals collectively adopted the perspective of one persona. The participants of the online survey who had provided their email addresses were invited to the two-and-a-half-hour early-evening workshop.

4.3 Simulation game framework

We opted to simulate only the two extreme scenarios: the complete closure of St. Anna Street and its full reopening. After all participants were assigned to one of the two scenarios, they received name tags representing their persona or age groups for the game. Individuals of the same age formed small groups, introduced themselves, and collectively tried to immerse themselves in their assigned personas. Each persona group was then tasked with selecting three mission cards from the 19 available options, choosing those they felt were most relevant or interesting to their age group. At this point, the actual game began, unfolding across three distinct phases.

First phase: Exploring surface changes

Guided by their chosen mission cards, the persona groups deliberated on where along St. Anna Street they would like to implement surface modifications. They were given three surface markers, each representing a specific category: streets, green spaces, and water areas. A street marker could indicate, for example, the transformation of cobblestones into asphalt or the paving of an unsealed path. The green marker could signify the removal of pavement to create a natural surface or the future planting of a tree or shrub. The water marker represented either uncovering a buried urban stream or installing a drinking fountain. Through these relatively broad designations, participants familiarized themselves with the game mechanics.

Second phase: Strategic placement of game tokens

In the second phase, persona groups collected as many game tokens as possible and placed them on any location within the game map. Again, their three mission cards guided these decisions. At this stage, emerging conflicts and agreements became apparent. Almost automatically, participants began asking, “*How do we reach a decision?*”, or “*What if someone wants something entirely different from our group at this place?*” These questions signaled the emergence of initial negotiations within and between groups. To ascertain preferences for the proposed design, groups were asked to place a small standee featuring their logo or a representation of their persona next to their preferred design.

¹ The following age groups were represented through personas: 6-10 years, 11-17 years, 18-30 years, 31-59 years, 60-74 years, and 75 years and older. Participants could simultaneously choose a gender within these age categories.

Figure 4. Third phase: Negotiation and consensus-building.

Figure 5. Fourth phase: game board with voting token.

In the final phase, the six persona groups actively negotiated their interests, sought allies, or worked to find compromises. Each persona group received five red and five white LEGO bricks as negotiation tools. The red bricks symbolized opposition to a proposal, while the white bricks represented strong support for its implementation. As the game progressed, participants could see small and large towers forming on the game board, visually representing both areas of conflict and zones of strong consensus regarding various proposed interventions.

5 Results of the Simulation Game St. Anna Street

Qualitative insights

The data-driven simulation was conducted from the perspective of six distinct age groups. To maintain a stable representation of each perspective, approximately two to three participants were assigned per age group. The qualitative evaluation focused on two key aspects: the documentation produced during the game and the recording of the public evaluation session. Documenting the decision-making process during the game posed certain challenges, as it was not possible to continuously capture the choices made by individuals or the group as a whole. Photographic documentation occurred between game phases, leading to the loss of valuable real-time information about the evolving decision-making dynamics. Numerous images of St. Anna Street and its surroundings were generated, illustrating the outcomes of table discussions. These images, however, required interpretation by the simulation's facilitators. We identified four distinct areas where differing opinions converged and were reflected in the photographs: (a) the square in front of St. Anna Church, (b) the transition from the street to the Klosterplatz, (c) the closed section of St. Anna Street, and (d) the vicinity of the adjacent school. Participants' preferences were tracked by having each persona group place their name tags next to their desired changes, allowing us to identify which groups advocated for specific concerns. Notably, both the older and very young generations expressed a strong desire for improvements to St. Anna Square. By contrast, the group comprising ages 31–59 primarily focused on St. Anna Street.

The public evaluation of the results was structured according to both the two simulation groups and their respective scenarios, as well as by age groups. Each simulation group articulated its demands and proposed changes for the designated urban space. Both simulation groups therefore addressed two key questions in a rapid-fire session: "Which topic was particularly important for your group?" and "On which topic did you have to particularly contend for a common solution?" For comparative analysis, alternating interviews were conducted with the corresponding age groups from both scenarios, allowing for a nuanced understanding of generational differences in spatial preferences and priorities. Observations regarding the responses and preferences for the two scenarios revealed a more holistic spatial consideration from the group advocating for street closure. This group focused on creating connections between public squares and expanding the schoolyard into public space. Conversely, the group tasked with scenarios involving the reopening of St. Anna Street explored various measures to enhance the street's versatility and safety, particularly for children. Their proposals included implementing one-way traffic, altering the road surface, reducing speed limits, and introducing temporary weekend closures.

Finally, all participants were asked for their direct recommendations to the district committee regarding the future of St. Anna Street, based on their experience in the simulation game. These recommendations were given in their capacity as residents, rather than in their assigned persona roles. The feedback coalesced around several key themes concerning the future design and function of urban spaces, particularly focusing on the St. Anna Street area. A prominent demand was the prioritization of pedestrian and communal space over motorized traffic, evidenced by calls for restricting street access to non-residents and creating a “play street”. Enhancing safety, in particular near the school, was frequently emphasized.

Significant attention was also given to inclusivity and accessibility, with requests to remove barriers, improve accessibility for wheelchair users, and address excessively smooth surfaces. There was a nuanced perspective on vehicle access, suggesting provisions for “interested parties” and local shop owners, alongside the desire for a partial rather than complete reopening of the street.

Specific design recommendations emerged, including the enlargement of the schoolyard, the leveling of cobblestone surfaces, and the improvement of transition areas near church steps. Participants also advocated for ecological considerations such as de-sealing surfaces and greening facades to address climate change. A clear sentiment expressed was the desire to avoid replicating the urban character of a highly frequented public square (Gärtnerplatz) popular with large segments of Munich’s urban society, and practical suggestions such as installing additional benches and potentially retrofitting speed bumps were put forth.

6 Discussion

6.1 Participation

Sherry Arnstein’s Ladder of Participation (Arnstein, 1969) provides a useful framework for understanding the depth of citizen involvement in decision-making processes. When considering the role of simulation games, we find that they can facilitate a range of participatory levels, often situating citizens at the higher rungs of the ladder. The Ladder of Participation conceptualizes citizen participation along eight levels ranging from non-participatory practices to full citizen empowerment. The model distinguishes: (1) Manipulation, (2) Therapy, (3) Informing, (4) Consultation, (5) Placation, (6) Partnership, (7) Delegated Power, and (8) Citizen Control. Arnstein argued that only the top three rungs of the ladder represent true participation. Therefore, these three stages will be briefly outlined with their key criteria:

- (6) Partnership: Citizens collaborate with decision-makers, sharing power and responsibility.
- (7) Delegated Power: Citizens have the authority to make decisions.
- (8) Citizen Control: Citizens exercise complete control over a project or decision.

Partnership entails a collaborative, equitable dialogue between citizens and decision-makers, where both parties work together to find solutions. In this model, citizens are not passive recipients of information or mere respondents to surveys but active co-creators of the process. In the case of St. Anna Street, citizens participated actively in interpreting and utilizing the survey data. They discussed the evaluation results, drew conclusions, tested these insights col-

laboratively, and collectively developed recommendations during the public evaluation session. Through this engagement, citizens assumed responsibility for the process, contributing their expertise and perspectives. Consequently, they were involved not only in forming opinions but also in the decision-making process itself. The outcomes of the game were entirely open-ended. This was particularly evident in the participants' ability to adopt extreme positions, ranging from complete closure to a full opening of the street segment. The real-world implications of the game were clear to all participants from the beginning of the workshop, especially given the presence of local district committee members who explicitly indicated their intention to consider the results in their decision-making. The insights and recommendations derived from the debriefing of the simulation game were directly incorporated into subsequent decision-making processes and proposals submitted to the city administration.

6.2 Broader implications

Citizen science should no longer be limited to the collection and generation of data; instead, citizens must also be actively involved in the stages in which findings are interpreted and recommendations are directly transferred to political decision-making bodies and administrative authorities. This shift necessitates a more comprehensive examination of participatory processes, including an analysis of power dynamics and the development of methodological adjustments to ensure more equitable participation.

7 Conclusion

While the participants had limited control over the overall game design due to its pre-determined structure, we designed the game board step by step in a collaborative process with the participants, using a minimum number of rules.

At present, we have not yet been able to systematically analyze the spatial design decisions made by different game groups during the simulation. The use of cameras was ruled out due to data privacy concerns, and continuous photographic documentation of the game board proved to be imprecise, with image framing often lacking clarity. In future iterations, we aim to enhance the reproducibility of decision-making processes by producing a more structured and continuous documentation of gameplay choices. As previously indicated in the description of the qualitative data collection process, alternative methods of analysis are needed to thoroughly examine the dynamics of the gameplay itself. Potential approaches could include guided interim evaluations focused on identifying areas of conflict, or a systematic analysis using AI-based image recognition. These methods are not mutually exclusive and could likely be combined to provide more comprehensive insights. However, from the perspective of partnership-based participation, a critical question arises: To what extent are these additional analyses truly necessary for informing the subsequent decision-making process?

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Chapter

Disaster Management & Urban Security

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From Complex Hydrological Data to Interactive Visual Flood Narratives

Abstract

In the face of climate change, uncertainty poses an increasing challenge in flood modeling and risk management. In this paper we present ReFlood. By leveraging real-time simulation technology, this software transforms complex hydrological data into accessible visual narratives, facilitating discussions in workshops with policymakers and local communities. Participants can explore various flood scenarios, assess risk management strategies, and experiment with adaptive urban planning measures.

Serious games may serve as boundary objects, as they can address critical societal challenges by enhancing communication, fostering collaboration, promoting education, and raising awareness. ReFlood is intended as a mediation tool for public consultations on flood risk management plans. This hands-on approach has attracted the interest of flood risk managers seeking to foster a shared understanding with urban planning authorities. Its effectiveness will be further evaluated through interviews with local stakeholders.

Keywords: Serious video game, Flood risk management, Interactive scenarios, Boundary object.

1 Introduction

In France, about 18 million people live in areas prone to flooding from river overflows or marine submersion. While residents are generally aware of their flood exposure (Roy, 2008), most of them are unaware of the existence of a Flood Risk Management Plan (FRMP) in their municipality.

Developing a FRMP follows an iterative process that includes assessing hazards through numerical modeling and cartography for extreme scenarios, identifying exposed assets and establishing risk zoning maps, drafting management regulations, and conducting consultation phases with authorities, residents, companies, associations, and other local stakeholders. The FRMP meetings allow for the presentation, the discussion, and potentially the adjustment of the plan. On the one hand, complex models and regulatory maps produced by engineering firms frequently cause misunderstandings between risk managers and stakeholders, exacerbated by disparities in expertise (Goutx & Narcy, 2012; Barbier & Charpentier, 2022). On the other hand, policy conflicts arise between the spatial planning and economic development policies pursued by local authorities and the risk prevention promoted by national authorities (Gralepois, 2020).

The concept of boundary objects (Star et al., 1989) facilitates the coordination of distributed knowledge through artifacts such as maps, charts, or classifications, which can be shared among actors with diverse backgrounds. Originally stemming from ethnology, this concept has gained significant attention in various other fields, including information sciences (Trompette & Vinck, 2009). In our case, while engineering maps are considered as important graphic aids in public debates (Joliveau et al., 2013), they can clash with personal cartographies that capture

individual perceptions and experiences (Arnaud, 2020). As a result, territorial managers are seeking mediation tools to bridge the gap between urban planning and flood risk regulation (Arnaud, 2020).

Serious games serve as boundary objects (Jean et al., 2018), as they can address critical societal challenges by enhancing communication, fostering collaboration, promoting education, and raising awareness. In the context of flood risk management, various educational and scientific games or animations (e.g., Spyropoulos et al., 2022; Breuer et al., 2017; Demiray et al., 2023; Macchione et al., 2019; Skinner, 2020) contribute to representing and understanding flood hazards. Nonetheless, hydrological simulations, gaming, and animations are usually developed by communities with distinct objectives and constraints, representing some trade-off between precision at the cost of computational expense and real-time performance at the cost of rigor.

Inspired by simulators developed for training in surgery, airplane flight or flood mitigation (Breuer et al., 2017), we combine simulation and gaming to design the real-time flood simulator ReFlood. It is based on terrain data that can be manipulated during the mediation phases of a FRMP to support risk planning managers. Particular emphasis is put on preparing the LIDAR terrain data, the gaming environment, and certain scenarios to provide the audience with an interactive experience while ensuring a degree of safety for presenters. A standalone version of ReFlood may be developed and made available for selected terrain configurations.

Materials and methods are described in Section 2. Some of the simulator capabilities are showcased in Section 3, then discussed from a mediation point of view in Section 4. Key insights and perspectives are outlined in the conclusion.

2 Materials and Methods

Data and the accuracy of representation are what typically distinguish numerical simulations (Teng et al., 2017), simulators (Breuer et al., 2017; Hum Interactive Limited 2023), animations (Skinner, 2020), and physical gaming boards (Barreteau et al., 2022). Many other forms of representation exist, and readers are referred to (Forrest et al., 2022) for a comprehensive review of serious gaming in flood risk management.

Focusing on FRMP, this research aims to connect the scientific, engineering, and territorial communities, each with diverse expectations and objectives regarding flood risk mapping. Providing a clear and inclusive description of the data and software is therefore essential for building trust by highlighting both the strengths and the limitations of the proposed approach.

2.1 Data for ground surface and water flows

Geographic Information Systems (GIS) maps have emerged as a key visual tool for public participation and engagement in debates or projects (Joliveau et al., 2013). Today, the practice of mapmaking is shifting away from experts, as creating maps – including advanced interactive 3D ones – has become accessible to anyone with a computer and an internet connection (Crampton & Krygier, 2010). Within the national LIDAR HD program, the Institut national de l'information géographique et forestière (IGN) produces and distributes a 3D map of France made of classified point cloud tiles.

Flooding often occurs on soils that are either saturated from prolonged rainfall, or extremely dry due to climate effects or anthropogenic soil sealing, making them effectively impervious (Teng et al., 2017). This assumption is commonly used in regulatory modeling. As a result, groundwater processes such as infiltration and subsurface outflow are neglected. The latter assumption is more controversial, as subsurface flows contribute to the stream network. It is worth noting that groundwater data are often unavailable at large scales or require complex additional modeling.

Public data on precipitation, water levels, and flow rates at monitoring stations are valuable resources. The HydroPortail platform provides access to these essential data. Streamflow rates can be used as inflow and precipitation may be converted into terrestrial runoff. High-water marks, along with videos collected from stakeholders and residents, can be used for both validation purposes and debates.

2.2 From point cloud tiles to terrain models

The IGN classifies LIDAR data (tiles of 1 km²) using artificial intelligence (Institut National de l'Information Géographique et Forestière, 2022). As of December 2024, classified clouds are publicly available for half of the metropolitan territory (released as open data under the Etalab 2.0 license). For now, the distribution of digital gridded models – elevation (DEM), surface (DSM) and terrain (DTM) – with a resolution of 0.5 m remains very limited because these require manual checks and optimization for better accuracy. This motivates the design of a graphical user interface.

We implement the ReFlood LIDAR viewer using MATLAB's integrated development environment. This software is able to convert certain ground and building classes within a point cloud (Figure 1, left) into a DTM (Figure 1, right). It also allows for local modifications in a straightforward manner. The resulting gridded model is saved in the .raw format for import as a terrain into the Unity engine. Digital elevation models (ground only) and digital surface models (all the points) can be built, too. It is worth noting that the ReFlood LIDAR viewer is also available in a Python implementation that utilizes LASzip – an open-source component of LAStools (Rapidlasso GmbH, 2007–2025) – to read compressed LIDAR data. The subsequent conversion to a digital elevation model involves projecting the point cloud onto a grid and interpolating to fill gaps, particularly those occurring over water bodies.

Figure 1. Snapshots of the ReFlood LIDAR viewer. Left: Ground point cloud, Right: Digital Terrain Model.

2.3 Designing scenes of the ReFlood simulator

The Unity game engine was launched by Unity Technologies in 2005 to create 2D/3D video games and animations. Due to its beginner-friendly interface, Unity developments are often introduced in the second year of Multimedia and Internet Bachelor's programs. Unity is also used in industries such as film, automotive, architecture, and engineering to develop 2D/3D interactive simulations.

Real-time game engines such as Unity take into account valuable scientific principles, including hierarchical decomposition of the game scene, gravity and object collision management, object control, illumination and shading of the scene, and terrain representation. A form of flow computation and rendering is implemented in the supplementary Flow asset developed by C. Wilkes (Wilkes, 2024). Unity, which can be employed as a black-box system, is therefore well-suited for the rapid development and control of the ReFlood simulator.

To start, we use Unity as a simulator interface and we mainly follow the Flow tutorial to build ReFlood scenes. First, the DTM is imported as a terrain object. Some objects may be added to figure out structures (red blocks of Figure 2, left). Game objects for flow modeling are a simulation box, a simulation surface attached to the terrain, and some flow modifier used as water inflow. The modifier object comes with a number of parameters such as position, strength of inflow, and fluid type. Some C# scripts may be added to monitor and control the flow (depth, strength) or to control objects such as the threshold (lower red block of Figure 2, left) in an interactive manner. Within Flow, water depths are computed as mean values over neighboring pixels.

Subsequently, we developed a dedicated user interface (UI) that allows ReFlood to be used as a standalone application (Figure 2, right), eliminating the need for a separate Unity installation. Playable elements positioned on the gray panel – specifically, cuboid modifiers that introduce fluid on demand and samplers that measure depth – are equipped with standard move/rotate/scale gizmos. The scene can also be populated with interactive cubes: gray ones symbolizing bridges and brown ones representing flow management structures. Users can freely navigate the camera across the scene and create configurations. Specific scene states and parameter settings can be captured and stored locally.

Figure 2. Left: A snapshot of the ReFlood simulator within the Unity interface. Right: The UI of the standalone ReFlood game (initial point of view).

2.4 ReFlood, stakeholders, and mediation

The ReFlood suite was initially designed as a serious game for FRMP mediation workshops. Efforts are focused on terrain representation using the LIDAR viewer and flood simulation, ensuring that both aspects can be operated in real time to incorporate stakeholder feedback. In addition, as a video game designed to promote a shared understanding, it can serve as an effective tool to educate decision-makers while raising awareness of flood risks and their impacts. This training may be conducted in advance. The proposed schedule is as follows:

1. Important notice: The risk managers are informed about the advantages of real-time handling as well as the drawbacks in terms of physical process representation in such video game simulations. In particular, accuracy and reliability are questioned in discussions with them.
2. Preparation: The risk managers prepare one or more scenes (data downloads) and scenarios (local terrain corrections/modifications, addition or removal of structures, inflow) in advance to ensure smooth simulator operation. A comparison with risk maps produced by the engineering firm is necessary to calibrate inflow parameters based on high-water marks.
3. Presentation & simulation: The risk managers present the scene and simulate an actual flood and/or a hypothetical flood hazard to initiate the debate, followed by the simulation of the prepared scenarios.
4. Debate: Feedback is monitored to better understand stakeholder perspectives, refine the scene in the simulator, and build a shared understanding of local flood risks.

Throughout the mediation phases, the objective is to observe how flood risk managers interact with the tool and how stakeholder positions evolve. This helps to evaluate the abilities of ReFlood in terms of representation, confidence, and conflict resolution.

3 Results

At the time of writing, the ReFlood approach, including the viewer and the simulator, is operational. It has been presented to some risk managers for potential use in their FRMP process. This section and the discussion thus report on the current state of ReFlood assessment and deployment.

The three case studies presented here focus on the Unified Nied watershed (Region Grand Est, France) and the same meteorological event. The first half of May 2024 was extremely wet, with a 73 percent surplus in rainfall. On the saturated marl soils of the Lorraine plateau, the exceptional rainfall accumulations on 16–18 May 2024 quickly led to flooding, including a more-than-centennial flood in Filstroff (Arnold et al., 2024) with a measured height of 5.63 m and an estimated discharge of 300 m³/s for the Unified Nied river (catchment of 1,170 km²). The other two examples are located in the city of Boulay-Moselle, which lies at the confluence of two right tributaries of the Unified Nied river.

Each case presents some geographical context, the highlighted ReFlood elements, and feedback from river managers. Hydrological modeling and uncertainty will be discussed from a scientific

point of view in a forthcoming paper. As a general comment, the simulator has been well received by river managers and has helped to intensify discussions and exchanges of knowledge.

3.1 Filstroff, a more-than-centennial flood

The Unified Nied river has a very gentle slope up to Bouzonville, causing the annual flooding of nearby meadows. Downstream, in the section including Filstroff, the Unified Nied forms wide meanders within a narrow rural valley. The 1 km² tile containing the village of Filstroff is represented as a point cloud, a DTM, and a terrain in Figures 1, 2, and 3, respectively.

This example introduces several elements (inflow strength and depth parameters, movable objects) that can be explored using the simulator during workshops, run in an engineering simulation, or a combination of both. Running ReFlood using an inflow for the Unified Nied only (with the small tributary parameter set to StrengthStream=0) successfully reproduces the flood map from the atlas (DREAL Grand Est, 2010). To enhance the rendering, a feedback loop is implemented to control the StrengthNied inflow parameter based on depth measurements at point DepthC. The simulation is run by using the Unity engine interface (Figure 2, left) to implement the feedback.

As discussed with river managers, the extreme rainfall led to an overflow of the left streamlet (which is partly buried downtown), causing water to spill from the pipe onto the main street. This event is simulated by setting StrengthStream=20 to accurately reproduce the actual May 2024 flood (Figure 3, center & right). The high-water mark DepthM and the water depth DepthB measured under the bridge align well with the collected data. The resulting figures have convinced river managers, who are now considering using ReFlood in meetings to illustrate the impact of threshold clearing (depicted as a fine red line in Figures 2, left, and 3) on river flow and habitats.

Figure 3. Left: Filstroff's flood zone (DREAL Grand Est, 2010) on an OpenStreetMap background. Center and Right: Flood extent at 10,000 and 85,000 frames, respectively.

3.2 Boulay-Moselle, urban flood

The flooding of the small medieval fortified city of Boulay-Moselle, which has an ancient moat feed by the Elbach stream (Figure 4, right) is under study. This example is presented to highlight discrepancies in flow between the raw DTM (1 m cell size) generated from the LIDAR point cloud

and the DTM corrected and validated with local river managers. Improvements have been made to restore the flow, which was obstructed at stream-road crossings and at the City Hall corner due to a house balcony. At flooding time, this makes possible the rendering of the stream's actual deviation from its channelized course near the City Hall corner (purple sampler). The simulated depths under the New Bridge and at City Hall corner (Figure 4, right) are in agreement with observed high-water marks.

An interactive presentation for local authorities is being discussed with river managers to debate mitigation measures along the Elbach stream. To that end, the simulation should be run on a larger terrain to include the upstream wetland buffer zone.

3.3 Boulay-Moselle, flood of the industrial zone

Boulay-Moselle is installing an industrial zone in a rather flat area located downstream from the medieval city, at the confluence of two streams, Elbach and Kalbach, two small right tributaries of the Unified Nied river. This example is built on a DTM of 3 km². The upper right 0.25 km² square corner corresponds to the lower left corner of the second example (Figure 4). The red bloc designates the river managers' office, flooded up to a height of 0.8 m.

Figure 4. Left: Boulay Center on an OpenStreetMap background (1 km² overlapping four LIDAR tiles). Right: Simulation on a corrected LIDAR-based DTM.

Using the simulator and the Unity interface, the terrain may be carved using the terrain tools asset to explain or avoid flow jams at stream-road crossings during the workshop.

The resolution approach is akin to an explicit finite difference method, which results in slow propagation in simulation mode (Figure 5, left) despite GPU optimization, due to the high frequency of rendering. The simulated depth of Figure 4, center, is in agreement with the observed high-water mark. The simulation clearly shows that a south extension of the industrial zone will be in the major bed of the Kalbach stream.

Alternatively, for a faster rendering inspired by video games such as Splatoon (Nintendo) and PowerWash Simulator (Square Enix), the modifier can be dragged along the watercourse to accelerate the visualization of flooding, thereby revealing topographic features and flow dynamics (Figure 5, right). Clearly, for a given resolution and shorter interaction duration, the

resulting visual outcomes can differ significantly, depending on whether the perspective is that of a simulation, a simulator, or a video game.

Figure 5. Left: Boulay's industrial zone, overlaid on an OpenStreetMap background. Center: Simulation mode. Right: Flooding the zone by dragging the Modifier.

4 Discussion

As reported in (Macchione et al., 2019), emerging multimedia formats offer powerful tools for engaging risk managers, decision-makers and the public with flood hazards. However, engineers, geoscientists, and fluid mechanics have yet to employ these techniques when interacting with non-experts. Besides the integration of computer graphics to environmental science and serious game about flood hazard communication, this preliminary discussion assesses some pros and cons of the ReFlood proposal within a dialogue between mediation and regulation.

In a FRMP, the selection of the hydraulic model is typically delegated to an engineering firm through a public tender issued by risk management authorities. Flood hazard assessments generally begin with water depth estimations, while velocity data is required to refine evaluations of potential damage (European Parliament and Council, 2007), including injuries to people and damage to vehicles and engineered structures such as dams, roads, and buildings (Lazzarin et al., 2022). These complex models are often computationally intensive, making them impractical for generating new flood maps during public consultations, especially given their status as authoritative and robust tools.

In general, flood risk management mainly relies on calibrated hydrological modeling, where maximum flood extent and water depth are typically sufficient for hazard mapping (Teng et al., 2017). With appropriate parameterization, ReFlood height maps align well with high-water marks (see Figures 3, 4, and 5). As discussed with risk managers, ReFlood transforms the modeling approach by introducing interactive 3D video game simulations that can be presented, adapted during discussions, and even experienced firsthand by stakeholders. Consequently, we do not intend to incorporate computationally expensive velocity calculations and recommend using the ReFlood simulator primarily for mediation purposes.

Among the misunderstandings between river managers and stakeholders are, notably, the representation of structures (e.g. dams and buildings) on the one hand, and the strength of the streamlets on the other. First, regulatory modeling is conducted using a modified digital elevation model to account for potential dike breaches. Second, the small showcased streamlets are

not yet included in the flood zone atlas (DREAL Grand Est, 2010). Third, flood memory decays over time (Song et al., 2021). Over the next six months, the effectiveness of using ReFlood as a mediation tool will be assessed through consultation workshops and interviews conducted after these public meetings.

New insights are arising from preliminary discussions. Incorporating the runoff process – which has long been omitted in hydraulic models – helps to visualize flow directions and accumulation points. River managers then introduce the concept of regenerative hydrology. This can be effectively modeled and demonstrated by modifying the terrain using the terrain tools asset while running the simulator, as part of the broader effort to support resilient social-ecological systems (Buckton et al., 2023). Similarly, they are also interested in showcasing flood mitigation measures (flood diversion canal, dynamic slowdown, flood, expansion areas) to stakeholders.

More generally, adapting to climate change requires rapid information processing and decision-making to support a more resilient transformation of land use planning. The collaborative development of new scenarios and experiments is being initiated with watershed managers and eased by ReFlood. Indeed, less than 30 minutes are needed to set up a new scene on a given terrain by processing either a LIDAR cloud (for better accuracy) or a downloaded DTM. ReFlood is recognized as a promising boundary object, the standalone version of which can be managed by a third party, serving as a facilitation tool to enhance communication between risk managers and stakeholders. ReFlood will be presented in June during the Forum des acteurs du bassin de la Moselle (Forum of Moselle Watershed Stakeholders) through a joint presentation with a watershed manager.

Additionally, similar to the SeCom2.0 collaborative learning platform (Breuer et al., 2017), ReFlood could be used to teach flood risk concepts, including GIS handling and mapping, serious gaming, scene design, simulation, automation, and game-based development, while also encouraging reflections on science and society. These ideas will be tested in focused conferences with targeted scientific communities, such as I.S. RIVERS 2025, which gathers environmental scientists and stakeholders, ISAGA 2025, and the French mechanics congress CFM 2025.

5 Conclusion

ReFlood is a video game designed to foster a shared understanding of local flooding processes and their implications for risk reduction and urban planning. It is beginning to demonstrate its potential as an effective tool for educating decision-makers and raising awareness of flood risks and their consequences.

The approach's advantages – real-time visualization, robust water height computation, and easy scenario adjustments – are clearly outlined, alongside its limitations, such as inaccurate flow velocity. This transparency aims to build trust and engage river managers, decision-makers, and other stakeholders in flood hazard discussions. In addition, new insights, such as regenerative hydrology, flood mitigation, and the development of a multidisciplinary learning platform, are emerging.

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Breaking the Learning Curve in an Analog Serious Game with the SIMRED Framework: The City Blackout Game

Abstract

We introduce the Simplification and Reduction (SIMRED) framework, which supports the development of mini tutorial games for analog serious games to simplify and shorten the time needed to master the game. SIMRED focuses on learning the core mechanics and introducing the main game narrative without revealing unnecessary information that might affect the serious game's impact. We present how we applied SIMRED to optimize players' learning curve for the City Blackout Game, a real-time resource management and planning game, by proposing a tutorial mini-game that delivered a simple, engaging, and meaningful simulation of a reality-based scenario. Emergency management professionals played the games (tutorial and main game) during an international emergency conference. Participants considered it helpful and necessary to learn how to play the main game, which allowed them to visualize the scenario, try out the mechanics, and explore their space for decision-making. We also propose exploring the SIMRED framework for other serious game development projects and applications.

Keywords: Emergency management; Learning curve; Tabletop game, Tutorials; Serious games.

1 Introduction

Learning a game can be a pleasurable activity when there is a sense of achievement and progression (Koster, 2013), even when player profiles prefer specific experiences (Hunicke et al., 2004). However, the learning curve and the attention span required can disengage users, preventing them from achieving mastery and spoiling other enjoyable experiences (Sweetser & Wyeth, 2005; Xu et al., 2011; Lazzaro, 2009). In the case of analog games, the learning process can be even harder (Crabb & Heron, 2023; Boghian et al., 2019; Sato & de Haan, 2016). In the case of analog serious games, projects might suffer more from this introduction barrier effect. Even though serious games are not specifically developed to deliver fun experiences, they must be built to engage players in a way that makes learning faster and smoother. Often, there are clear time constraints when learning complex and longer games. The game development process should consider this as an engagement pitfall and aim to reduce the learning curve. Otherwise, the serious purposes of the games might never be achieved.

In this paper, we propose the Simplification and Reduction (SIMRED) framework as an initial formalization of the game design method to reduce the learning curve when introducing analog serious games with considerable complexity, especially when introducing new mechanics. SIMRED can be described as a scaffolding process for games.

The framework guides designers through the integrated creation process of a serious game and an associated minigame that serves as a scaffolding tutorial. The minigame allows players to familiarize themselves with the core mechanics of the game in a short time, reducing the barrier to entry and the overall negative impact of dealing with a novel game system. Minigames are short games (Stolovitch, 1978) typically nested within macrostructures, such as a main game or a traditional learning program (Rahmadi et al., 2021). They usually contain a limited number of objectives, and there is a heavy emphasis on “player participation and very little on the stimulus materials” (Stolovitch, 1978). Microgames are even shorter and more constrained games that mainly focus on one objective. Minigames often have different gameplay elements than the main game and provide unique objectives, rules, and gameplay styles that are simple and accessible (Kwalee, n.d.). The literature presents select studies on the use of minigames and microgames, including their educational applications (Lukosch et al., 2016; Rahmadi et al., 2021; Rahmadi et al., 2022). The use of minigames to introduce players to relevant aspects of the gameplay, lowering the overall complexity, has been reported (e.g. de Rosa & Strode, 2022). However, there has been limited formal attention on the use of minigames with objectives and gameplay styles aligned with the main game to serve as tutorials.

We will describe how the SIMRED approach was applied to the development of the City Blackout Game (CBG) and its corresponding tutorial (in the form of a minigame), the Snowstorm Game (SSG). Implementing the game allowed us to test its playability and how users activated the game mechanics. We established metaphorical relationships with the scenario addressed in the game, avoiding the learning pitfalls of disconnecting mechanics and narrative framed as ludonarrative dissonance (Hocking, 2009).

In Section 2, we frame the challenges of learning analog serious games, some techniques to reduce the learning curve, and the need to find new design solutions to tackle the challenge. Section 3 presents the SIMRED framework. Section 4 presents the design of the City Blackout Game and Snowstorm Game as a use case. In the discussion section (Section 5), we critically analyze our results based on the players’ perspectives and post-game survey responses. The conclusions (Section 6) summarize how the method can be replicated in the future for the development of other games, with the aim of creating tutorial experiences to learn a new serious game. Furthermore, Section 6 includes limitations and suggestions for future research.

2 Learning Analog Serious Games

Collaborative planning of serious games can be implemented either in analog, digital, or hybrid formats (Solinska-Nowak et al., 2018; Sousa et al., 2022a). Regardless of their format, the overall purpose and structures are similar from a conceptual perspective. Serious games pursue other purposes beyond entertainment (e.g. education and learning or analysis) while delivering fun experiences. Some authors frame them as games for purposes or applied games (Schmidt et al., 2015) to reinforce the requirement that there must be other aims beyond engagement and ways to verify and evaluate whether the games achieve their purposes during and after play (Mayer et al., 2014).

Analog serious games have advantages and disadvantages (Sousa et al., 2022a). Analog games can be easier, faster, and cheaper to develop, but they do not have automatic rule enforcement,

tend to require facilitation, and require physical space to play, which may limit the number of participants. However, these disadvantages can be deliberately transformed into advantages during development and implementation. An example is higher player agency (Duarte & Battaiola, 2017) and adaptability, even in real-time during gameplay (Sousa et al., 2022b). If players have higher agency and the game can be easily adapted (Duarte & Battaiola, 2017) (i.e. the spread and adoption of house rules or informal rule modifications by users in popular mass-market board games), the game can better fit user and context requirements. In an analog game that is played in a multiplayer experience, there are always indirect forms of collaboration and interactivity, such as for game bookkeeping and clarifications (Zagal et al., 2006; Zagal, 2020), especially if the game is designed to be fully collaborative and stimulate empathic experiences (Duarte et al., 2015; Sousa, 2023a).

Although serious games differ from entertainment games, which are sometimes described as orthogames (Elias et al., 2012), they share design features. To dive into game design, we need to analyze the literature, handbooks, and seminal guidelines to explore how it is possible to develop games that are easier to grasp so that users can fully explore a game's purposes. The literature and findings regarding modern board and tabletop gaming are growing, with research analyzing their design characteristics and players' experiences. As Arnaudo (2023) frames it, the tabletop revolution is reinventing board games, mixing styles and design approaches (e.g. *Terraforming Mars* and *Lisboa* have elegant mechanical systems). There is a continuous effort to integrate the mechanics and narrative of the games into meaningful and realistic playable models (Shipp, 2024), avoiding ludonarrative dissonance (Hocking, 2009). This balance between playable simplicity and innovative mechanics that simulate scenarios and virtual realistic environments (Sousa et al., 2019) is a viable option for analog serious games. There are several examples of modern board and tabletop modding to transform some of these entertainment games into serious games (Castronova & Knowles, 2015; Sousa, 2020a). Also, there have been attempts to use some of the game mechanics of these modern board games in serious games for learning (Triboni & Weber, 2018; Sousa, 2020b) and spatial planning (Sousa, 2024; Sousa, 2023b).

However, one ongoing difficulty is to make rule-based analog games easier to learn in time-limited settings, mainly those that are more complex and aim to simulate detailed scenarios, intricate interactions, and narratives. Although they use commercial and entertainment games, Sato & de Haan (2016) confirmed that repetition of play sessions is necessary to learn and use the game experience. Only after mastering the game rules and consciously taking non-random actions that reflect their choices can players explore all the serious game learnings and training take-aways. Sousa (2023c) proposes an approach where teachers select and adapt existing games, simplifying them and using them in several sessions where players can progressively address the game's complexity. Neither of these previous examples tackles the design and development process of an analog serious game and how to decrease the learning curve without requiring multiple play sessions and considerable time.

In the domain of entertainment tabletop games, games such as *Gloomhaven: Jaws of the Lion* (Childres, 2020) present tutorial rulebooks that enable players to read the rules and play simultaneously. Newer games such as *Sleeping Gods: Distant Skies* (Laukat, 2023) use streamlined rulebooks with a narrative graphical presentation resembling a comic book that introduces the

narrative and game mechanics. Going into hybrid approaches, *Destinies* (Gołębiowski & Miłurński, 2021) uses its digital app to help players learn and follow the rules. These are some of the attempts in the entertainment industry to simplify learning for analog games that result from considerable investment. In the field of serious games, when the purpose is to show and present early beta versions of the games, there might not be enough resources to deliver such sophisticated solutions. This paper proposes a framework to tackle this challenge during the development of an analog serious game.

3 Methodology

We developed two games focused on a snowstorm and a blackout to be deployed during an emergency management conference. The main game inspired the development of a tutorial game that helped the participants understand the game mechanics and the overall narrative. The tutorial addresses one of the core narrative elements that are explored in the full game and simplifies the overall map (size and events effects). The tutorial game does not reveal the narrative of future events nor present rule changes beyond the core mechanics. It includes a randomization system to allow replayability because players might want to repeat until they master the core game mechanics. The tutorial game delivers the necessary examples and repetitions to teach the core game mechanics, following Sato & de Haan's (2016) findings. It prepares the players for the main game challenge, applying the interconnected and progression of games approach proposed by the MBGTOTEACH framework principles (i.e. interconnecting sequences of different games to introduce new mechanics progressively) (Sousa, 2023c).

The tutorial was developed as an integrated approach to the game's overall development. The tutorial game should be meaningful and fast; it should avoid frustrating players and spark their interest in playing the main game. It should make users eager to play the second game, meaning it should be familiar for players after the tutorial and able to surprise them with novelty and better simulation of the scenario.

The conceptualization of the design approach and the analysis of the outcomes delivered a first-set framework for the development of analog serious games with meaningful playable tutorials. This method reduces the learning curve and maintains engagement.

The SIMRED framework allows the development of tutorial minigames that align with the main game they support, either departing from the concepts or simplifying the game mechanics and reducing the game world but maintaining the core mechanics that players need to master before starting the main game and entering the game narrative.

The development process is depicted in Figure 1. In the beginning, the tutorial was defined by the narrative, the scenario was linked to the goal of the serious game (1). Then, the tutorial was built and made into an interactive system by combining different game mechanics (2), as explained above. There is a connection between narrative (1) and meaningful play (3), the play space, and the game world. These spaces and virtual worlds are where players make decisions, react to feedback loops, and influence the game's progression. Meaningful play (3), when integrated with the mechanics that players need to activate in the system, influences operational complexity (4). When the mechanics have a meaning, are familiar, and can be interpreted from a thematic perspective and not just as a abstract system, we can reduce operational complexity

in games that propose innovative mechanical solutions. The relationship between narrative and mechanics defines a decision space complex enough to engage players (5).

To deliver a simplified game that works as a tutorial, we can aim to reduce the game's duration, reduce cognitive load and memory requirements, and include fewer options. Hence, the decision space is smaller and easier to grasp. Arguably, this simplification results in a smaller game world where fewer things are happening; tutorial games are clear and follow the same logic as the fully developed main game, which might help reduce the cognitive load of learning a new game. This simplified process of building the tutorial is more efficient if developed in parallel with the overall development of the full serious game (6), thus guaranteeing that both games are integrated and coherent.

Figure 1. SIMRED Framework to Create an Independent Tutorial Game to Support the Main Serious Game: Integrating the Core Game Mechanics Into the Game Narrative Without Revealing It.

4 Developing the City Blackout Game and the Tutorial Game

The game development process started with a scenario definition, which is related to the narrative dimension. The scenario was inspired by the Snowmageddon that affected Texas in 2021, a snowstorm that resulted in a long-term blackout (NCEI & NOAA, 2021). A subject matter expert involved in the actual event co-designed the narrative game dimension to ensure informational accuracy and increase the game's plausibility.

The learning objective of the main game is to show the impact and importance of preparedness and planning, as well as contain and deal with the cascading effects of a massive climate disaster. Furthermore, the game has been designed along the organizational goal of creating a simple, fast, and engaging experience that can serve as a means to showcase the usefulness of serious games to emergency management stakeholders. To this end, we created an educational game that was played during an emergency management conference.

To deliver these goals, we defined the game as a real-time collaborative analog game where the participants would manage emergency resources to address the progression and cascading

effects of the disaster at hand. The cascading effects were implemented by tech-tree mechanics, combined with events, resource cycles, and integration with a hexagonal grid map that represented a city inspired by Austin, Texas (USA). We followed the descriptions of Engelstein & Shalev's (2019) encyclopedia of mechanisms for tabletop games.

The real-time game dimensions resulted from using timers as resources and other types of timers to control the events. This design option aims to create stress and a sense of emergency. The collaborative gameplay aimed to deliver a collaborative experience to train communication and collective decision-making. In order to avoid the alpha player effect that constrains collaboration in tabletop games (Zagal et al., 2006; Allen & Appelcline, 2019) and foster the involvement of all players, the game had many resources and events challenging the players simultaneously.

Playtesting and lowering the learning curve

One of the most significant constraints of the game is the available time for the play sessions. Since the game's overall purpose is to show an example based on play experience to potential stakeholders, the game's duration has to be short. Without more available time and playing in a fuzzy, loud, crowded event, we needed to test solutions to reinforce immersion and help participants learn a complicated game. Hodent (2017), based on her research for the videogame industry, warns about the very low attention and high memory lapse users can have when dealing with a new game system. We therefore needed a tutorial that could be played in about 10 minutes to consider these limitations and reduce the overall cognitive load.

One possibility was to repeat the beginning of the game. However, since the game explores a scenario with events linked to real and unexpected situations, repeating the game's first stages might disengage participants and break the surprise effect.

The solution was to create a new game that introduced the players to the core mechanics of the main game. We tested whether creating an alternative game (tutorial) related to the main game would be a viable way to introduce newcomers to a new game system and reduce the complexity and learning curve of an analog serious game. The main game consisted of a sequence of events, some located in specific parts of the city (hex map) and others affecting the whole territory (cascade board), that required players to move emergency resources. The quantity of resources, events, cascading effects, and interconnections delivered a considerable real-time challenge. Players had to be familiar with the game mechanics and collaborate to perform well. Some events even alter some of the game rules as the game progresses. The tutorial game was developed following the SIMRED framework to prepare players for the challenges of the main game.

During the development of the CBG, we continuously simplified the game and ended up using only one type of relevant resource. In the case of Snowmageddon, only fire trucks could operate in extreme cases when the cities lack the resources to clear the snow from the roads. Even with this simplification, the first beta game in a prototype version revealed the complex activation mechanics. Sand timers represented the resources (fire trucks), with time effects linked to the time needed to reach the location of the event (hex map) and to activate (roll a die) and verify if the threat was successfully solved or not. The subsequent simplification was to remove data collection design elements from the game, such as tracking tokens and dice results. Even with-

out this aspect, players felt lost when playing the game just after a standard explanation of the rules.

Considering our development and playtest findings, we created a tutorial game called the Snowstorm Game (SSG). This game was designed to be played in 6 minutes plus time for explanation as part of the gameplay. The tutorial game introduced some limited effects of massive snow. Only the firetrucks could move according to the scenario, introducing the resource limitation for the main game (CBG). The hex map was simplified (3 hexes only), there were three resources to manage, and the cascade board (tech-tree mechanic) had only two rounds (3 minutes each) and five cascade boxes (interconnected events to address the cascade effects).

The CBG is longer, with three turns lasting 10, 5, and 3 minutes. Players have 8 resources to manage on a map with 19 hexes representing relevant elements of a city and its surroundings. The map includes topographical elements such as the river and mountains, as well as infrastructure such as the central hospital, bridges, highway, and water treatment plant. Land uses are also represented by color and background illustrations and icons (different urban densities, woodland, farmland, and industrial zones), as seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Examples of Mechanical/Narrative Simplifications and Reductions for the Case Study.

Main game	Tutorial game
City with 19 hexes	Town with 3 hexes
8 resources to manage	3 resources to manage
9 cascade boxes and associated effects	5 cascade boxes
11 event cards with extra game effects	3 random card events with no extra effects
3 turns of 10, 5, and 3 minutes	2 turns of 3 minutes each
Blackout as the result of the snowstorm	Standard effects of a snowstorm
Map elements that affect resource movement	No extra elements affecting movement

In the SSG, the role of the facilitator is to present the scenario: The forecast predicts a giant snowstorm in the region and there are no specific available resources to deal with this kind of threat and disaster. In the past, other cities had to use fire trucks to deal with emergencies (the Texas case). The facilitator explains the core mechanics of how to activate resources to resolve the threat situation (which are covered with black solving tokens to track progress and feedback) in the event cards (map) and cascade boxes (board with the tech-tree and income mechanic implemented as an analog algorithm that triggers events and tracks progress). The facilitator is expected to run the first round as a practical demonstration, asking the participants for help in making decisions and allocating resources. In the second round, participants play by themselves but continue to be supported by the facilitator. This solution introduces a gradual transition from the facilitator to the players, which gradually allows them to focus on a limited number of details.

Figure 2. The City Blackout Game Is a Complex Version of the Snowstorm Game (Table 1). The 19-Hexes-Large Board Represents the City. The Bottom Cascade Board (9 Cascade Boxes) Is a Tech-Tree Mechanic and Analog Algorithm That Tracks the Game State and Triggers Effects and Events.

5 Results

The games were played by nine teams ($n=56$) during the conference. Each game session (including the two games) lasted less than 1 hour. Participants completed a post-game survey asking about engagement, complication, and usefulness of playing the games while also including a specific question on the usefulness of the tutorial game (Table 2, Q3). From a game purpose perspective, we asked the players about the narrative's plausibility and overall game narrative arc and progression, including our modeling of game economy and the players' scope for action in the games. Each dimension was evaluated using a five-point Likert scale and additional text comments (open-ended questions). These questions aimed to understand the balance between playability and simulation, which should deliver an engaging experience and accurately address the topic at stake and the overall purposes of the serious game.

Table 2. Post-Test Questions and Their Purpose in the Context of Serious Games.

Qualitative question	Q#	Likert scale: 1	Likert scale: 5	Purpose of the question
How engaging were the games?	Q1	Not engaging	Very engaging	Engagement
How complicated were the games to play?	Q2	Easy	Hard	Complexity and learning curve
How useful was the first game to learn the second game?	Q3	Useless	Captured well	Effect of playing the tutorial
How did the games capture the experience of managing resources during an emergency?	Q4	Did not capture	Captured well	Balance between simulation and game design
How accurate were the games' details and scenario?	Q5	Not accurate	Very accurate	Accuracy and meaningful play
Other observations	Q6			General game experiences

We analyzed the resulting data, looking at the direct players' answers and performing a thematic and clustered analysis building on a grounded theory approach for game analysis (Charmaz, 2014; Farkas et al., 2020). This allowed us to extract data from the open questions.

Table 3 presents the results of the Likert scale answers to questions (Q) 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5. Although there were 57 participants, some surveys were blank and thus invalid. We considered the median value (\tilde{x}), mode (Z), and variation (σ^2) to analyze the participants' perspective.

Table 3. Survey Questions and Likert Scale Results (1 to 5).

Questions (Q#)	Valid (n)	Likert scale totals					\tilde{x}	Z	σ^2
		1	2	3	4	5			
How engaging were the games?	54	0	0	1	10	43	5	5	1.36
How complicated were the games to play?	54	1	5	27	20	1	3	3	0.90
How useful was the first game to learn the second games?	43	0	1	3	11	38	5	5	0.47
How did the games capture the experience of managing resources during an emergency?	42	0	1	8	22	11	4	4	0.56
How accurate were the games' details and scenario?	42	0	0	3	20	19	4	4	0.39

Table 4 presents the clusters resulting from the content analysis iterations for all the comments related to each question. We counted the number of valid survey comments. Not all participants (P#) who filled out the forms wrote comments; some only filled out the Likert scales. Moreover, some only addressed suggestions for improvement. The percentages express how many comments address that specific cluster, highlighting their relative importance regarding the number of total comments. This analysis allows us to interpret the comments quantitatively.

Table 4. Clusters For All the Comments In the Port-Game Survey Per Open-Ended Questions (Q#).

Q#	Identified clusters	+/-	Number of comments	% of total comments
Q1	Confusion and complexity	-	6	14.29%
Q1	Difficult to learn	-	2	4.76%
Q1	More time and elements to strategize	-	2	4.76%
Q1	Engaging and fun	+	17	40.48%
Q1	Easy to learn	+	2	4.76%
Q1	Engaging challenge	+	2	4.76%
Q1	Active participation and interaction	+	20	47.62%
Q1	Effective collaboration	+	16	38.10%
Q1	Time constrains positive effect	+	9	21.43%
Q1	Relevant content and simulation	+	14	33.33%
Q1	Play session and environment conditions	-	1	2.17%
Q2	Confusing actions and game algorithm	-	8	17.39%
Q2	Resource type and quantity	-	5	10.87%
Q2	Clear progression and learning curve	+	26	56.52%
Q2	Tutorial effect on learning and playing	+	8	17.39%
Q2	Facilitator effect on playability	+	6	13.04%
Q2	Easy to learn	+	11	23.91%
Q3	Overall confusing	-	5	12.82%
Q3	Helped	+	31	79.49%
Q3	Necessary	+	5	12.82%
Q3	Avoid rulebooks	+	1	2.56%
Q3	Visualization	+	1	2.56%
Q3	Hands-on	+	3	7.69%
Q3	Small-scale	+	6	15.38%
Q4	Lack of regional interactions	-	1	4.55%
Q4	Generalizations	-	7	31.82%
Q4	More uncertainty	-	4	18.18%
Q4	Not enough time to discuss	-	1	4.55%
Q4	Overall realistic	+	4	18.18%
Q4	Realistic injects	+	2	9.09%
Q4	Good simulation of resource management	+	8	36.36%
Q5	More details would improve	-	4	20.00%
Q5	Resource generalizations and inaccuracy	-	4	20.00%
Q5	Overall accurate	+	11	55.00%

Q#	Identified clusters	+/-	Number of comments	% of total comments
Q5	Great when considering limitations	+	4	20.00%
Q5	Simulate unpredictability	+	1	5.00%
Q6	Improving resource simulation	-	5	23.81%
Q6	Confusion and waiting time	-	1	4.76%
Q6	UI/UX improvements	-	1	4.76%
Q6	Very positive experience	+	8	38.57%
Q6	Good to introduce emergency management	+	6	28.57%
Q6	Reality- and science-based	+	3	14.29%
Q6	Identified future uses for the game	+	7	33.33%

6 Discussion

From an engagement and enjoyment perspective, we can conclude that participants evaluated the game positively (Table 3: $\bar{x}=5$; $z=5$; $\sigma^2=1.36$). From a simulation and accuracy perspective, the global values are also positive, with median values of 4 (Table 3, Q4 and Q5). Participants highlighted the relevance of the content and simulation (Table 4, Q1: 33.33%), the overall good quality of the simulation regarding resource management (Table 4, Q4: 36.36%), overall accuracy (Table 4, Q5: 55.00%) and even ability to account for operational limitations (Table 4, Q5: 20.00%). Some participants felt that the game contained excessive simplifications and generalizations (Table 4, Q5: 31.82%). However, this is unsurprising since the game was developed as an example of a serious game framework that is adaptable, delivers fast games, and focuses on cascading effects rather than on details of how to manage different types of resources. P30 clearly described this: "This is a good example and adequate for a fast game. However, the game would need more detail for more complex simulations." Furthermore, P13 addressed the non-optimal play environment: "There are a lot of moving pieces. I think playing it in an environment such as a classroom would ease that difficulty."

Considering the players' feedback, it appears that the tutorial game was successful as a fast playable exercise for learning the main game without reducing its positive impact. Participants reported (Table 4, Q3: 79.49%) that the tutorial (minigame) helped them to master the main game, as highlighted by the obtained score and small variation (Table 3, Q3: $\bar{x}=5$; $z=5$; $\sigma^2=0.47$). Without this tutorial stage, some participants said it would be almost impossible to play the CBG (Table 4, Q3: 12.48%). More than half of the comments about the game's complication and learning difficulty (Q2) reported that the learning curve for the session experience was progressive and adequate (Table 4, Q2: 56.52%). We should mention that players rated the game's complexity as average (Table 3, Q2: $\bar{x}=3$; $z=3$; $\sigma^2=0.90$), with 21 participants finding the game to be complicated (values of 4 and 5) and only 6 participants saying it was simple (assigning it values below 3). The analysis of the clusters in Table 3 shows that some users recognized the effects of the hands-on approach, i.e. that the use of a smaller-scale game and rule visualization were helpful in learning a new game.

Some participants found the games complicated but also stated that the tutorial and facilitation lowered the entry barrier. Only two out of 57 participants reported understanding everything by the end of the CBG, while others indicated that the game became simpler as they played and they learned along the way (Table 3, Q3: 56.52%).

Our case study allowed us to infer how to apply the SIMRED framework to one serious game (Steps 1 to 5 going towards 6, Figure 1). The game narrative (Step 1, Figure 1) was simplified; there was a big snowstorm, but the blackout was not an issue in this game. We did not want to reveal how and when the blackout would affect the gameplay as it is an important part of the scenario narrative and the mechanical effects on the CBG (Steps 1 and 3, Figure 1). Moving emergency resources in a city unprepared for these events/disasters was difficult. Emergency managers had to use firetrucks for this, which underscores why there was only one resource in the CBG. Using the firetrucks was the core mechanic to activate the sand timer to move and solve threats on the map (3 hexes) and the cascading board (only five cascade boxes) (Step 2, Figure 1). The narrative integration (Steps 1 and 3, Figure 1) and the role of the facilitator demonstrating the first round and allowing the participants to play the second round reinforced learning by example and repetition (Step 4, Figure 1) while playing a game and not just simulating a turn. In the tutorial game (SSG), the goal was to learn the mechanics and introduce the narrative; moreover, understanding the effects of decisions was also part of the learning process to help players perform well in the CBG (Step 5, Figure 1).

It appears that using a tutorial minigame based on the SIMRED framework of simplifying options and reducing the game world while maintaining core mechanics in order to introduce the narrative of the main scenario might be a valuable solution for learning to play such complicated and new game systems. Following the principles of the SIMRED framework helped lower the learning curve with the help of playable solutions such as minigames and tutorial games. Our systematic approach helps identify what game elements can be simplified. It clarifies that the game's goal is the core driving element and that a thematic integration of narrative and game mechanics is essential. However, due to the variety of serious games, further research is needed to fully assess how the SIMRED framework might be applied to other games.

As we have seen, some users found the combination of the two games challenging to understand (Table 4, Q2: 14.29%; Q3: 17.39%), even if, in the end, all confirmed that they understood the game and no one stated that the game failed to achieve its serious goals. Players may come from very different backgrounds, and having more experience playing games will reduce the learning curve to learning new games. The feedback from P9, a person with gaming experience, is very much on point: "Playing to learn is awesome! Not everyone loves a rulebook." The player's experience of the scenario and narrative will affect how they learn the game. Despite all this, players will have different learning experiences when playing with such a heterogeneous public. Having more time for deeper explanations and allowing peer learning in a cooperative game might solve some learning difficulties. The performance of the facilitator is also important to consider (demonstration, clearing doubts during gameplay, and reinforcing the narrative interpretation of the mechanical system), as some participants recognized (Table 4, Q2: 13.04%).

7 Conclusion

Professionals working with serious games must always consider users' attention span and cognitive load. These factors affect the learning curve for any game and can be a considerable barrier for newcomers. Without overcoming this barrier, the overall impact of the serious game, its ability to be engaging, and its ability to address serious goals can be jeopardized. Even the most promising game might fail in its purpose.

Analog games suffer even more from this barrier to entry. In the case of analog serious games, if they aim for deeper simulation and data collection, game complexity usually increases to the point where users might have difficulties understanding and mastering the game mechanics and easily understanding their decision space.

We proposed the SIMRED framework as a streamlined solution to develop tutorial games for analog serious games as an integrated game development process while developing the main game. We tested it with the City Blackout Game, played during an international emergency management conference with a diverse group of emergency managers and related experts. The games were engaging, and the proposed simulation and scenario were realistic and meaningful for the users. Players managed to complete both the tutorial and the main game in less than an hour at a busy and noisy event, all while also being able to fill out a post-game survey.

Participants recognized the usefulness of the tutorial (Snowstorm Game) in understanding and preparing to play the main game (City Blackout Game), detailing some of the deliberately designed elements such as the hands-on approach, the smaller scale, and the visualization of rule teaching. However, a minority of players were disengaged, and some only fully understood the game as it ended. Even if a game is a success for the majority of users, that same game might not be able to impact all users in the same positive ways. Redefining the game elements and delivering clear instructions are continuous improvements. Although the tutorial was efficient, considering the players' perspectives and their ability to play the game from the facilitator's perspective, it required a competent facilitator and a team of supporters to contain the adversities of the environment in which the game was played. Including higher player counts makes explaining the game challenging and requires even more supporting facilitation. Future research should focus on the facilitator's role and how it can be simplified and reduced, following the overall principles of the SIMRED framework in a way that makes the game design even more self-explanatory to users.

The SIMRED framework provides guidelines and a way to introduce scaffolding processes, while each game has specific traits. Reduction strategies might require more effort in some games than others. However, every game has core mechanics that players must learn and master. Aiming for the simplification and reduction of these core elements will help players learn the game and be ready for game progression and narrative development.

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